

The Management and Credit
Accessibility Challenges Facing SMEs in Ghana:
Proposing an Alternative Solution.

Abdul-Mumin Bapube Abubakar
B00354308

The School of Business and Creative
Industries

UWS London Campus

April 2023

Thesis submitted to
School of Business and Creative Industries,
University of West Scotland, London Campus,
in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of
Doctor of Business Administration

Date of Submission:

Sign...

Personal details withheld.

ABDUL-MUMIN BAPUBE ABUBAKAR

(B00354308)

Date: Sunday, 23rd April 2023

Personal details withheld.

Supervisors

Dr. Berhane Tewolde

School of Business and Creative Industries,
UWS London Campus.

Dr. Steve Smithson

School of Business and Creative Industries,
UWS London campus.

Examiners

Dr. Bernard Boateng

School of Business and Creative Industries,
UWS Lanarkshire Campus.

Professor Prabia Bhattacharya

Special Economics and Econometrics Centre
Heriot-Watt University Edinburgh

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to my late dad, Bapube Abubakar Baggyawie, for his immense love for education, although he was not educated. He insisted that my siblings and I must go to school and always believed that I would go far with my studies. Here I am today, although he is unfortunately not alive to witness this. May the Almighty Allah have complete mercy on his soul. Aameen!

DECLARATION

I, Abdul-Mumin Bapube Abubakar, thus certify that this thesis and the research work that underpins the analysis and findings were written and conducted solely by myself. I also certify that this thesis has never been submitted to or approved by any academic institution to confer a degree or other academic distinction. Finally, I declare that, to the best of my knowledge, all sources of information used in this thesis have been adequately recognized and referenced.

 Personal details withheld.

Abdul-Mumin Bapube Abubakar

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I foremost appreciate the Almighty Allah for providing me with good health, mental fortitude, and physical strength to help me survive and cope with the difficult times in my research.

I specially appreciate my director of studies, Berhane Tewolde (PhD), for his fatherly care and support throughout my research journey. His guidance and support day and night are next to none. It has helped me grow in confidence and sharpen my research skills. Also, another gratitude goes to my assessor Steve Smithson (PhD), for his outstanding reviews and inputs. I must say, they have helped me a lot in shaping my thesis. I also wish to thank the management and the rest of the staff of UWS for their various contributions to this life-changing journey.

Also, to my dear family, who has always supported and stood by me throughout my academic life. My mom, Zainab Issifu Jaayaw, for her prayers and outstanding motherly care; my late dad for his selflessness and dedication towards my education; my elder brother Hon Mohammed Bapube Johnson, for playing a fatherly role after the demise of our dad; my wife, Hawa Issaka Banda and for taking care of our beautiful kids whilst I study; my sister Miss Rahaina Bapube and the rest of my siblings for their support financially and morally. May Allah richly bless them all.

Moreover, my lovely friends, especially Hakeem Tahiru Ballubie (PhD), for his brotherly and mentoring support at any given time: Abdul Rahman Abu, a friend like a twin brother and all that supported me in diverse ways.

Finally, Mr and Mrs Esin of Amber Home Carers Limited for their unflinching support and for giving me a job to help cushion my studies. Mrs Victoria Garthwaite and her family for their support whenever it matters. GILL CHRIST for financial support towards my studies. May the Good Lord Bless You All.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

QE	Quantitative Easing
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
MSME	Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise
GERDFA	Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development and Financing Authority
MFI	Microfinance Institute
FI	Finance Institute
CI	Credit Institute
GEA	Ghana Enterprise Agency
NBSSI	National Board for Small Scale Industries
MASLOC	Microfinance and Small Loans Centre
RGD	Registrar General Department
NCCE	National Commission for Civic Education
PLWD	Persons Living with Disabilities
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
AfCFTA	Africa Continental Free Trade Agreement
LI	Legislative Instrument

ABSTRACT

Creating an enabling business environment has been a common challenge across most developing economies. A challenge that is attributable to the existing uncoordinated services of both government and non-governmental institutions providing financial and technical support to SMEs. The repercussions of the challenges above in Ghana are duplication of services and subsequent stagnation in SME development (Nkuah, Tanyeh and Gaeten, 2013). This quantitative study employs correlation and regression analysis to establish the causal effects between why SMEs are often refused credit (dependent variable) and SME history of loan default, SME purpose for loans & SME classification (independent variables). Interestingly, the chances of an SME being refused credit to rise by 0.627 points for every default in loan payment history, increase by 0.224 points for the purpose of loan acquisition; and decrease by 0.203 points based on the classification of the SME involved.

Moreover, all the predictors were confirmed to have causal effects on the criterion. Subsequently, this thesis proposes the merger of the Microfinance & Small Loans Centre (MASLOC), The Registrar General Department (RGD) and the Ghana Enterprise Agency (GEA). The outcome of the above merger would be Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development, and Financing Authority (GERDFA). The GERDFA will act as a one-stop centre for all activities of SMEs (business registration, advisory and financing services). Moreover, this thesis develops a strategic policy to guide the operations of GERDFA through a comparative study of the SME sectors of Ghana and Mauritius (see section 6.9.8). The above strategic change will include introducing nationally recognised SME management training and certification centres nationwide (see section 6.7.1). Only GERDFA would be mandated to issue licences for business operations and credit accessibility in Ghana. Consequently, the proposed strategy will ensure the free flow of credit (Fig. 6.3) to SMEs and eventually create some 1,137,611 SME jobs periodically (see section 6.1.4.2.1).

Contents

DEDICATION	III
DECLARATION	III
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	IV
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	V
ABSTRACT	VI
1.0 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Research Background	1
1.1.1 <i>Historical Overview of SMEs in Ghana</i>	4
1.2 Ease of Doing Business in Africa	5
1.3 Problem Statement.....	10
1.4 Objectives of the research	11
1.4.1 <i>General Objectives</i>	11
1.4.2 <i>Specific objectives</i>	11
1.5 Research Question	12
1.5.1 <i>Main research question</i>	12
1.5.2 <i>Specific research question</i>	12
1.6 Significance of the Study.....	13
1.7 Limitations of the Scope of the Research	14
1.8 Outline of the study	14
2.0 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	16
2.1 Literature	16
2.2 Small and Medium Enterprise: Definition.....	17
2.2.1 <i>Classification of SMEs by the Integrated Business Establishment Survey (IBES)</i>	19
2.2.3 <i>The average number of persons/percentages engaged per establishment by size in Ghana</i>	21
2.2.4 <i>Ten percent increment target on the average number of persons engaged per establishment</i>	22
2.2.5 <i>Further Job Creation Analysis</i>	24
2.3 The unemployment rate in Ghana.....	26
2.4 Operational Definition	27
2.5 SME Credit Accessibility Challenges in Africa	28
2.6 SME financing constraints in Ghana	32
2.6.1 <i>Interest Rate as a Financial Constraint</i>	33
2.7 Non-Financial Constraints Facing SMEs	35
2.7.1 <i>Management challenges facing SMEs</i>	35
2.7.2 <i>Competition and Lack of Innovation</i>	37
2.7.3 <i>Technology</i>	38
2.7.4 <i>Regulatory Framework</i> :	39
2.7.5 <i>Political Instability and Corruption</i>	39
2.7.6 <i>infrastructure</i>	41
2.7.7 <i>Human resource</i>	42
2.8 Relationship between SME Management and Credit Accessibility.	44
2.9 Research Gap	44

2.10 Conceptual Framework.....	45
3.0 CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION	48
3.1 Research Philosophy	48
3.2 Research Methodology and Design	49
3.2.1 Quantitative Research Design	49
3.2.2 Approach to theory development.....	50
3.2.3 Methodology	51
3.2.4 Research Strategy.....	52
3.2.5 Study Time Horizon.....	52
3.2.6 Techniques and Procedures	53
3.3 Research Coverage.....	54
3.3.1 Description of the selected place for the Study	54
3.3.2 Justification of the selected place for the Study	55
3.4 Targeted Stakeholders for the Study	56
3.4.1 Analysis of the shortlisted stakeholders	58
3.5 Targeted Population for the Study	59
3.5.1 Population sampling.....	60
3.6 Data Collection Methods	61
3.6.1 Primary Data Collection.....	61
3.6.2 Secondary Data Collection.....	62
3.7 Limitation of data collection	62
3.7.1 Resource limitation.....	62
3.7.2 Women Participation.....	63
3.7.3 Fear of Taxation.....	63
3.7.4 Covid-19 Impact.....	64
3.8 Objectivity, Reliability and Validity of Data.....	64
3.8.1 Objectivity.....	65
3.8.3 Reliability	66
3.8.4 Validity.....	66
3.9 Ethical issues in this study.....	67
3.9.1 Confidentiality and Anonymity	67
3.9.3 Non-maleficence and Beneficence.....	68
3.9.4 Justice and Inclusiveness.....	68
4.0 CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION	70
4.1 Data Analysis Process.....	70
4.1.1 Quantitative Data Analysis.....	71
4.1.2 'Descripto-Explanato-Evaluative' Statistics	71
4.1.3 Quantitative report writing	72
4.2 PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION	74
4.3 DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF RESPONDENTS	75
4.3.1 Sex of Respondents.....	76
4.3.2 Age of Respondents	77
4.3.3 Educational Level of Respondents	78
4.4 SME MANAGEMENT IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY OF GHANA	79
4.4.1 SME Managers Questionnaire (refer to appendix).....	80
4.4.2 SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions Questionnaire (refer to appendix).....	91
4.5 DATA ON SME FINANCING IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY	97

4.5.1 SMEs Managers questionnaire	98
4.5.2 SME Financing Institutions	110
4.6 THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON BUSINESSES	117
4.7 SME POLICY RECOMMENDATION DATA IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY	119

5.0 CHAPTER FIVE: TECHNICAL ANALYSIS: CROSSTABULATION AND TESTING FOR CORRELATION, REGRESSION AND CAUSALITY 123

5.1 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FROM THE SME MANAGERS QUESTIONNAIRE	123
5.2.1 Definition of terms	125
5.2.2 The impact of education on SMEs lifespan	127
5.2.3 How SMEs 'type' affects their Lifespan.....	130
5.2.4 The impact of SME classifications on their lifespan.....	131
5.2.5 The effects of SMEs classification on their staff Strength.....	134
5.2.6 How refresher training can help SMEs develop a business plan.....	136
5.2.7 The impact of refresher training on the practice of bookkeeping	138
5.2.8 The effects of Bookkeeping on SMEs' profit margin	140
5.2.9 The effects of refresher training on SMEs' profit margin	143
5.2.10 The impact of higher Education on SMEs' profit margin	145
5.2.11 The impact of credit on SMEs lifespan.....	148
5.2.12 The Effects of Credit on SMEs' Profit Margin.....	149
5.2.13 The impact of bookkeeping on SMEs credit application.....	151
5.2.14 How the gender of SMEs owner/manager affects their credit amount	153
5.2.15 How SMEs' perception of lending rates affects their interest in credit	156
5.2.16 SMEs' Perception of lending rates and how they raised their initial capital	158
5.2.17 How SMEs raise their initial capital and their sources of continuous funding	160
5.2.18 The effects of covid-19 and owner/managers perceive their businesses post covid.....	163
5.4 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FOR SME FINANCING INSTITUTIONS	171
5.4.2 The impact of the amount of credit accessed on the amount of credit recovered.....	171
5.4.3 The impact of background checks before crediting SMEs on credit recovery	173
5.6 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FOR SMEs SKILL DEV'T AND ADVISORY INSTITUTES	177
5.6.2 The impacts of post-service follow-ups on the number of clients	177
5.6.3 The effects of post-service follow-ups on client improvement	179

6.0 CHAPTER SIX: RESEARCH FINDINGS: SME MANAGEMENT AND CREDIT POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS..... 184

6.1 THE SMEs- DEMAND SIDE	184
6.1.1 Diagnostic Analysis of SMEs in the Wa Municipality.....	184
6.1.2 Recommendations based on the WEAKNESSES revealed by the SWOT analysis.....	185
6.1.3 Recommendations based on the THREATS revealed by the SWOT analysis.....	186
6.1.4 Recommendations on how to maximise the OPPORTUNITIES by the SWOT analysis.....	190
6.2 THE LIFECYCLE OF SMES IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY.....	193
6.2.1 Service/Product Lifecycle Model.....	194
6.2.2 Recommendations Based on the Product Lifecycle Model.....	195
6.2.3 Increasing SMEs Profitability Through Product Management	196
6.3 THE FINANCIERS OF SMEs – (CREDIT INSTITUTES).....	199
6.3.1 Sources of Credit for SMEs.....	199
6.4 THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CREDIT INSTITUTES (CIs) AND SMES	203
6.5 THE PROVIDERS OF TECHNICAL SUPPORT TO SMES.....	204

6.5.1 Types of SME Advisory Services	204
6.6 THE GOVERNMENT, COVID-19 AND SMEs.....	204
6.6.1 The ‘Mandala’ Analysis of the Ghanaian SMEs Industry	205
6.7 PROPOSED STRATEGIC CHANGE FOR SMES MANAGEMENT AND CREDIT ACCESSIBILITY	206
6.7.2 National SMEs Training and Certification.....	208
6.7.3 Publicity and Commitment	209
6.7.4 Effectiveness and Usefulness of the Proposed Strategies.....	209
6.7.5 Implementation of the Proposed Strategies.....	211
6.8 COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GHANAIAN AND MAURITIAN SMEs.....	213
6.8.1 Ghana’s Draft SMEs Policy.....	214
6.9 Ten-Year Master Plan for The SMEs Sector in Mauritius	217
6.9.1 Overview	217
6.9.2 Institutional Framework	218
6.9.3 Regulatory Framework	218
6.9.4 Strategic Directions.....	220
6.9.5 Main Constraints and their implementation strategies	220
6.9.6 Observations from the SMEs policy documents of Ghana and Mauritius	224
6.9.7 Comparing the Vision, Mission and Objectives of SMEs Policies of Ghana and Mauritius....	225
6.9.8 Proposed Strategic Policy Guide for Ghanaian SMEs with Insight	227
from Mauritius.....	227
6.9.9 Justification of the Proposed Strategic Guide.....	229
CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	231
7.1 CONCLUSION.....	231
7.1.1 Chapter One.....	231
7.1.2 Chapter two	231
7.1.3 Chapter three.....	232
7.1.4Chapter four.....	232
7.1.5 Chapter five.....	233
7.1.6 Chapter Six.....	233
7.2 RECOMMENDATION	234
7.2.1 Recommendations for SME Managers/Owners	234
7.2.2 Recommendations for SME Credit Institutions.....	235
7.2.3 Recommendation for SME Skill and Advisory Institutes	235
APPENDICES	247
APPENDIX A: QUESTIONNAIRES FOR SMEs.....	247
APPENDIX B: QUESTIONNAIRES FOR SME FINANCING INSTITUTIONS	254
APPENDIX C: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SME SKILL DEVELOPMENT AND ADVISORY ORGANIZATIONS ...	258
APPENDIX D: CHINA ON THE VERGE OF BECOMING THE WORLD’S LARGEST ECONOMY BY 2030 ...	262
APPENDIX E: INTEREST RATES OF AFRICAN COUNTRIES	262

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2-1: Graphical illustration of the SMEs in Ghana by size and percentage.....	20
Figure 2-2: The representation of persons employed by establishment size	21
Figure 2-3: projected employment figures.....	25
Figure 2-4: unemployment trend in Ghana	26
Figure 2-5 Historical interest rates in Ghana	35
Figure 2-6: Traders selling on the street in the Kumasi Central Market, Ghana.	42
Figure 2-7: Conceptual framework developed after critically reviewing the literature.....	46
Figure 3-1: The methodological path of this study highlighted in orange.....	52
Figure 3-2: The Map of Wa Municipal	55
Figure 4-1: SME management that has received capacity-building training.....	85
Figure 4-2: SMEs with a business plan.....	87
Figure 4-3: What happens if an SME defaults on loan repayment	106
Figure 4-4: How the SMEs raised their start-up capital	107
Figure 4-5: Constraints to SME growth.....	109
Figure 5-1: A sample chi-square test result	125
Figure 5-2: Graphical representation of Pearson's correlation coefficient.	126
Figure 6-1: The Hoover of Financial Regulation.....	189
Figure 6-2: Employment by SMEs in Ghana without a Policy Guide.....	191
Figure 6-3: Employment by SMEs in Ghana with the proposed Policy Guide	193
Figure 6-4: Service/Product Lifecycle	194
Figure 6-5: Proposed hybrid SMEs banking framework	203
Figure 6-6: Yin and Yang's Mandala Symbol	206
Figure 6-7: A proposed strategic framework for SMEs Management and Credit Accessibility	207
Figure 6-8: KURT Lewin's vs Kotter's eight models of change	213
Figure 6-9: Strategic guide for Ghanaian SMEs regarding Mauritius	227
Figure 6-10: The Strategic Map of SMEs.....	229

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1-1: Doing Business indicators with their corresponding areas being measured	7
Table 1-2: Ease of doing business index for the 2020 Top 18 African Countries.....	9
Table 2-1: Definition of SMEs by the number of employees.....	18
Table 2-2: Definition and Classification of MSMEs by IBES in Ghana.	19
Table 2-3: Average number of persons engaged per establishment in Ghana.....	22
Table 2-4: Average number of persons employed at a projection of10%	23
Table 2-5: real interest rate values for African countries (see appendix for complete list).....	34
Table 2-6: The corruption perception index of African countries (see appendix for full list).41	
Table 3-1: Summary of the chosen research route for this study	53
Table 3-2: SME stakeholder groups	57
Table 4-1: Firm type and percentage of SMEs involved	80
Table 4-2: SMEs' number of years in business.....	81
Table 4-3: SMEs' quarterly profit	88
Table 4-4: SMEs advocating for the creation of a business management training Centre	89
Table 4-5: Sources of SMEs credit	100
Table 4-6: Highest amount SME ever borrowed	103
Table 4-7: causes of loan default among SMEs.....	104
Table 4-8: How SMEs find lending rates	105
Table 4-9: Consequences of loan default.....	106
Table 4-10: Percentage of credit SMEs accessed from credit institutions.....	111
Table 4-11: Credit accessibility requirements	112
Table 4-12: Occasional basic financial management training for SMEs.....	114
Table 4-13: Common reasons for SME loan default	115
Table 4-14: Bridging the gap between credit institutions and SMEs	116
Table 4-15: SME Managers' policy recommendations.....	120
Table 4-16: SME Financing Institutions policy recommendations	121
Table 4-17: SME Advisory Institutions Policy Recommendations.....	122
Table 5-1: Selected questions for crosstabulation	124
Table 5-2: A guide on the strength of correlation.....	127
Table 5-3: The crosstabulation of the educational level of the SMEs management team versus the length of time they have been operating.	128
Table 5-4: Chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.3	129

Table 5-5: crosstabulations of a firm (SME) type and the number of years it's been in operation	130
Table 5-6: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.5	131
Table 5-7: Firm (SME) classification and the number of years it's been in operation.....	132
Table 5-8: Chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.7 above	133
Table 5-9: SME classification with their required number of staff	134
Table 5-10: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.9.....	135
Table 5-11: crosstabulation of continuous professional development training for SME staff and the existence of a business plan at the SMEs	136
Table 5-12:The chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.11 above	137
Table 5-13: crosstabulation of Continuous Professional Development training of SME staff and the practice of standard bookkeeping.....	139
Table 5-14: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.13.....	140
Table 5-15: The cross-tabulated results of the practice of standard bookkeeping by SMEs and their percentage quarterly profit.....	141
Table 5-16:chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.15.....	142
Table 5-17: crosstabulation of the continuous professional development training of SME staff and SME's percentage quarterly profit.....	144
Table 5-18: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.17 above.	145
Table 5-19: crosstabulation of the impact of an SME management team member's highest educational qualification and its quarterly profit percentage.....	146
Table 5-20: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.19.....	147
Table 5-21: crosstabulation of SME loan acquisition status and how long the SME has been in business.....	148
Table 5-22: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.21	148
Table 5-23: crosstabulation of SME loan acquisition status and SME percentage quarterly profit.....	150
Table 5-24: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.23 above	151
Table 5-25: Crosstabulation of the practice of bookkeeping and SME loan application status	152
Table 5-26: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.25.....	153
Table 5-27: Crosstabulation of the gender of SME owner and the highest amount of loan borrowed	155
Table 5-28: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.27 above	156
Table 5-29: Crosstabulation of interest rates and the willingness of SMEs to apply for loans	157

Table 5-30: chi-square and correlation test results support Table 5.29 above.....	157
Table 5-31: Crosstabulation of how SMEs raise their initial capital and how SMEs find lending rates	159
Table 5-32: chi-square and correlation test results support Table 5.31 above.....	160
Table 5-33: How initial capital was raised versus continuous sources of funding SMEs	161
Table 5-34: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.33.....	162
Table 5-35: Crosstabulation of the effect of covid 19 on SMEs and how the SME owners perceive their businesses after covid 19.....	164
Table 5-36: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.35 above	165
Table 5-37: Correlation and Regression test results on SME Owner/Managers	166
Table 5-38: selected questions from the SME financing institution’s questionnaire for crosstabulation	171
Table 5-39: Accessed credit by SMEs versus recovered credit by the financial institute	172
Table 5-40: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.39 above	173
Table 5-41: SME background checks before loans accessibility versus loan recovery rates	174
Table 5-42: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.41 above	175
Table 5-43: Regression Analysis for SME Financing Institutes.....	176
Table 5-44: selected questions from the SME skilled development and advisory institute’s questionnaire for crosstabulation	177
Table 5-45: post-service follow-up versus clients served.....	178
Table 5-46: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.45 above	178
Table 5-47: post-service follow-up versus annual percentage client improvement	180
Table 5-48: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.47 above	180
Table 5-49: Correlation and regression analysis for SME Advisory Institutes	181
Table 6-1: SWOT Analysis of the SMEs industry.....	185
Table 6-2: The Ansoff Matrix illustration of the SMEs industry in Ghana.....	198
Table 6-3: Average lending rates of universal banks compiled by Bank of Ghana, July 2021.	200
Table 6-4: Average lending rates of Microfinance Institutes in Wa Municipal	201
Table 6-5: Effect of Covid-19 on some Stakeholders in the SMEs industry.....	205
Table 6-6: perception of SMEs Stakeholders post covid-19	205
Table 6-7: Applying the SAF criteria to the proposed strategies.....	210
Table 6-8: Starting a Business in Ghana.....	215
Table 6-9: Strategic directions and thematic areas	216
Table 6-10: SME Support Institutes in Mauritius.....	218

Table 6-11: Starting a Business in Mauritius.....	219
Table 6-12: Challenges and strategic policies on regulatory & institutional framework of SMEs.....	221
Table 6-13: challenges and strategic policies on national entrepreneurship.....	222
Table 6-14: challenges and strategic policies on human capital & skill Development	222
Table 6-15: challenges and strategic policies on innovation technology transfer & Green SMEs.....	223
Table 6-16: challenges and strategic policies on Access to Finance & Equity	223
Table 6-17: challenges and strategic policies on Marketing and regulatory exports capacity building	224
Table 6-18: SMEs Policy Vision Statements for Ghana and Mauritius	225
Table 6-19: SMEs Policy Mission Statements for Ghana and Mauritius	226
Table 6-20: Objectives of the SMEs Policy Guides for Ghana and Mauritius.....	227

1.0 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Earmarked as the primary source of growth in the world's economy, Small and Medium Enterprises (henceforth SMEs) are proven mechanisms for accelerating economic growth and development. SMEs are also noted for their high tendency to eradicate social-economic hardships and reduce poverty to its barest minimum (Chowdhury, Azam, and Islam, 2013). An estimated 60% of the private sector employment globally is created by SMEs, representing more than 95% of businesses around the globe (Ayyagari, Demirguc-Kunt, Maksimovic, 2011). Asian countries have justified the need for developing countries like Ghana to pay critical attention to SMEs, especially concerning their financing and management. Almost 82% of employment in Bangladesh is provided by SMEs which contribute 50% of the Gross Domestic Product (henceforth GDP). Also, Nepal relies heavily on SMEs, which form about 98% of its firms and contribute 63% to GDP (Chowdhury et al., 2013).

Moreover, India is tipped to become the world's second-largest economy by 2030 after China through SMEs, with Indonesia also making a breakthrough into the top five (Curran (2019). Interestingly, Japanese SMEs are characterised by their consciousness of belonging to a group. The linkages among the SMEs in Japan have resulted in a unique small business sector popularly known as *Chusho Kigyō* (Dana, 1998). Moreover, Japanese SMEs are said to be inspired by their core religious values of diligence, frugality and hard work. They account for about 99% of businesses and create over 70% of employment (Kuwahara, Yoshino, Sagara, and Taghizadeh-Hesary, 2016).

Last but not least, Korea has a long, humble and successful history of SME development which has eventually pushed them to be part of the world's top economies (Sung, Kim and Sungyang,

2016). The success stories of the countries mentioned above are primarily attributed to their unflinching culture of ensuring the existence of solid synergies between SMEs and the formal sector. It is not a surprise that Reid (2019) reported that SME dominations influence British Airways' business travel routes around the globe in those destinations.

The story of SMEs is not different to the youthful African continent, where above 90% of businesses are SMEs, mainly employing the youth and women (Fjose, Grunfeld and Green, 2010). The situation in Africa is more critical than earlier because of its high rate of unemployment coupled with a fast-growing workforce. In 2017, the United Nations estimated 40% of Africa's population to be between (0-14) years old, potentially graduating over 900 million into the working class by 2050 (World Economic Forum, World Bank, African Development Bank, and OECD. 2015). The above situation is more alarming than ever due to inadequate investment in African SMEs. The consequences are; underproduction and the inability to network to build strong brands that can compete globally.

Moreover, Africa has long been tagged as a high-risk investment destination globally (International Trade Centre, 2018; see Collier, 2009). The above perception about African SMEs is further worsened because, globally, investment into SMEs (Small businesses) is generally considered risky (ibid). Because of the above, the African continent is left with a vast difference to cover regarding investing in SMEs (International Trade Centre, 2018). A difference that the local investor community cannot handle alone.

The good news is that trade and investment provide African SMEs and those in the diaspora who choose to invest in Africa with a vast untapped commercial opportunity. Africa invests only a fraction of its GDP, accounting for 23.5%. To meet the continent's development goal, it is crucial to invest 37% of its GDP (Ibid). The above implies that by 2040, a gap of \$11.4 trillion will have been created (Ibid). The African investor community could not fill the above

gap alone. However, it would require the presence of overseas investors to take advantage of the opportunity and help close the investment gap. Attracting investors means gathering accurate and reliable data on SMEs' strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT). Making the above data readily available to potential investors would guide them to make choices that are effective and supported by evidence (Ibid). See section 6.1.1.1 for the application of SWOT analysis to Ghanaian SME.

In Ghana, SMEs account for 92% of businesses, contribute 70% of GDP and employ around 85% in the manufacturing industry. The above statistics make SMEs necessary in employment creation, alleviating poverty (Quaye et al., 2014) and macro-economic development. Moreover, SMEs are highly recognised for their essential role in economic development. Most Ghanaian communities, sectors, gender, and cultures are gainfully employed through SMEs. According to the Korean Development Institute, in a study conducted in 2008 dubbed 'Building the Foundation for SME Development in Ghana', an estimated 90% of all businesses in Ghana are SMEs and employ 60% of the working class. The 2008 United Nations report on Ghana also confirmed the above statistics.

Despite some significant efforts by Ghana's governments through monetary policy and financial sector reforms (Irwin and Scott, 2010), SMEs in Ghana still do not get the needed attention and are bedevilled with managerial and financial accessibility challenges (Abor and Biekpe, 2006). The above challenges prevent Ghanaian SMEs from; operating at full capacities, producing enough to support the Ghanaian economy, employing more teaming youth and competing globally. According to Nkuah et al. (2013), lack of the right managerial skills, limited credit accessibility, high-interest rates and collateralisation are still barriers facing SMEs. These challenges can be viewed as a demand and supply scenario. On the demand side are the SMEs who are viewed as not competitive enough with their demands due to

challenges like; not being formally registered, not having enough equity, not possessing the right management abilities, and generally classified as risky ventures.

On the other hand, the supply side is the financial institutions that prefer to credit less risky firms than the 'risky' SMEs in a 'risky' business environment (Africa).

This thesis seeks to address effective ways of building the capacities of Ghanaian SMEs to help close the demand and supply gap between SMEs and financial institutions. The above will allow SMEs to competitively meet the demanding needs of financial institutions, government grants and other donors and stakeholders. It will also help in bridging the supply gap by proposing alternative solutions.

1.1.1 Historical Overview of SMEs in Ghana

The concept of promoting SMEs in Ghana has been around since 1970. However, not much was done at the time. The Office of Business Promotion and the Ghana Enterprise Development Commission (GEDC) were among the critical entities established to assist SMEs' development. The primary goal of GEDC was to help Ghanaian entrepreneurs break into industries that foreigners previously dominated. It also included technical and financial support for small-scale industries (Kayanula and Quartey, 2000).

Since its inception in 1983, the Economic Recovery Program (ERP) did expand the institutional assistance for SMEs until it was no more. To address the needs of small enterprises, the Ministry of Industry, Science, and Technology formed the National Board for Small-Scale Industries (NBSSI), now Ghana Enterprise Agency (GEA). The NBSSI established an Entrepreneurial Development Program to train and help people with entrepreneurial skills who want to start their businesses (Abor and Biekpe, 2006). Also, in 1987, the Ghana Appropriate Technology Industrial Service (GATIS) was established for the industrial sector. The mission of GATIS was to oversee the country's Intermediate Technology Transfer Units (ITTUs).

GATIS intended to address small-scale industrial concerns at the grassroots level by transferring appropriate technologies to small-scale and informal industries. The ITTUs in the various regions were designed to improve the engineering skills of small-scale manufacturing and service enterprises that performed car repairs and related work (Kayanula and Quartey, 2000).

In 2003, the Kufour-led government created a new Ministry for Private Sector Development to focus on developing the SME sector. Again, in 2004, under the president's office, the Microfinance and Small Loans Centre (MASLOC) was created to cater for the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana (Abor and Biekpe, 2006). NBSSI (now GEA) and MASLOC are still operational, providing almost the same services (duplicated) to SMEs. This study makes a strategic proposal for the efficient operation of NBSSI (now GEA) and MASLOC in chapter six. In 2014, The Mahama-led administration assigned a minister in charge of Public-Private Partnerships to help facilitate the development of SMEs. In 2017, the Akufo Addo-led administration also created the Ministry for Business Development to help promote the private sector. Nonetheless, Ghana is still poorly placed on the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business index (International Trade Centre, 2018).

1.2 Ease of Doing Business in Africa

Doing Business is born out of the principle that when rules are spelt in an economy, every economic activity can benefit positively in such an environment. Rules that ensure that partners bonded by contracts are free from abuse and arbitrariness; rules that ensure smooth mediations for commercial disputes; rules that make provision for economic actors to do exchanges voluntarily without any difficulty. Such rules' accessibility, transparency, and efficiency ensure effectiveness in boosting growth and development in the environment under consideration. With the proper business rules, individuals or groups with passion and the right creativity can

easily create new businesses. Firms doing well also can employ more people through investment and expansion (Doing Business, 2020, p18).

The Doing Business data primarily focuses on how local SMEs' daily management and running are affected by government policies. The above ensures transparent, efficient, and practical regulation that will grow SMEs. In each sampled 190 economies, comparable quantitative measures using standardised case studies were employed among SMEs in their biggest business cities based on 12 regulatory areas. However, only ten are included in the scoring and ranking by The Doing Business Index. These are: starting a business, getting credit, paying taxes, getting electricity, registering property, dealing with construction permits, protecting minority investors, trading across borders, enforcing contracts, and resolving insolvency. The two non-scoring and ranking regulations are; regulation on contracting with the government and employing workers (ibid).

Table 1.1 below outlines the various regulatory indicators employed by doing business against the specific items measured to score the indicators in each of the 190 globally selected economies. Time, Procedure and Cost are the common indicators. 'Time' is directly mentioned among nine (9) of the twelve (12) indicators. The above emphasises the importance of time in running a business and that 'time is money'. The less time spent on an indicator, the easier to register a business. Another indicator that is highly rated is 'cost'. It appeared among nine (9) indicators in both direct and indirect forms. The primary aim of every entrepreneur is to minimise costs and maximise profit. When the cost of doing business becomes high, it breeds general hardships in the economy as business managers transfer the cost to consumers. Also, it retards the growth of businesses as they cannot meet their essential expenditure with ease and still have additional room to improve. The lesser the cost of doing business, the better it is for SME owners, the general public, and the economy scores high marks for the Doing Business ranking. The last highly flagged item is 'procedure'. It appeared under nine (9) indicators, both

directly and indirectly. The 'Procedure' of registering a business is vital for business owners because it involves time and cost. The longer the procedure in registering a business, the more time one spends, and the more money will likely be spent or lost. Cumbersome business registration procedures lead to frustrations and discourage new entrants to the formal SME sector. When the above becomes the case, people either start businesses illegally or do not venture into business. The easier the procedures in meeting the twelve (12) indicators, the better for the SMEs and the Ghanaian economy.

Table 1-1: Doing Business indicators with their corresponding areas being measured

INDICATOR SET	WHAT IS MEASURED
Starting a business	Procedures, time, cost, and minimum paid-in capital to start a limited liability company for men and women
Dealing with construction permits	Procedures, time, and cost to complete all formalities to build a warehouse and the quality control and safety mechanisms in the construction permitting system
Getting electricity	Procedures, time, and cost to get connected to the electrical grid; the reliability of the electricity supply; and the transparency of tariffs
Registering property	Procedures, time, and cost to transfer a property and the quality of the land administration system for men and women
Getting credit	Movable collateral laws and credit information systems
Protecting minority investors	Minority shareholders' rights in related-party transactions and corporate governance
Paying taxes	Payments, time, and total tax and contribution rate for a firm to comply with all tax regulations as well as post-filing processes
Trading across borders	Time and cost to export the product of comparative advantage and to import auto parts.
Enforcing contracts	Time and cost to resolve a commercial dispute and the quality of judicial processes for men and women
Resolving insolvency	Time, cost, outcome, and recovery rate for commercial insolvency and the strength of the legal framework for Insolvency
Employing workers	Flexibility in employment regulation
Contracting with the government	Procedures and time to participate in and win a works contract through public procurement and the public procurement regulatory framework.

Source: Doing Business, (2020 p19)

Table 1.2 below illustrates the best eighteen (18) business destinations in Africa by rank in 2019 and 2020. Mauritius sat top of Africa and made a tremendous improvement by moving from 20th in the world in 2019 to 13th in 2020, making it the best business-friendly economy in Africa. Mauritius remains Africa's best because they continually tried to tackle their deficiencies, as spelt by the Doing Business Index. Four major regulations were improved: construction permits, property registration, contract enforcement, and resolving insolvency. These have gone a long way to improve investment security and soften the grounds for SMEs in Mauritius. Rwanda remains second in Africa but dropped significantly from 29th to 38th worldwide. Morocco moved seven (7) steps from 60th in 2019 to 53rd in 2020 on the global stage but remains 3rd on the African ranking. Kenya improved by 2.89%, moving from its 2019 ranking of 61st to 56th in 2020 worldwide while maintaining fourth (4) on the African continent. The remaining countries who made reforms on the indicators are Tunisia (2.59%), South Africa (0.97%), Zambia (1.82%), Botswana (0.80%), Togo (7.10%), Namibia (0.87%), Malawi (1.31%), Ivory Coast (2.70%), Egypt (1.54%), Uganda (2.94%) and Ghana (0.78%). It is crucial to highlight Togo because it made headlines by appearing among the economies that made the most improvement (7.10%) in 2020. Also worth mentioning is Nigeria (4.01%; 136th in world ranking), although that was not enough to get through the best 18 in Africa (Doing Business, 2020, p13). Ghana, the host of the newly agreed African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) secretariat, managed an overall improvement of 0.78% and could not hold on to its positions but slipped from 11th to 17th on the African ranking and four (4) steps backwards to 118th on the 2020 global ranking (ibid p16).

Despite the general improvement, some economies paid less attention to making positive business reforms and, as a result, scored negatively for 2020 the Doing Business ranking. Seychelles (-0.71%), Djibouti (-1.52), and Lesotho (-1.20) are the countries that made awful improvements. Surprisingly, some notable African economies like; Nigeria (4.01%; 136th in

world ranking), DR Congo (-0.65% and 183rd on the world ranking), Sudan (-4.04% and 171st on the world ranking), and Ethiopia (-1.06 and 159th on the world ranking) could not make it to the top African eighteen (18) (ibid).

Table 1-2: Ease of doing business index for the 2020 Top 18 African Countries

Economy	World Rank (1–190)		Ease of doing business score (0–100)		
	DB2019	DB2020	DB2019	DB2020	Percentage difference
Mauritius	20	13	79.58	81.5	1.92
Rwanda	29	38	77.88	76.5	-1.38
Morocco	60	53	71.02	73.4	2.38
Kenya	61	56	70.31	73.2	2.89
Tunisia	80	78	66.11	68.7	2.59
South Africa	82	84	66.03	67.0	0.97
Zambia	87	85	65.08	66.9	1.82
Botswana	86	87	65.40	66.2	0.80
Togo	137	97	55.20	62.3	7.10
Seychelles	96	100	62.41	61.7	-0.71
Namibia	107	104	60.53	61.4	0.87
Malawi	111	109	59.59	60.9	1.31
Ivory Coast	122	110	58.0	60.7	2.70
Djibouti	99	112	62.02	60.5	-1.52
Egypt	120	114	58.56	60.1	1.54
Uganda	127	116	57.06	60.0	2.94
Ghana	114	118	59.22	60.0	0.78
Lesotho	106	122	60.60	59.4	-1.20

Source: Doing Business database, (2019 p5) and (2020 p4).

Note: The closeness of these economies to the international best practices of doing business was the primary reference point for the rankings. Those with higher scores in 2020 were ranked best.

1.3 Problem Statement

Amid shallow financial markets and high interest culminating from rising inflation, SME entrepreneurship has become one of the main alternatives to investing excess liquid money holding in Ghana and the sub-Sahara of Africa (Quartey, Turkson, Abor, and Iddrisu, 2017). The above has led to several Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) across Ghana and the sub-Saharan African countries. However, growth has eluded most of these businesses mainly because of the lack of access to adequate credit, managerial competence (financial numeracy and basic business management skills), availability of the needed technology and equipment, and a reasonably friendly business environment. (Steel and Webster, 1991; Aryeety et al., 1994; Gockel and Akoena, 2002).

Ibid reported that 38% of SMEs in Ghana cited credit accessibility as their primary challenge. Parker supported this argument in 1995 when access to credit was on top of the list of his respondents in a survey he conducted to ascertain the challenges facing SMEs. According to Nkuah et al. (2013), Micro and small business easily mix their personal and business finances due to a lack of basic managerial knowledge and skills in proper accounting principles and procedures. As earlier as 1982, Schmitz documented a lack of managerial ability as a primary reason most SMEs could not expand and access credit in developing countries.

While earlier researchers concentrated on mainly outlining the credit accessibility challenges for SMEs (Nkuah et al., 2013), not much has been done to comprehensively address the demand and supply challenge between SMEs and the financial institutions in Ghana. This study

seeks to improve SME access to credit in Ghana by developing a framework to address the demand and supply challenges SMEs face in Ghana and beyond.

Also, this research is unique because it looks at the difficulty in accessing credit from the perspective of managerial incompetence by SME operators. It will further make a policy contribution through consultancy, employing several business management models, to ensure the sustainability of SMEs' growth in Ghana. Also, the study will propose that the capacity of existing SMEs should be built to manage their finances effectively and attract credit. It would further suggest comprehensive business management training for potential entrepreneurs to be made a requirement for accessing SME loans or grants in Ghana. Finally, it will reveal how SMEs can be used to curb unemployment in Ghana.

1.4 Objectives of the research

1.4.1 General Objectives

This research explores the managerial challenges and difficulty in Ghana's credit access by SMEs and then develops a comprehensive guideline that can enhance their effectiveness. The primary management challenges include; business administrative skills, numeracy, developing a bankable business proposal, building growth strategies, business counselling & mentoring support, and capacity building. Also, collateralisation and lack of positive discrimination are some of the challenges hindering credit accessibility by SMEs in Ghana.

1.4.2 Specific objectives

The aim of the research can easily be attained through the following specific objectives:

To ascertain and address the managerial shortfalls encountered by SMEs in Ghana and beyond. This part of the study will seek first-hand information on the managerial loopholes confronted by SMEs in their day-to-day management. The above will be achieved by

interviewing sampled SMEs and their Advisory and Skills Development Institutes in the Wa Municipality of Ghana.

To investigate the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana and beyond. This thesis will investigate existing SMEs and credit institutions in Ghana to reveal any possible difficulty hindering the smooth flow of credit between these two institutions.

Develop guidelines to enhance the effectiveness of managing and financing SMEs in Ghana. Finally, a comprehensive SME management and credit accessibility policy would help address the demand and supply challenges between SMEs in Ghana and the rest of Africa.

1.5 Research Question

1.5.1 Main research question

How do addressing the inadequate managerial skills and the challenges in accessing credit by SMEs enhance their growth in Ghana?

1.5.2 Specific research question

To successfully answer the main research question, the following sub-questions need to be addressed by this study:

What are the managerial shortfalls of SME operators in Ghana? Here, issues like

Misappropriation of funds and making wrong business decisions, improper marketing of products, product lifecycle, SMEs lifecycle, and their strengths and weaknesses will be addressed.

What are the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana? The following will be addressed as part of efforts to address the above research question: Collateralisation,

unnecessary bureaucracies, lack of positive discrimination and the perception that "small is risky".

What guidelines can enhance the effectiveness of managing and financing SMEs in Ghana?

The above would be the climax and seeks to bridge the gap that has long existed between SMEs and credit institutions.

1.6 Significance of the Study

Significantly, this study will help improve SME management. Also, it will suggest some credit accessibility-friendly policies to be implemented by the Government of Ghana through a proposed Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development and Financing Authority (GERDFA). The above-proposed Institute will be born out of a merger between the Registrar General Department, Ghana Enterprise Agency (GEA) and the Micro Finance and Small Loans Centre (MASLOC) under the Ministry of Trade and Industry's supervision. GERDFA will ensure that all SME owners and potential entrepreneurs register their businesses, undergo comprehensive training and be certified with a nationally recognised certificate that will serve as the basis for accessing credit in Ghana. Other stakeholders that will benefit include; the promising SME sector, the Government of Ghana, and the youth actively seeking employment. This study will guide future researchers venturing into SME management and credit accessibility research in the sub-region. Ultimately, SMEs benefit from this study by learning how to step up, to meet the demands of financial institutions, donor agencies and the government. It is further hoped that the financial institutions (credit suppliers) will realise that the long-standing perception of "small is risky" is a misnomer and pave the way for an equitable distribution of credit.

Lastly, adaptation and resilience become significant to ensuring survival and growth in an environment where uncertainty is almost inevitable. This thesis will equip SMEs with how to

adapt to changes and innovate new ideas to stay relevant to the international business community, especially in this era of the African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA). Socio-economic challenges will be reduced when the government and other stakeholders embrace the SME policy issues this study will address. Moreover, the relationship between the informal sector and the government will improve to facilitate bridging the gap between the credit institutes and the SME industry.

1.7 Limitations of the Scope of the Research

The scope of this thesis is restricted to the study of the management and credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana. It further focuses on how to turn around the above challenges to benefit the majority of Ghanaians. The above is achieved by expanding production through easy credit accessibility and basic business management skills to ensure growth, employment creation and competitiveness in the Ghanaian SME sector.

Limiting the study to just Ghana and the SME industry is in line with the recommendation of Yin (2003); researches of this nature need to be limited to a country and an industry to quickly reduce the scope of the subject area to something that is much more realistic to carry out.

1.8 Outline of the study

The rest of this proposal is scheduled as follows: Chapter one introduces the topic by giving a general overview of SMEs, telling the success stories from the global point of view, and carefully narrowing it to the African continent and Ghana, where the research is being conducted. It also hammered on credit accessibility as th]e main challenge hindering the growth of SMEs in Ghana and the world at large. It reiterated the importance of a credit-friendly environment for SMEs to operate.

Chapter two deals with the Literature review, where Various researchers and institutions define SMEs. The subject matter is discussed more in this chapter because of the many pieces of literature employed under this section as required. The main aspects include reviewing the literature on SME management and credit accessibility challenges.

Chapter Three focuses on Research Design and Methodology. The research method is carefully selected based on the formulated research questions. Sample size, study area, data collection methods and ethical issues are also addressed in this chapter. Objectivity, reliability and validity are tackled too.

Chapter four looks at Data Analysis: The data analysis methods are discussed. Data analysis is done with the chosen statistical package and interpreted.

Chapter Five will be a follow-up to chapter four. It focuses on the technical analysis of the data through cross-tabulation: testing the statistically significant relationships and differences by further exploring Pearson's chi-square test and Pearson's correlation coefficients test. Moreover, regression and causalities will also be tested.

Chapter Six presents the research findings; the research outcome is clearly stated here for the appropriate recommendations and conclusions to be derived.

Chapter Seven: Recommendations and Conclusions are made based on the research findings.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature

Literature on SME finance and the non-financial constraints in Africa are abundantly available in primarily peer-reviewed journal articles, book chapters and policy papers. Evidence on other regions also exists, especially the Asian economies, where their success stories are attributed mainly to SMEs. Most of the reviewed studies were SMEs centred, and where there was a reference to larger firms, it was mainly for comparison. The literature reviewed by this thesis heavily explored qualitative and quantitative methods. Also, perception-based subjective and objective data were employed. There are often similar findings with these data sets; access to finance, for example, is likely to be reported as an increasing challenge by financially constrained firms (Kuntchev et al., 2012). The World Bank enterprise survey data was used mainly by this literature, with some of them noting research gaps like; the correlation between firm productivity and finance (Onubedo and Yusuf, 2018), high firm growth-related issues (Olafsen and Cook, 2016); how higher firm finance can help with growth (Adomako, Danso, and Damoah, 2016); and how to develop context through innovation (Cirera and Maloney, 2017). Nkuah et al. (2013) publication was heavily relied on for SME definition. Lastly, reports from the Ghana Statistical Services were primarily employed. The above include IBES Summary Report (2015): *Ghana Statistical Service*; IBES Regional Spatial Business Report (2016); Ghana Statistical Service (2015); Ghana poverty mapping report, as well as the 2021 Population and Housing Census Report.

2.2 Small and Medium Enterprise: Definition

Their minor nature and private ownership generally characterise SMEs. Although significant attempts, by definition, have been made by earlier researchers, the argument is that "there is no universally accepted definition of a small and medium-sized business" (Nkuah et al., 2013), and micro-enterprises still hold. Nonetheless, region, country, industry, production methods, capital assets, labour, turnover and legal status (Adjei, 2012) are some of the areas that inform the definitions of SMEs. In Ghana, the enterprise's size is critical when defining SMEs (Boon, 1989), cited by Ackah and Vuvor (2011). However, those that define SMEs by their fixed assets should be cautious of exchange rate fluctuations. The above could render their definition outdated for any significant currency fluctuation.

Per the European Commission, SMEs are enterprises with less than €43million of an annual total balance sheet, engage less than 250 staff, or make no more than €50 million as annual turnover (Taylor and Adair 1994). Practically, most developing countries will not endorse this definition due to the high exchange rate between their currencies and the Euro. In the United States, SMEs are businesses with less than 500 employees (ibid). In Australia, SMEs employ not more than 15 staff (Australian Fair Work Act 2009).

Bangladesh had to reform its definition of SMEs to reflect its people (Hasan and Jamil, 2014). In Bangladesh, SMEs are establishments that employ less than 150 workers (BBS, 2004; Alauddin and Chowdhury, 2015)

The World Bank defined SMEs based on employees; SMEs are businesses with not more than 500 staff (just like in the case of the USA). UNIDO's definition of SMEs in developing countries was also based on the number of employees. Micro enterprises were described as those with staff strength of less than 5, small enterprises as establishments with staff ranging

from 5 to 19 and medium enterprises classified as those businesses that employ between 20 and 299 labour force (UNIDO,1983)

In Ghana, various institutions dealing with SMEs have defined it in their context. In 1987, the Ghana Statistical Service conducted the Ghana Industrial Census, defining SMEs by the number of staff and fixed assets. In that survey, small-scale businesses were classified as those employing a workforce between 5 and 29 and holding a total fixed asset not more than \$100,000. On the other hand, any business with a staff strength between 30 and 99 falls within the medium-scale enterprise category. Also, the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI) defines small-scale enterprises as those with less than nine (9) staff and have fixed assets (land, buildings, and vehicles, not counted) not valued more than US\$ 9506 (1000 Ghana cedis, per the 1994 exchange rate). Furthermore, a legal Act, Act 2004 (Act 680, section 28), was set up to empower Venture Capital Trust Fund (VCTF) to finance SMEs. This Act defines an SME in Ghana as a business with a staff strength of not more than 100 and holds an asset base (does not include buildings and lands) not more than the cedi equivalent of \$ 1000,000.

Table 2-1: Definition of SMEs by the number of employees.

EST TYPE	GSS	NBSSI	VCTF	UNIDO-DEV. COUNTRIES	WORLD BANK
SMALL	5-29	<9	<100	5-19	<100
MEDIUM	30-99	>9		20-299	

Source: (UNIDO, 1983; NBSSI, 1990; WORLD BANK, 2015; GSS, 2016; Act 2004 (Act 680, section 28)

Table 2.1 above shows the definition of SMEs by the number of employees according to the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI), The Venture Capital Trust Fund (VCTF), UNIDO and the World Bank. The VCTF and the World Bank are on the level with their definition of SMEs. However, compared to the definition by

UNIDO, it becomes evident that there will be variations regarding the cross-institutional application of the SME definition (Weston and Copeland, 1998).

2.2.1 Classification of SMEs by the Integrated Business Establishment Survey (IBES).

The Integrated Business Establishment Survey (IBES) was the first in Ghana. It was the first-ever attempt to get a comprehensive business register for all Ghanaian non-household establishments. This economic census was conducted in two phases, I & II, within almost 3 years. The first phase did list all business establishments in the country to develop a register for businesses and extract a sample out of it for the second phase (IBESS Regional Spatial Business Report, 2016 piii). MSMEs in Ghana were defined by IBES as; Micro enterprises are businesses with less than five (5) staff; Small businesses are those with employees from 6 to 30 and medium enterprises, as establishments employing from 31 to 100 workers. It further recorded that SMEs contribute about 70% of the GDP and employ 85% of the Ghanaian manufacturing industry (ibid).

Table 2-2: Definition and Classification of MSMEs by IBES in Ghana.

EST. TYPE	STAFF STRENGTH	CONTRIBUTION TO GDP	NUMBER EMPLOYED
MICRO	1-5	70% (IBES, 2016)	85% in the manufacturing industry (IBES, 2016)
SMALL	6-30		
MEDIUM	31-100		

Source: IBES Regional Spatial Business Report, (2016, p11)

IBES further classified Ghanaian establishments into; Micro, Small, Medium and Large. In total, 79.8% (509,033) of the establishments are Micro, 117, 329 representing 18.4% are small, medium enterprises summed up to 9,333 (1.4%), and the remaining 0.4% (2,539) are large enterprises.

Figure 2-1: Graphical illustration of the SMEs in Ghana by size and percentage

Source: Author’s compilation from IBES Summary Report, (2015 p16)

Note: All the figures in Figure 2.1 above were duly captured during the IBES census and published accordingly on the website of the Ghana Statistical Service under the IBES Summary Report (2015).

From Figure 2.1 above, 79.8% of Ghanaian establishments are micro and employ between 1 to 5 staff. Those that employ from 6 to 30 are only 18% of Ghanaian businesses, whilst enterprises with Medium (31 to 100) employees and large (over 100) staff are 1.4% and 0.4%, respectively.

2.2.2 Number of persons employed by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana

The representation of people engaged by Large, Medium, Small and Micro (Henceforth LMSM) Enterprises in Ghana is showcased in Figure 2.2 below. Micro enterprises employ most Ghanaian working class, with 1,106,971 (32.72%) people to its credit. Small enterprises come next on the list of the high number of people engaged in working with 994,395 (29.39%) workers, whilst large and medium follow with 858,253 (25.37%) and 423,587 (12.52%) employees, respectively.

Figure 2-2: The representation of persons employed by establishment size

Source: Author's compilation from IBES Summary Report, (2015 p41)

2.2.3 The average number of persons/percentages engaged per establishment by size in Ghana

Table 2.2 below reveals the average number of persons engaged by all establishments under their respective types. Each large business averagely employs 338 (85.78%) staff, with more than 238 employees above the minimum requirement of 100 staff per the IBES definition. Medium enterprises are doing an average of 45 (11.48%) staff in Ghana, thus 14 more than the essential requirement of 31 staff. Also, each small business in the country engages 9 (2.28%) employees, three above the required number of 6 workers. Lastly, on average, micro-enterprises work with only 2 (0.51%) staff, the owner and a possible assistant.

X = Number of persons engaged and the average percentage number of persons engaged

Y= Number of establishments and the Average percentage number of establishments

Z= Average number of persons engaged per establishment and the Average percentage number of persons engaged per establishment

Table 2-3: Average number of persons engaged per establishment in Ghana

EST. TYPE	X		Y		Z = X/Y	
	Persons	%	Establishments	%	Average	%
LARGE	858,253	25.37%	2539	0.40%	338	85.78%
MEDIUM	423,587	12.52%	9333	1.46%	45	11.42%
SMALL	994,395	29.39%	117,329	18.38%	9	2.28%
MICRO	1,106,971	32.72%	509,033	79.76%	2	0.51%

Source: Author's computation from IBES Summary Report, (2015 p41)

Note: The figures under Z = "Average number engaged per establishment" have been rounded to the nearest significant figures.

Table 2.3 above makes a pioneering revelation of the number of persons each business in Ghana employs on average, depending on whether it is a micro, small, medium or large enterprise. This revelation is significant because it has helped project future employment figures (as shown in Table 2.4 below), a sure way to arrest unemployment in the country. Much interesting is that without the overburdened public sector, the private sector, through SMEs alone, can do away with unemployment if the needed attention and resources are invested. Mathematically, the Average number of persons engaged per establishment (Z) = The Number of persons engaged (X) / Number of establishments. The above implies $Z=X/Y$ with the figures rounded to the nearest significant figures since the unit of measurement is the employees (Human beings).

2.2.4 Ten percent increment target on the average number of persons engaged per establishment

Table 2.4 below are targeted figures for the number of persons engaged at a rate of 10% by the respective SME Classifications. It is proposed that if the government can set and meet a 10% job creation target (every three years) on the current micro establishments, 110,697 (see Table 2.4 below: $50903.3 \times 2.174654688$) more jobs will be created if each newly created establishment employs a minimum of two staff. Again, at the same rate, 331,980 (Z-W under small) more vacancies will be created at the small establishment's level, provided each takes on at least nine staff. Meanwhile, 490,332 (Z-W under Medium) and 315,482 (Z-W under

large) more employment opportunities will be unveiled in the medium and large business sectors, respectively, as the newly promoted medium firms employ at least 45 staff and the newly promoted large firms can take on 338 workers.

V = Number of establishments in year one

W = Average number of persons engaged in year one

X = Number of establishments, a projection of 10% every three years.

Y = The average number of persons engaged per establishment.

Z = The average number of persons engaged at 10% projection in 3 years.

Table 2-4: Average number of persons employed at a projection of 10%

EST. TYPE	V	W	X	Y = W/V	Z = Y*X
MICRO	509,033	1,106,971	509,033*	2.174654688	1,106,971
SMALL	117,329	994,395	156,499.4**	8.475270394	1,326,375
MEDIUM	9,333	423,587	20,132.6***	45.38594236	913,737
LARGE	2,539	858,253	3,472.3****	338.0279638	1,173,734

Source: Author's computations, 2021

NB:

$$156,499.4^{**} = 117329 - 11732.9 + 50903.3$$

$$20,132.6^{***} = 9333 - 933.3 + 11732.9$$

$$3,472.3^{****} = 2539 + 933.3$$

Table 2.4 above is a continuation of Table 2.3 with a 10% increment target on the number of establishments and the average number of people engaged by establishment size over three years. Generally, the Table has outlined figures that, when operationalised, could end unemployment in Ghana within a reasonable timeframe, as illustrated in Fig 2.3 below. Based on the summary report published by the Ghana Statistical Service after IBES in 2015; There

were a total of 638,234 businesses in Ghana; ranging from Micro (509,033), Small (117,329), Medium (9,333) and Large (2,539) (IBES Summary Report, 2015 p16) that were in business as at the reference year of the survey, 2014. The lifespan of these businesses ranged between 1975 and 2014 (ibid, p22), with over 67% of them established between 2005 and 2014 (ibid, p19). These 638,234 establishments provide 3,383,206***** jobs (see ΣW in Table 2.4 above). Of these jobs, 1,417,982***** (see Table 2.4 above) are provided by SMEs, whilst the remaining are provided by micro and large enterprises (ibid).

2.2.5 Further Job Creation Analysis

Banks (2013) documented that most SMEs in developing economies fold up in their early years of operation. Data from this study gibes to the above fact. Given the above, this study introduces the Service/Product Lifecycle Model in Chapter 6 below. The Model is to help SMEs properly manage their services/products and eventually boost their profitability to stay in business and create more employment (see section 6.2.1 for details). With the above and the other policy recommendations in place, the study suggests an increment target of 10% for the respective SME Classifications making up the 638,234 establishments (see section 2.2.1 above). It is envisaged that if these establishments get the needed support from the government and other stakeholders, each business type should be able to graduate at least 10% of their group to the next higher group within three years. Thus 10% of the micro (50903.3) group graduates to become small businesses; 10% of the small (11,732.9) business group transform to become medium enterprises; 10% of Medium (933.3) enterprises reform into large enterprises whilst a fresh opportunity is given to a new 10% of the existing number of the micro (50903.3) enterprises to come on board. The above means 1,137,611***** (4520817-3383206); new jobs will be created each period for job seekers to grab.

Figure 2-3: projected employment figures

Source: Author's computations

From the figure above, the employment figures under micro-enterprises that translated into the bars remain the same year in and year out. As 10% of graduates are projected to enter small businesses, a new 10% micro-enterprises are created to fill the gap. In the second year (period) of the small business category, the employment figures increased from 994,395 to 1,326,375. It means an additional 331,980 jobs directly resulted from the 10% (50903.3 ref Table 2.4) of the micro-enterprises that became small businesses. Thus, the bar in the second year (period) under the small business category grows taller periodically as new jobs are created. More so, 10% (11732.9) of the small businesses would have also been transformed into medium enterprises with the ability to employ an average of 45.3859 workers each now. At this level, $913737 - 423587 = 490150$ new jobs are created. Lastly, 10% of the medium enterprises also move to be large firms, employing an average of 338.0279 staff. At their level, $1,173,734 - 858,253 = 315,481$ jobs are added to the national job basket. In total, 1,137,611 unemployed Ghanaians will be engaged to earn a living and pay taxes to the government for national development periodically. The above is a significant discovery that will fit into the SME policy document of Ghana and most developing economies. The government of Ghana is urged to pay

serious attention to this bit of research work. To achieve the above policy recommendation, a lot has to be done to create the needed atmosphere for SMEs to operate efficiently and grow as expected. Therefore, the rest of this chapter has detailed the main challenges hampering SME development with some possible remedies that will guide policymakers to achieve the best for Ghana and Africa.

2.3 The unemployment rate in Ghana

Unemployment refers to that portion of the labour force with no jobs but is actively seeking and ready to work. According to the 2021 Ghana Population and Housing Census, Ghana had a labour force of 11,541,355 in 2021 and an unemployment rate of 13.4% (Ghana Population and Housing Census, 2021). From the above definition, the number of people unemployed in Ghana in 2021 = $0.134 * 11,541,355 = 1,546,542$. The above computations imply that 1,546,542 people were not engaged in 2021. Comparing this figure to the 1,137,611 jobs SMEs could generate means that Ghana could solve its unemployment challenge if the government pays attention to SME development.

Figure 2-4: unemployment trend in Ghana

Source: Macrotrends.net

Figure 2.4 above shows the unemployment trend in Ghana from 1991 to 2020. The highest-ever rate of unemployment was recorded in 2000 at 10.36%, the year Ghana had its first-ever democratic transition of governance. The lowest was 4.57% in 2007 after the new government had made some interventions to boost the SME industry, including the skill development programme and the introduction of the Ghana Youth Employment Agency, which employed many young people in the country. The unemployment rate has hit a record high of 13.4% (Xinhua, 2021; and Ghana Population and Housing Census, 2021), yet to be added to the above graph.

2.4 Operational Definition

Operationally, this research adopts the Integrated Business Establishment Survey (IBESS) definition of Microenterprises as establishments with staff strength from 1 to 5. Meanwhile, businesses with 6 to 30 and 31 to 100 staff represent small and medium enterprises, respectively.

The choice of this definition allows for a proper justification and alignment with the chosen topic. The GSS is the only recognised governmental organisation with a comprehensive register for Ghanaian businesses. The primary investigator of this thesis was part of the field officers that collected data in both phases (IBESS I & II) to compile this historic business register.

2.5 SME Credit Accessibility Challenges in Africa

Adaptation and resilience become significant to ensuring survival and economic growth in an environment where uncertainty is almost inevitable. In light of the above, SMEs have emerged as an all-inclusive way of regaining the lost economic confidence after the Covid-19 Pandemic. Nurturing these establishments' contributions can ensure that the benefits of growth are shared more broadly (OECD, 2017). As promising as SMEs have proven to be across Africa and the world, one would have expected a globally adopted SME policy. A policy focused on creating an enabling environment for businesses to strive and move the African economy forward. Nonetheless, SMEs face stringent measures in accessing credit (ibid).

Recently, Onubedo and Yusuf (2018) employed data from cross-sectional firms to study the effects of access to finance on labour and total factor productivity in Africa. They concluded that almost 25% of the firms surveyed pointed out finance as the finest challenge (ibid, p.6). Furthermore, 69% of the firms studied complained of being unable to access overdraft, whilst those that had no access to loan facilities and or credit lines amount were 75% (ibid, p.8).

Moreover, Wang (2016), using data from a database contained by the World Bank's Enterprise Survey, also pointed out credit accessibility as the main barrier to SMEs' growth in Africa. By analysing the evidence on financial access interventions and existing lessons, Kumar (2017, 22) reported that only (17-32) % of traditional sources of finance are available to small firms in low- and middle-income economies. "This is in contrast to more than 50% of small firms in

high-income countries” (Haider, 2018). In an attempt to explore the cause of the existing disparities in financing between developed and third-world countries, Wang (2016) listed complex application procedures; high-interest rates; lack of records; demanding collateral requirements; and the fear by SMEs that their application could be turned down.

2.5.1 SMEs Financing Constraints in Sub-Saharan Africa

Africa, especially sub-Saharan Africa, has received significant highlights regarding small business financing constraints from researchers. "Indeed, the SME sector within sub-Saharan Africa has been referred to as the 'Missing Middle' in the context of financial inclusion or access to financial (including banking) services" (Quartey et al., 2017). SMEs in most lower economies are noted for their fierce battle with access to credit. The above challenge is primarily attributed to stringent collateral requirements, demanding application procedures, high-interest rates, and poor financial records (Haider, 2018). While these challenges affect lower economies globally, Sub-Saharan African countries face a double hitch because they are often noted as less developed financially compared to the less privileged countries in the other regions of the world (Fowowe, 2017; Quartey et al., 2017).

2.5.1.1 SME Financing Constraints in The COMESA Region

Ali, Abu-Hadi, and Ali (2013) studied how SMEs access microfinance in the Somali capital of Mogadishu. They found out that many of the SMEs surveyed had severe challenges in accessing finance. Their findings were attributable to the stringent requirements and bureaucracies (initial deposit or guarantor, loan collateral, possibility of repayment) that SMEs were expected to fulfil before being granted credit facilities. According to the researchers, the inability of Somali SMEs to access credit mainly results in their closure.

Again, Anderson (2017) researched SMEs in Tanzania by analysing the factors affecting them, and it revealed that stringent collateral requirements and complex bureaucracies were the

challenges hindering SME owners from accessing credit. This makes working capital a primary concern for SME start-ups (Ibid). Also, A selected sample of Ethiopian enterprises rated high-interest rates on business loans as the second most worrying obstacle SMEs face (Amentie et al., 2016).

Lastly, SME managers and owners in Limpopo, a less-developed province in the Thulamela Municipality of South Africa, were surveyed. It was revealed that access to finance was their most pressing challenge (Donga et al., 2016). The study further revealed that credit accessibility challenges are primarily due to the unavailability of tax records, inadequate credit records, failure of businesses to register, and SMEs' inability to draft a standard business plan.

2.5.1.2 SME Financing Constraints in The ECOWAS Region

Despite its essentiality to the growth of small businesses, adequate SME financing is still significantly missing in most West African countries (Fowowe, 2017; Amentie, Negash, and Kumera, 2016; Olafsen and Cook, 2016). According to Haider (2018), most available literature in West Africa indicates that smaller enterprises will more likely encounter financial challenges than giant enterprises. Limited credit accessibility was also documented as a significant constraint to SMEs development (Ndiaye, 2018; Kumar, 2017; Quartey et al., 2017)

Also, High bank charges, high legal documentation fees and high collateral securities were revealed as the leading financial constraints facing SMEs in Nigeria (Tunde and Abiodun, 2017). Moreover, Piabuo, Baye, and Tieguhong (2015) conducted a study on the '*Effects of credit constraints on the productivity of small and medium-sized enterprises in Cameroon*'. It was revealed that the legal status of an enterprise, interest rates, loan size, collateral size, enterprise size, and maturity of loans were the primary sources of SME credit constraints in the francophone country of Cameroon. The research further revealed that although medium

enterprises were more constrained with credit, small enterprises appeared to be more affected by the effects of credit constraints.

2.5.2 SME Financing Constraints in the MENA Region

The story is not different in the Middle East and the North African Region (MENA). Albeit possessing a relatively larger financial sector (including banking), the MENA region still has a chunk of its loan facilities going to the few larger firms leaving SMEs with either little or no credit (de Lima et al., 2016). Most infant firms have distanced themselves from the banking sector mainly because of collateralisation (ibid).

A 2017 World Bank report states that 70% of SMEs are incapacitated by adequate credit. The remaining 30%, although they might have access to credit, are heavily burdened with paperwork and information overload. Hence, transactional processes suffer risk-averse attitudes such as delays in approval, collateralisation and institutionalisation of stringent and "complex legal requirements, leaving business owners less time to run their business" (Bajaj, 2019). Credit accessibility became more difficult after the financial depression in 2008 (ibid) and Covid-19.

2.5.3 Financing Constraints of Female-Owned SMEs in Africa

Women are generally risk-averse and may avoid taking bigger loans to invest in their businesses, which mostly come with higher risks. In a situation where they have to compete for these loan facilities, they become adamant. In sub-Saharan Africa, women-owned SMEs are more exposed to financial challenges than their male counterparts (Lutz and Lutz, 2017).

Moreover, Aterido, Beck, and Iacovone (2013) argued that the inability of women-owned businesses to access credit could result from the size of their businesses. The researchers further purported that SMEs have lesser chances of accessing credit than larger firms, and most female businesses in the sub-region are synonymous with smaller businesses. In contrast, Wellalage

and Locke (2017) did not find women-owned businesses to be discriminated against when researching South Asia.

2.6 SME financing constraints in Ghana

In Ghana, a survey based on participatory methods in some randomly selected five districts of the Volta and Oti regions revealed inadequate capital as the significant challenge SMEs and local artisans face. The high cost of inputs and lack of market and equipment were the remaining challenges outlined in the survey (Amegashie-Viglo and Bokor, 2014, 30-32). It further documented that instead of accessing bank loans and other lending sources, most owner-managers in these regions started their businesses through start-up capital, personal savings or both. The above is so because only 27% of the entrepreneurs, who had ever sourced for bank facilities, were successful. The difficulty in accessing credit was a headache for the start-ups, and already established firms had their fair share of facing similar challenges in their quest to expand. Ibid (2014) documented that only 6 out of the 158 already established SMEs seeking to expand had access to bank credit; the remaining 96.2% had their applications turned down.

Nonetheless, various governments have made strides to curb the above menace. However, despite the efforts to reform the system (Steel and Webster, 1991), Ghana is no exception because the potential of SMEs is suppressed by inadequate credit accessibility (Association of Ghana Industries, 2011). Even more challenging is the fact that there are unrealistic demands and applied bureaucratic rigmaroles in the circumstances where credit is accessible. The above challenges have consequentially confined SMEs to traditional funding sources like; donations and gratuitous funding from friends, families and other philanthropists (Nkuah et al. 2013), and the relatively newly discovered village savings and Loans (VSLA) in the case of microenterprises in rural Ghana.

As earlier as 1994, Aryeetey et al. reported that 38% of SMEs in Ghana cited credit accessibility as their primary challenge. Parker (1995) supported this argument when access to credit was on top of the list of his respondents in a survey, he conducted to ascertain the challenges facing SMEs. These studies offer the precursor to further studies into ascertaining the magnitude and latitude of the credit accessibility challenge SMEs face, despite their potential. Collateralisation and the bureaucratic lending systems currently employed by funding agencies have proven not to be the practical solution for the underlying challenges facing SMEs in Ghana and beyond. It is, therefore, appropriate to suggest a pragmatic approach. The above-proposed approach will strategically guide the government and other stakeholders into championing and coordinating all efforts.

Moreover, it is anticipated that the suggested approach will successfully leverage access to credit for all SMEs across the length and breadth of Ghana. In fact, "The problem of financing SMEs is not so much the sources of funds but its accessibility" (Agwu and Emeti, 2014). To make credit more accessible to SMEs, there is a need for political will through policy formulation and enforcement, backed by the government's unflinching support. This study seeks to make a policy contribution to the government and all stakeholders in the SME industry.

2.6.1 Interest Rate as a Financial Constraint

Table 2.5 below is the listed real interest rate figures from some selected African countries published by the trading economics website for 2021. It reveals the African country with the lowest interest rate and the country with the highest interest rate.

Table 2-5: Real Interest Rate values for African countries (see appendix for complete list)

Country	Last (%)	Previous (%)	Reference Date
Cape Verde	0.25	0.25	Oct/21
Comoros	0.94	0.94	Mar/21
Morocco	1.5	1.5	Oct/21
Mauritius	1.85	1.85	Oct/21
Seychelles	2	2	Sep/21
Algeria	3	3	Jul/21
Libya	3	3	Oct/21
Botswana	3.75	3.75	Dec/21
Namibia	3.75	3.75	Oct/21
South Africa	3.75	3.5	Nov/21
Nigeria	11.5	11.5	Nov/21
Malawi	12	12	Oct/21
Mozambique	13.25	13.25	Nov/21
Sierra Leone	14	14	Oct/21
Ghana	14.5	14.5	Nov/21
South Sudan	15	15	May/21
Sudan	17.1	19.3	Aug/21
Angola	20	20	Nov/21
Liberia	20	20	Oct/21
Zimbabwe	60	40	Oct/21

Source: Trading Economics, 2021

Table 2.5 above displays actual values and historical data for interest rates for some selected African countries. Cape Verde, Comoros and Morocco are the first three African countries with the lowest interest rates of 0.25% (Oct 2021), 0.94% (March 2021) and 1.5% (Oct 2021), respectively. The countries with the highest interest rates are Sudan, Angola, Liberia and Zimbabwe with 17.1% (Aug 2021), 20% (Nov 2021), 20% (Oct 2021) and 60% (Oct 2021), respectively. Interestingly, Ghana is one of the African countries with a high-interest rate of 14.5% (tradingeconomics, 2021), which is a severe barrier to SME development and must be reduced drastically to create an enabling and competitive business environment. Figure 2.5 below is the historical data of Ghana's interest rates for the last decade. The least was in 2012 (12.5%) and peaked at 26% in 2016 and 2017. Ghana's interest rate, as of March 2022, was 17% (Bank of Ghana).

Figure 2-5 Historical interest rates in Ghana

Source: Tradingeconomics, 2022

2.7 Non-Financial Constraints Facing SMEs

SME growth has been cited by many as an essential ingredient to the prosperous economic growth of most economies, given the proper credit assistance. Nevertheless, as necessary as it may be, credit accessibility is seen as insufficient, according to Olafsen and Cook (2016). Although difficulties in accessing credit are the most discussed by many researchers, significant literature also points to the following list of non-financial barriers that hinder SME growth (Haider, 2018):

2.7.1 Management challenges facing SMEs

Most SMEs are constrained to putting the best practices to work. The above can be attributed to their small staff strength and inability to hire skilled staff for the right job. Most SMEs have one person performing multiple roles without necessarily having the required skills to multitask for the multiple roles they occupy successfully. The above has caused stagnation in growth to many of these enterprises and, in extreme cases, triggered some otherwise potentially viable businesses to fold up after a significant initial investment. SMEs in most developing countries

are victims of microfinance loans simply because they lack the basic financial management skills to turn these facilities into profits. "Small firms lack proper accounting procedures, and owners easily mix their business and personal finances, making their financial statements often unreliable" (Nkuah et al., 2013) if they have financial statements. Supporting the argument, Schmitz (1982) and Hasan and Jamil (2012) also believe that in 3rd world countries, micro-producers cannot grow because of managerial incompetence. This research alludes to the above fact.

Moreover, West and Wood (1972) opine; lack of experience and fundamental competencies contributes to 90% of SME failures. Rogers (2002) could not agree any better when he listed; Inefficiency and improper record-keeping as the main factors crashing SMEs. Further attestation of the above was documented by; Hasan and Jamil (2014). The duo stated that misappropriation of funds and making wrong business decisions are manifestations of SMEs' incompetency in managing their finances, marketing their products, procuring goods & services, and engineering robust production techniques. Although education plays a significant role in firm growth (King and McGrath, 2002), it must be the proper education. Proper education equips SMEs with human resources with the relevant professional skills required to adapt to emerging challenges from the business climate.

Furthermore, staff with the proper education can identify and seize the opportunities businesses require to develop. Nonetheless, most SMEs are not privy to institutions that can adequately support their growth. Furthermore, even where they get to know the above institutions, most SMEs lack the required skills in most cases to access these opportunities (Adjei, 2014). After the 2012 general election in Ghana, the government announced a \$ 10 million SME support fund. Also, the outbreak of the Covid-19 Pandemic saw the government introducing a grant for affected businesses. Most SMEs that needed support fell out because they could not produce the needed paperwork to meet the essential requirements for the above grants.

With much technical support from the World Bank (Beck, Demirguc-Kunt & Levine, 2003), governments and many other donor agencies, SMEs are being targeted as an economic development vehicle (Snodgrass & Winkler, 2004). The government of Ghana has tried many skills development programmes to boost SMEs, ranging from The National Vocational and Training Institute (NVTI), Opportunity Industrialisation Centres (OIC), National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI now GEA), Ghana Appropriate Technology Industrial Service (GATIS) (Kayanula and Quartey, 2000), Youth Enterprise Support, and Youth Employment Agency. However, fundamental challenges like; bookkeeping, stock management, efficient service delivery, customer satisfaction, and value chain management are primarily associated with Ghanaian businesses as their main challenges. The above is linked to the lack of effective coordination of institutions and foreign donors' efforts to address the challenges. The need to set national standards for relatively free and accessible entrepreneurial training as a prerequisite for accessing SME credit in Ghana is long overdue. The above will go a long way to ensure that the government and other funding agencies lend credit to competent SMEs.

2.7.2 Competition and Lack of Innovation

Fierce competition without the right accompanying innovation can hinder SME growth. Competition becomes inevitable in an open market where everyone is free to operate. The only way to stay competitive as a business is to scale up innovative skills. However, most SMEs in lower economies like Ghana lack the right skills to innovate and stay competitive. They lack the right technology to develop such ideas into realities whenever necessary. Lorenz and Pommet (2017) mentioned insufficient finance as a significant contributing factor to SMEs' inability to innovate new ideas and stay competitive. Also, *ibid* documented that SME owner-managers lack the required creativity and innovation to scale up growth. Drawing data from the African Science, Technology and Innovation Indicator survey, firms in the Ghana

manufacturing and service sector were studied. It was revealed that innovative firms employ more people than firms that are not innovative.

Furthermore, smaller firms are more innovative than medium and large firms (Tetteh and Essegbey, 2014). Once these Small firms attain the Medium to Large status, they relax with their innovations, settling for 'good' locally instead of continuously innovating to compete in the international market. There is a need to motivate local enterprises to set international targets to continuously and competitively innovate even after achieving their local targets.

2.7.3 Technology

In the 21st century, it is almost impossible to do anything without technology. Social media, World Wide Web; email; e-commerce; e-business; e-marketing, the Internet, intranet and extranet have become the most popular and cheapest way of doing business. Unsurprisingly, most high street shops are closing down, making online businesses stay competitive. Over the years, the online business strategy has proven to be cost-effective and a sure way of staying competitive, as the cost of hiring a physical space does not exist. Nonetheless, most SMEs in Ghana and some lower economies are technologically bankrupt, so much so that some SME owners do not know how to access simple electronic mail. As a result, most of these SMEs still pay significantly for communication and marketing when they can almost access them for free with the right technological skills.

Most importantly, SME grants and government support are accessed online; this automatically disadvantages those who do not have the right technological skills. Whilst researchers cited SMEs for having admitted to the importance of technology in their holistic growth, how to get access to the right technology remains a hard nut to crack (Donga et al., 2016). The absence of resource centres for technology transfer and incubators to enhance production and promote

business effectiveness highlights the core challenges facing SMEs in Tanzania (Anderson, 2017), Ghana, and most developing countries.

2.7.4 Regulatory Framework:

Olafsen and Cook (2016) documented an overly burdensome framework as a significant challenge to firm growth and cutting low tax rates for new firms. Taxes were added when (Ndiaye, 2018; Amentie et al., 2016) made a similar argument. The low tax burden on new and small businesses; more flexible labour market; effective property rights; strong protection of creditors' rights; sound mechanisms for contract enforcement, and low administrative burden are some of the factors raised by *ibid* when they argued for the right environment for SME entry and growth. Anderson (2017) conducted a study in Tanzania revealing the following regulatory and legal framework as significant challenges to SMEs start-up and growth; unnecessary bureaucracies in the local government ~~and~~ offices; corruption; multiple levies and taxes. These same challenges can be said of Ghana and many other lower economies.

2.7.5 Political Instability and Corruption

An enterprise survey conducted in some Middle East and North African (MENA) countries revealed political instability as the main concern for Chief Executive Officers and managers. De Lima et al. (2016) added that political instability has a dire consequence on productivity, growth and sales. Corruption is also among the key worrying concerns for SME Managers in the MENA region. Ghana, as well as many developing countries, are no exception to the menace of corruption. Stagnation in employment, sales reduction and less output in labour are some of the dividends yielded through corruption. These are part of why SMEs face growth challenges in these regions. *Ibid* (2016) reported that enough evidence outlines that corruption scares businesses from coming into contact with public officials, and as a result, relevant opportunities are mostly not explored.

Table 2.6 below is the corruption perception index of African countries out of the 180 surveyed globally. Top on the list is primarily African countries. The least the score, the higher corruption is perceived in that country (World Population Review, 2022). The youngest country in Africa, South Sudan leads the chart as the most corrupt country in the world with an abysmal score of 11, dropping a point from its previous 12 in 2020. The over 16 million populated Somalia has improved over its 2020 combined score with South Sudan and now occupies the second slot with 13 points. Libya (17 points), Equatorial Guinea (17 points), Dr Congo (19 points), Sudan (20 points), Chad (20 points), and Comoros (20 points) are the countries that follow as the worst corrupt countries in Africa. Surprisingly, most of the above countries are war-torn nations, bearing that war breeds corruption.

Ghana maintained the same score as 2020 (43), sharing the 8th least corrupt position in Africa with its West African counterpart Senegal, who dropped 2 points from the previous 45 in 2020. The countries that are the least corrupt in Africa are Botswana (55 points), followed by Mauritius (54 points), Rwanda (53 points), Namibia (49 points), Tunisia (44) and South Africa (44), respectively. It is not by chance that most of these countries are leading the chart of the ease of doing business in Africa (refer to Table 1.1). When corruption is not controlled, the needed infrastructure cannot be developed to create a sound environment for doing business.

Table 2-6: The corruption perception index of African countries (see appendix for full list)

Rank	Country	corIndex2020	corIndex2021	pop2022
1	South Sudan	12	11	11,618,511
2	Somalia	12	13	16,841,795
3	Libya	17	17	7,040,745
3	Equatorial Guinea	16	17	1,496,662
4	DR Congo	18	19	95,240,792
5	Sudan	16	20	45,992,020
5	Chad	21	20	17,413,580
10	Nigeria	25	24	216,746,934
26	Burkina Faso	40	42	22,102,838
27	Benin	41	42	12,784,726
28	Ghana	43	43	32,395,450
29	South Africa	44	44	60,756,135
29	Tunisia	44	44	12,046,656
30	Namibia	51	49	2,633,874
31	Rwanda	54	53	13,600,464
32	Mauritius	53	54	1,274,727
33	Botswana	60	55	2,441,162

Source: World Population Review (2022)

2.7.6 infrastructure

Like any other business, SMEs require the proper infrastructure for smooth operations and development. Electricity, transport, telecommunication and a good road network were cited as having a good impact on the growth of SMEs by Amentie et al. (2016). Electricity is the most mentioned by researchers in the list of infrastructure above (Anderson, 2017). According to a study conducted in Tanzania, fluctuating electricity supply and excited utility prices were mentioned as the main challenges to SME development (ibid). In the studies mentioned above, interviewees in their numbers lamented that it is almost impossible to attain a physical space to operate a business due to the overhyped cost of rent (ibid). The above is a common challenge in most developing countries and has forced most SMEs to operate by the roadside and on a mobile basis. Many businesses have incurred losses due to unreliable power supply, among other utility challenges (Ibid).

s

Figure 2-6: Traders selling on the street in the Kumasi Central Market, Ghana.

Source: Africaway, 2021

SME development is seen to be on the setback because of substandard Infrastructure in South Africa's Thulamela Municipality and many more African cities. A similar study in Ethiopia also revealed poor communication facilities and high electricity costs as the key challenges to SME growth (Amentie et al., 2016). Even though the government's efforts to tackle these challenges, Egypt, Yemen, Gaza, and Lebanon are examples of countries in the MENA region whose SMEs are mostly faced with erratic electricity supply and, by extension, hinder their growth. Solid sales and productivity are significantly reduced due to an irregular power supply (de Lima et al., 2016).

2.7.7 Human resource

SMEs are mostly bedevilled with limited human capital due to their minor nature and weak hiring capacity. As a result, most SMEs have one person improvising to perform several roles. The above primarily affects output and growth because; the individual cannot keep track of all the numerous roles they play and simultaneously plan effectively for growth. Moreover, SMEs

that manage to hire mostly settle for cheap labour, which often comes with inexperience and inadequate qualification. In an industry where mentoring, training, and development are mostly missing, and more so when there is not enough room for learning, hiring raw talents becomes a recipe for disaster. Nkuah et al. (2013) made it clear in their research that SME owners easily mix personal finance with their businesses because they lack the proper accounting skills. The above further renders their financial statements less valuable, restricting them from accessing credit from credit institutions.

According to Ndiaye (2018), a firm's performance is mainly associated with its human resource. Therefore, experienced and skilled employees and managers are the priorities of every well-performing firm (Olafsen and Cook, 2018). Proper knowledge of budgeting, debt acquisition and payment; the ability to meet financial targets through effective consumer market management is the key and necessary financial literacy skills required (Adomako et al., 2016). SMEs cannot grow and compete with larger firms because of their deficiency in financial management (ibid). A report on financial inclusion by World Bank in 2014 reveals that SMEs' contribution to employment, innovation, growth and productivity is undermined because of their significant financial constraints (ibid). In Tanzania, women in SME management have been identified as needing technical assistance with budgeting, inventory control, and proper business planning (Msoka, 2013). A dozen researchers have linked SMEs' inability to grow to insufficient human capital. Before setting up their businesses, most SME operators in South Africa were identified as lacking formal business training. The above was authenticated when surveyed SMEs in the Thulamela Municipality did not have business plans, the proper human resource management and the correct financial management practices (Donga et al., 2016). The operators of these SMEs also confirmed the importance of training on the growth of their businesses (ibid).

In Ghana, although most respondents were keen on participating in the existing formal training programmes that they knew, only 28% confirmed taking part in courses that upgraded their skills. However, the above was blamed on a particular academic requirement to be met by participants before partaking in those courses (Amegashie-Viglo and Bokor, 2014, p29). Additionally, lack of programme awareness and publicity, lack of participating fees, and doubts about the programme's impact were the documented reasons why SME owner-managers in Ghana do not participate in formal training programmes (Damoah et al., 2017). The above, according to *ibid*, has made firms that run training programmes in management make multinationals and large firms their priorities when designing their programmes for training to neglect SMEs.

2.8 Relationship between SME Management and Credit Accessibility.

In a world where "if it is not documented, it is not done", It is both a practical and scholarly fact that proper administrative work can lead to easier credit accessibility (Nkuah et al., 2013; Steel and Webster, 1991; Aryeetey et al., 1994; Daniels and Ngwira, 1993; Abor and Quartey, 2010; Kashuliza and Kydd, 1996; Zeller, 1994; Schmidt and Kropp, 1987). Most credit accessibility challenges identified can be linked to improper management practices. This work contributes significantly to providing accessible and basic management skills to SMEs and potential entrepreneurs in Ghana.

2.9 Research Gap

With the exponential growth in unemployment, creativity has become necessary. More young graduates are inventing many entrepreneurial ideas that are bogged mainly by credit inaccessibility in Ghana and beyond. These potentially viable business ideas curtailed by the

unavailability of funding mostly end up in the bins leaving the young innovators in frustration and joblessness.

A significant amount of the research carried out on credit accessibility is mainly focused on stating the challenges SMEs face (Steel and Webster, 1991; Aryeetey et al., 1994; Daniels and Ngwira, 1993; Abor and Quartey, 2010; Kashuliza and Kydd, 1996; Zeller, 1994; Schmidt and Kropp, 1987). There is not much scholarly evidence outlining the subject matter as a demand and supply problem that impacts employment, and as such much has not been done to deal with it comprehensively. Hence, the need for research of this nature to be conducted. Granting credit to small businesses is considered time-wasting and not cost-worthy by the banks and other funding sources. These firms have been cited as not having the required accounting skills to differentiate personal finances from corporate funds. Therefore, owners easily mix their finances with the business (Nkuah et al. 2013), making it practically cumbersome to measure profit and loss. Also pointed out by researchers as factors impeding SMEs' access to credit are management lapses such as; improper business planning and registration and inaccurate bookkeeping (ibid). Few policy guidelines were suggested for permanently dealing with these challenges. This research proposes a funding framework that will guide Ghana's SMEs and financial institutions.

2.10 Conceptual Framework

After critically exploring the required literature on credit accessibility and management challenges SMEs face, the following conceptual framework is developed through the identified research gap.

Figure 2-7: Conceptual framework developed after critically reviewing the literature.

Strategically equipping SMEs with essential managerial skills will contribute to SME success. The thesis will employ management models to explicitly propose strategies that Ghana's government could follow to address the SMEs' managerial challenges in chapter six successfully.

A comprehensive financing framework can give access to many more SMEs and contribute to their success. Chapter six of this thesis proposes an SME financing framework that could help address the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana.

A national policy on SME operation will synergise the system and ensure efficiency. In chapter six, this dissertation studies Ghana and Mauritius and proposes a Policy Guide for Ghanaian SMEs development.

In a nutshell, available literature has proven that globally, SMEs are the vanguards of economic empowerment. Lack of the required technical abilities and easy accessibility to credit were some of the significant factors affecting SMEs' growth in Ghana and beyond. It also revealed that proper management skills could lead to easy finance and SME growth access.

However, not much has been suggested regarding the specific policies and practical approaches towards addressing this menace. This dissertation addresses this knowledge gap by proposing

a funding framework and a practical approach using the existing state institutions. It is believed that this gap, when addressed, will not only improve the fortunes of SMEs operating in Ghana but also give them a strategic platform to compete globally and create more jobs.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

3.1 Research Philosophy

Assumptions and beliefs systematically characterise the quest to develop knowledge through this study. These assumptions and beliefs will serve as guidelines at the various stages of this thesis, whether knowingly or unknowingly (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, as cited in Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016, p. 124). Ontology, axiology and epistemology are the assumptions mainly employed to assist with understanding the methods, the formulated research questions and the interpretation of the research findings (Crotty, 1998) employed by this research. The primary aim of sequencing these assumptions is to ensure the proper alignment for the study (Saunders et al., 2016, p.125) and establish a credible research philosophy.

Researchers in Business and Management often use the following five research philosophies: Interpretivism, positivism, postmodernism, pragmatism and critical realism (Saunders et al. 2016, p. 135-143). After carefully considering the above assumptions and thoroughly reviewing the formulated research questions, this study has applied the positivist research philosophy. Positivism in research leads to unequivocal and precise findings through a discernible social reality (ibid, p.135)

Considering the research objectives below:

- i. To ascertain and address the managerial shortfalls encountered by SMEs in Ghana.*
- ii. To investigate the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana.*
- iii. To develop guidelines that can enhance the effectiveness of financing SMEs in Ghana.*

It is almost certain from the first two research objectives that the study is expecting a specific response. However, instead of employing inferential statistics to verify or falsify these premises

by collecting primarily numeric data from the sampled respondent, this dissertation will result in what is referred to as 'descripto-explanato-evaluative' statistics, as partly stated in Saunders et al. (2016, p. 175). The 'descripto-explanato-evaluative' statistics combines descriptive, explanatory and evaluative statistics (see section 4.1.2 for details). The above-stated features of this research's objectives make it deductive and, by far, a reserve for the positivist research philosophy (ibid, p. 144). Although not explicitly deductive, the last objective could still be analysed quantitatively, as suggested by (ibid, p.136). The positivist research philosophy is highly linked to natural scientists and their philosophical stance in producing what is termed a 'law-like generalisation' from social research of this kind. With outcomes mostly unambiguous and accurate, the positivism philosophy has been in existence for more than a century and has evolved into twelve types, according to Crotty (1998) as cited in Saunders et al. (2016 p. 136), creating a lot more options for social researches of this nature.

On the other hand, Interpretivism is the study of the meanings humans make in research compared to a physical phenomenon. Critical realism, postmodernism, and pragmatism are between positivism and Interpretivism (Saunders et al. 2016, p. 135-141).

Positivism stresses quantitative research methods, making it appropriate to achieve the first two formulated research objectives. The final objective, which is more of consultancy and contribution to practice, could also allow for the quantitative analysis method. Hence, the research will adopt the deductive approach throughout.

3.2 Research Methodology and Design

3.2.1 Quantitative Research Design

In this kind of social research, three major research design options are available—quantitative, qualitative and mixed-method. However, the choice of which design to adopt largely depends

on the objectives of the ongoing study. Considering the research objectives stated above, applying the quantitative research design with the positivism philosophy is appropriate. Especially as the first two objectives appear very deductive in their approach, as Saunders et al. suggested (2016, p.166) in their book. Although it may have some elements requiring opinion-based data, the third objective does not exclusively limit it to a qualitative study (ibid). It is worth mentioning that a mixed method could be an option for this survey, but this study will stick to the quantitative approach due to its efficiency and cost-effectiveness (ibid). More so, Nkuah et al. (2013) employed the quantitative research design when they carried out a similar study on *Financing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana: challenges and determinants in accessing bank credit*.

3.2.2 Approach to theory development

The use of theory in research of this calibre is inevitable (Saunders et al., 2016, p.144). However, the stage and timing of applying the theory could affect the research design the study employs (ibid). There are three main approaches to theory development; deduction, induction and abduction. The deductive approach mostly starts with a theory, where the researcher reviews several academic works of literature. Instead of inferentially developing and testing a hypothesis, this study will employ descriptive, explanatory and evaluative statistics in analysing the data and synthesising the formulated ideas. It is vital to mention that the employed descriptive statistics is only a harbinger of explanation. This dissertation will also use evaluative statistics through cross-tabulations and correlations to further detail the relationships between variables identified through the data collection processes (Ibid, p.175-176). Finally, evaluative statistics will be employed as a tool for comparative studies between the SME policy documents of Ghana and Mauritius in chapter six.

However, the inductive approach to theory takes the opposite direction of the deductive approach. In this sense, the researcher kicks off through data collection. The collected data is

used to study a physical process, and a theory is developed in the form of a conceptual framework. Lastly, the researcher employing the abductive approach to theory goes through a data collection cycle to either develop a new hypothesis or adjust an existing one. Other steps included in the abductive approach are the explanation of data patterns and the identification of themes.

For this study, the deductive approach to theory development is chosen. Various academic literature on SME financing and management challenges have been reviewed. Quantitative survey questionnaires have been designed for ethical approval, data collection, data analysis and presentation of findings.

3.2.3 Methodology

Purposely for this study, the multi-method quantitative study will be employed; this allows for multiple data collection techniques and analytic procedures, subsequently (Saunders et al. 2016, p. 166). After reviewing the required literature, building the appropriate framework, and working on the questionnaires, the quantitative data collection method will be applied. Initially, it will be on a pilot basis to test the questionnaire's robustness and sequencing. Once satisfied, time will be allocated for the proper data collection. Figure 3.1 below is the methodological structure of this dissertation.

Figure 3-1: The methodological path of this study highlighted in orange

3.2.4 Research Strategy

Quantitative research of this nature needs a strategy that supports a deep understanding of the field of study. The survey research strategy is appropriate for a business and management study, as Saunders et al. (2016, p.181) suggest. Moreover, it is suitable for using a questionnaire and economical in gathering reasonably large data in a standard way that allows for easy comparison. Even more so when the nature of the questionnaire is a mixture of descriptive, exploratory and evaluative (ibid). Also, employing the survey strategy paves the way for the investigator to have a firm grip on the research process. The survey strategy allows the researcher to make meaning out of the chosen sample using a probability sampling technique less than spending more money to gather data on the whole population (ibid, p. 182).

3.2.5 Study Time Horizon

This study, by its nature, will employ the cross-sectional study and not the longitudinal one. The above means that a one-time data collection throughout the research lifespan is advisable for saving time and cost (Saunders et al. 2016, p. 135-141).

3.2.6 Techniques and Procedures

The summary of the chosen research route is stipulated in Table 3.1 below.

Table 3-1: Summary of the chosen research route for this study

Type	Quantitative
Philosophy	Positivism
Approach to theory development	Deductive (description-explanatory)
Methodology	multi-method quantitative study
Strategy	Survey/questionnaire
Time horizon	cross-sectional
Techniques and procedures	Primary and secondary data collection

Source: Authors compilation from Saunders et al. (2016 p. 164)

Table 3.1 above clearly stipulates the chosen research route for this study. This quantitative research employs the positivism philosophy and a deductive approach to theory development as practised by earlier researchers like Nkuah et al. (2013). The multiple-method quantitative study is the chosen methodology this study employs. As Bryman (2006) advocates, the chosen methodology creates a way for better data collection, analysis, and interpretation, as documented by Saunders et al. (2016, p. 166). Moreover, this methodology has the potential to overlook most of the limitations that may arise from using the mono-method quantitative study (ibid). A questionnaire is the most common strategy of every quantitative study (ibid, p. 181). The chosen time horizon for this study is the cross-sectional study and not the longitudinal one. Sticking to the cross-sectional study means a one-time data collection throughout the research; lifespan is advisable for saving time and cost (Saunders et al. 2016, p. 135-141). Lastly, Primary and secondary data collection procedures/techniques will be applied to gather the needed data for this research.

3.3 Research Coverage

3.3.1 Description of the selected place for the Study

The research is conducted in Ghana's Wa Municipality of the Upper West Region. The region comprises eleven (11) Municipal and District Assemblies (MDAs). The Upper West Region is situated in the northwest part of Ghana. It borders the Savana and Upper East Regions to the south, Burkina Faso to the north and Ivory Coast to the northwest (UKEssays, 2018).

Formerly known as the Wa District, the current Wa Municipality is bordered to the west by the Wa West District, to the north by the Nadowli-Kaleo District, and to the east by the Wa East District. The Wa Municipality was created in 2004 to champion decentralisation through the Legislative Instrument (LI) 1800. The LI 1800 mandates the Wa Municipal Assembly to take over the political administration of the Municipality and see to the smooth running and execution of policies of national interest, among many others. The Local Government Act 1993 (Act 426), section 10, further empowers the Assembly to undertake executive, legislative and thoughtful functions that will ensure the comprehensive development of the Municipality (UKEssays, 2018), including ensuring the availability of an enabling environment for the smooth running of SMEs.

Geographically, the Wa Municipality is positioned between longitudes 9°40' W and 10°15' W and latitudes 9°50' N to 10°20' N. The significance of the geographical position of the Wa Municipality in terms of SME development is the easy facilitation of bilateral trade and commerce with its neighbouring French-speaking countries, especially with the launching of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA). With the location and AfCFTA in progress, the Wa Municipality tends to transmogrify into a viable commercial and industrial arena for the north-western gateway of Ghana (UKEssays, 2018).

However, in terms of land coverage, the Municipality occupies only 3.36% (597 km²) of the total land area of the Upper West Region (Citi Population, 2020). The above is backed by the fact that all significant crop producers in the region come from the Sissala East Municipality and Wa East District, which have land arrears of 5100 km² and 4335 km², respectively. Population-wise, the Wa Municipality houses 200,672 people (Ghana Statistical Service: 2021 Population and Housing Census, General Report Volume 3A. p74), with 71.4% living in urban arrears due to the economic advantages. Women form the majority in the Municipality, with a total of 102,179 (50.92%) against their male counterparts of 98,493 (49.08%), and are the most economically active in the Municipality (ibid).

Figure 3-2: The Map of Wa Municipal

Source: UKEssays, 2018

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

3.3.2 Justification of the selected place for the Study

The Wa Municipality is selected because of its continuous surge in MSMEs numbers. According to the 2010 Population and Housing Census, the private sector covers 85.1% of employment in the Municipality, most of whom are women. Interestingly, only 5% of these SMEs are formalised, and 80.1% are informal. More male SMEs are formalised (1,116) than their female counterparts (633), possibly because of the discrepancies between their respective levels of education (Ghana Statistical Service: 2010 Population and Housing Census, District

Analytical Report, Wa Municipal, 2014 p32). Conversely, 80.1% of informal SMEs are dominated by women (15,494) against the 12,522 unregistered male SMEs (ibid p36). The above statistics flag the Wa Municipality as an SME hub worth studying and possibly contributing some knowledge to help develop the industry.

Also, the SME sector in the Wa Municipality is highly diverse and competitive, which allows the principal investigator to study across many economic sectors to enrich the study. For instance, the 2010 Population and Housing Census has revealed that the economy of the Wa Municipality has shifted from a traditional agricultural base to a service-based economy. The latter now employs 21.1% more people than the previously dominant agricultural sector. The next competitive sector is the industry sector which provides 18.4% of the employment in the Municipality. The other sectors are tourism, energy, transport, finance and telecommunication (ibid p4).

The Wa Municipality belongs to the poorest of the sixteen (16) administrative regions in Ghana (the Upper West Region). The region's poverty rate is 70.7% (Ghana Poverty Mapping Report, GSS 2015). This alarming poverty rate can be linked to inadequate economic overhead capital such as; a good road network, telecommunication, internet, and electricity. The underdevelopment of these overhead capitals leads to an un conducive business environment, thereby restraining the growth and development of the SME industry in the Wa Municipality (UKEssays, 2018) d.

3.4 Targeted Stakeholders for the Study

Stakeholder analysis is a means of understanding the parties involved before possibly engaging them in the data collection exercise. Identifying and prioritising the stakeholders is very important, considering the enormous numbers of stakeholder groups in the SME industry

(Slabá, 2016). In Ghana and Africa, over 90% of businesses are SMEs, mainly employing the youth and women (Fjose et al. 2010). Several stakeholders influence the activities of these SMEs.

Slaba (2016), after reviewing the following literature (Andriof et al. 2002; Buysse and Verbeke 2003; Chinyi et al. 2010; Freeman 2010; Freeman 1984; Bourne and Walker 2006; Šimberová 2008) identified the list below as the stakeholders in the SME industry:

Banks and financial institutions, communities (general communities and local communities), competitors, consultancy firms (taxes, financial and other consultancies), customers, contractors, educational institutions, employees, end users, government (local and state government), management, media, owners, subcontractors, suppliers, trade unions and associations, and transporters.

Considering their numbers, Chinyio et al. (2010) and Freeman (2010) categorised them into internal, external, primary and secondary.

Table 3-2: SME stakeholder groups

TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER GROUPS			
PRIMARY	SECONDARY	INTERNAL	EXTERNAL
Customers, Employees, Suppliers, Government, Competitors	Banks and financial institutions, Consultancy firms, Education institutions, Local communities, Media, Transporters, NGO	Employees, Management, Owners, Shareholders	Banks and financial institutions, Competitors, Consultancy firms, Customers, Education institutions, NGOs, Government, Local communities, Media, Suppliers, Transporters

Source: Slaba, (2016)

For this study, the above list is further slashed down to the following four most identified stakeholder groups with commercial organisations in the world Slaba (2016):

- Financial Institutions
- Consultancy Firms
- Government
- Owners

3.4.1 Analysis of the shortlisted stakeholders

3.4.1.1 Financial Institutions:

Financial institutions are considered at the top of the list of stakeholders due to their importance in SMEs' growth and development. For this research, they will include the banks, The Micro Finance and Small Loan Centre (MASLOC), Microfinance institutions, formal savings and loans Institutions, Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA), Venture capitalists and individual credit lenders. It is almost impossible for SMEs to do without this stakeholder. Collecting data from them will always be challenging due to their confidential nature. However, this study haven undergone ethical review and been cleared by the Ethical Review Committee; it is hoped that with a proper introduction and stress on confidentiality, the institutions will be willing to provide data for research and development purposes.

3.4.1.2 Government:

The Government has the mandate to create an enabling environment for the smooth operation of the industry. Apart from the Ministry of Trade and Industry, the Government of Ghana has also set up the National Board for Small-Scale Industries (Now the Ghana Enterprise Agency) and the Micro Finance and Small Loans Centre (MASLOC). These institutions are to provide business advisory services and grant credits to facilitate the smooth operations of SMEs in

Ghana. Data collection from these institutions only requires formal notice, which would not challenge the researcher.

3.4.1.3 Owners:

These are the primary stakeholders in the industry. They include the owners and co-owners of the various SMEs. A random selection will be made across the various sectors of the SME industry, and owners of the sampled SMEs will be interviewed. The study does not envisage any challenge in gathering data from this category of stakeholders. Experience has shown that with a proper introduction, SME owners are most welcome and happy to provide any requested data.

3.4.1.4 Consultancy Firms:

These private firms take advantage of the knowledge gap in the SME industries to provide essential services for a fee. Most of them have a good database of SMEs in their catchment area. An interaction with them could reveal much information on SMEs around the study area. This study has identified Star Brand Consult, a consulting firm for SMEs and has since been in touch with them. The researcher will snowball the remaining consultancy firms in the Municipality for data collection with Star Brand Consult.

3.5 Targeted Population for the Study

The Wa Municipality houses 5,370 of the 13,728 business establishments in the Upper West Region of Ghana (Ghana Statistical Service; IBESS Summary Report, 2015). The population of this study will be a sample of SMEs among the business establishments in the Wa

Municipality. The Wa Municipality is selected because it contains 39.12% of all the businesses in the Upper West Region. In manufacturing, the Municipality contains 38.19%, 39.4% in the service industry, and 28% in the Upper West Region agricultural establishments. The Wa Municipality has the highest percentage of formal establishment, at only- 10.1% in the Upper West Region. Interestingly, 42.96% of the dominant sole proprietorships in the Upper West Region are in the Wa Municipality (GSS, Regional Spatial Report, 2016).

3.5.1 Population sampling

Unlike (Nkuah et al., 2013), who selected 80 respondents in the same environment for a similar study, this research will sample 281 for its intended quantitative study.

As used by most quantitative researchers, the probability sample size is used to select the sample for this study. The study selected its survey respondents based on probability sampling. The total number of SMEs in the Wa Municipality is 947 establishments (GSS, Regional Spatial Report, 2016, p.256).

A formula for determining sample size given by Miller and Brewer (2003) was used to have a sample that is devoid of bias. Thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(\alpha)^2}$$

Where n = required sample size, 1= constant, N = Population =947, α = level of significance or margin of error = 0.05. To have a proper representative sample size, the sample size is determined at a 95% confidence level (at a 0.05 significance level). Therefore:

$$n = \frac{947}{1+947(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 281.22 \approx 281$$

Using the above formula, the sample size of the survey is 281.

The 281-sample size will be selected across all the different SME sectors in the Municipality to give a fair representation, as Saunders et al. (2006) suggested. Two hundred sixty-eight (268) of the samples will be for SME managers, nine (9) for financial institutions and four (4) for SME advisory institutions. Nkuah et al., (2013) identified the following as the existing SMEs in the Wa municipality of Ghana; Chop bar operators/fast-food operators/restaurants, tailors/dressmakers, Textile/Leather Works, Woodworking, Metal Fabricating, Repair Services, Auto repairs, chemical sellers/pharmacies, and retailers, spare part dealers, motorbike dealers, hairdressers/barbers and sachet water producers.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

Both primary and secondary data will be used in this research. The interview of SME operators, Financial Institutions, VSLA groups, the institutional heads of MASLOC, GEA, and other private business advisory service providers in the Wa Municipality constitute the primary components of the data for this survey. The secondary data for this study is made of highly recognised publications on SMEs, drafted SME policies, books and journal articles from reliable internet sources. Most significantly, the Integrated Business Establishment Surveys I & II reports conducted by the Ghana Statistical Service and the final drafted copy of Ghana's SME policy guide were highly patronised.

3.6.1 Primary Data Collection

In August 2020, the primary data collection for this study was conducted in Wa in the Upper West Region of Ghana. Using structured questionnaires and personal observations were employed as the survey falls under quantitative study. This type of interview fed the author a deeper understanding of the subject matter through the respondents (Gabriel and Griffiths, 2014; 114; cited in Saunders et al. 2016, p. 135-141). Precisely, two hundred and eighty-one

(281) structured interviews were conducted. Two hundred and sixty-eight (268) of the survey were responded to by SME managers, nine (9) by the management of financial institutions and the remaining four (4) by the proprietors of SME Advisory Institutions.

3.6.2 Secondary Data Collection

The secondary data component of this study will focus mainly on reliable sources (Journal of Publications) to access relevant previous studies and historically published government reports by the Ghana Statistical Service on SMEs and The Ministry of Trade & Industry (especially the drafted copy of the SME policy guide). Archival records on SMEs in the Wa Municipality will also be accessed.

3.7 Limitation of data collection

Research of this nature is bound to encounter some form of limitations. The following are the restrictions encountered by this study:

3.7.1 Resource limitation

The primary investigator limited the research to the Wa Municipality of the Upper West Region of Ghana alone. The above was necessitated by the high cost of carrying out a nationwide sampling to ensure respondents were drawn from all sixteen administration regions of Ghana.

Moreover, the fact that the ism for this study was championed mainly by the primary investigator restricts the research to the sole intellectual ability of the researcher. Although the researcher has demonstrated enough knowledge in the subject area, which has helped shape the study, it does not take away the fact that the outcome is influenced by his involvement (Musabayana, 2012).

Most importantly, the researcher had plans to conduct a focused group discussion that would include the three main stakeholders of this study. The idea was to bring together selected SME managers, Financing Institutions and Advisory Institutions. Also, to be invited includes the Director of this Studies, the Upper West Regional Minister, heads of departments and the media for a proper deliberation on the subject matter. Unfortunately, resource limitations coupled with the outbreak of Covid-19 prevented this seminar from taking place. The researcher still nurtures the idea of hosting this seminar in the future.

3.7.2 Women Participation

This study has revealed that 47.4% of women are SME owners. This milestone was not achieved without the usual male dominance and interference. The researcher faced many situations where women SME owners portrayed their husbands as business owners instead of themselves. There is a longstanding cultural phenomenon in most Ghanaian homes where it is assumed that the man owns everything, including whatever the woman would have achieved through her efforts. The man mainly attends to strangers, and because most SMEs are attached to the owner's residence, many of these challenges occur during the data collection process. It took the researcher's experience to get the men to give way to their spouses to answer the applicable questionnaires. Nonetheless, about five (5) men insisted they had to sit and listen to the conversation, which did not allow the respondents to express themselves well and most likely would have impacted the study outcome.

3.7.3 Fear of Taxation

Most SMEs are not formalised and do not pay taxes, or where formalised; they do not pay the required taxes. The above has made it difficult to get the correct information from such businesses as they see it as means of potentially getting them into the tax books. Despite the

assurance and notice of confidentiality, the fear of potentially paying taxes is a limitation on the outcome of this research work (Ackah and Vuvor, 2011).

3.7.4 Covid-19 Impact

The Covid-19 virus has struck the whole world. That has left businesses, especially SMEs struggling for survival. The impact is even worse on SMEs in developing countries like Ghana, where this research is being carried out. There is little government intervention, and because most of these SMEs are not formalised, it is difficult for them to access such support. The above undoubtedly affected the responses during the data collection process, as the study was conducted in the heat of the Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 impact rendered most respondents kitschy, resulting in responses that mainly were lamentations and complaints. Undoubtedly, the Covid-19 impact is a limitation on the study's outcome.

3.8 Objectivity, Reliability and Validity of Data

A business research study of this nature is a reliable source of information for companies. The understudied firms and their likes use the survey results to make critical decisions to ensure growth and profit-making. Because of that, such surveys are typically tailored to the specifications of the company/sector being studied, just as it is done for this study. More so, the outcome of a successful business survey should most likely reflect the strategic plans of the beneficiary companies. Given the above, ensuring closeness to reality regarding the outcome of a business survey is critical. The reality mentioned above can be achieved by ensuring that the data-collecting methods are subjected to the following quality control measures; Objectivity, Reliability and Validity.

3.8.1 Objectivity

An online Market Researching Firm, Appirio (2021), defined Objectivity as a survey whose outcome is “independent of the market researchers who conduct, evaluate and interpret them” (ibid). They further classified Objectivity under the following; Objectivity during data collection, Objectivity during evaluation and Objectivity during interpretations.

3.8.1.1 Objectivity during data collection

During data collection, (ibid) believes that the interviewer should not influence who a sample group or who a respondent should be. As much as possible, high standards should be ensured for the condition under which the study is carried out. More importantly, the survey result should be independent of the person carrying out the research. To achieve Objectivity during data collection, this study resulted in a random sampling of its respondents and the coding of questionnaires. The above has helped curtail any possible influence the researcher might have on the responses received during data processing and report writing.

3.8.1.2 Objectivity during an Evaluation

According to (ibid), Objectivity during survey evaluation is achieved when the outcome of a survey conducted by different researchers produces a match. A survey questionnaire should be standardised enough to produce the same evaluated result after being administered by different researchers. In a nutshell, the data evaluation should be independent of the researcher and follow some pre-determined rules to ensure any possible comparison between the outcomes of similar surveys (ibid). To ensure Objectivity during evaluation, a pilot study was conducted first with the same survey questionnaires before the primary data collection was done. Different researchers carried out the pilot and primary surveys, and interestingly, the outcome was the same after evaluation. In a nutshell, the questionnaire standards for this survey were tested and approved.

3.8.1.3 Objectivity during Interpretation

To achieve Objectivity during the interpretation of survey results, it is essential to set out clear procedures for interpreting the available survey results. The procedures mentioned above are primarily set to avoid subjectivity during the interpretation by the individual researchers. Ensuring that all those involved in evaluating a particular study arrive at the same outcome is vital. According to (ibid), Objectivity can easily be achieved when possible human influences have been reduced drastically. Reducing human influence is achievable through automation and digitalising research processes (ibid). This study ensured Objectivity through coding, data cleansing and interpretation using the Scientific Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS Statistics 25). This automated process has helped reduce human involvement drastically. Most importantly, the survey outcome produced a remarkable homogeneity between the stakeholders' expectations in this study.

3.8.3 Reliability

Achieving survey objectivity, as mentioned above, means the ground is adequately prepared for the checks on the reliability of that study to be carried out. A reliable survey ensures that a research questionnaire produces the same results, even if it is answered by different respondents or carried out by the same respondents at different times (ibid). Reliability checks have been successful under this thesis as the study often recorded the same results from multiple respondents during the data collection process.

3.8.4 Validity

A survey can adequately be valid after successfully going through the Objectivity and reliability checks explained above. A valid questionnaire produces precisely the responses a firm yearns to possess. According to (ibid), validity can be classified into internal and external. To ascertain the internal validity of a questionnaire, the survey must demonstrate that an

independent variable influences a dependent variable in market research. An example is establishing the influence an SME's design of a product (independent variable) has on the willingness of its customers to purchase and consume such a product (dependent variable). Specifically, the internal validity of a survey questionnaire is said to be high if a change in the independent variable (design of a product) is a result of a change in the dependent variable (willingness to purchase) (ibid).

Nonetheless, a survey questionnaire is considered externally valid if its outcome is highly representative and universal. In other words, an externally valid survey questionnaire measures the linkage between survey responses and the fundamental behaviour of the respondents. For example, if an SME wants to ascertain whether a customer is interested in buying bread subsequently (independent variable), the responses provided by the respondent (dependent variable) must excogitate reality. In a nutshell, an externally valid questionnaire ensures responses that reflect the actual conduct of the respondents (ibid).

3.9 Ethical issues in this study

The following ethical principles of research of the University of West Scotland were upheld to ensure the study follows the ethical practices of standard doctoral-level business management research:

3.9.1 Confidentiality and Anonymity

Research of this nature requires adequate assurance of strict confidentiality to respondents regarding how their responses would be treated. The respondents for this study were highly assured of the privacy and confidentiality of their responses and the anonymity of their identity. They were made to understand that coding would be employed to anonymise each interview

and the respondent's name. The codes denoting interview responses were inscribed in all analytical sections throughout the research.

The responses were confidently protected and, as soon as possible, transferred onto a computer that is protected by a password. Finally, all hardcopy data will be destroyed immediately after the data processing is over.

3.9.2 Autonomy

The autonomous consent of participants was requested to confirm their voluntary willingness to participate in the interview process before the start of every interview. Both written and verbal explanations were used to ensure respondents were adequately informed and up-to-date with what was about to happen. Participants were informed that they could withdraw from the interview at any time. Participants were given the contact information of the primary investigator so they could contact him on any latest development concerning their participation. It was refreshing to note that all the sampled participants willingly complied and completed the questionnaires.

3.9.3 Non-maleficence and Beneficence

Participants' physical and emotional safety is essential during the data collection period. Therefore, the participants were encouraged to contact the author in case of any unfortunate development or when they will require some explanations about this study.

3.9.4 Justice and Inclusiveness

The research ensured an all-inclusive approach. No discrimination in race, gender, sexual orientation, religion, ethnicity, culture, disability or language was entertained during the selection process. The selection was random, with no pre-information on the private life of any selected respondents. Participants were assured of equal treatment of all the data gathered for

the study. All respondents were also informed that they would have access to a copy of the research after it is completed and upon request as a benefit of partaking in the study.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

This chapter details the data analysis processes this thesis employs, quantitative data analysis and quantitative report writing structure. As a quantitative study analysed through ‘Descripto-Explanato-Evaluative’ Statistics, this chapter will include the statistical analysis of the data, Tables, pie charts, and histograms. This chapter will primarily present the results of the analysed data, whilst the technical analysis through cross-tabulations, correlations, and regression will be in a subsequent Chapter Five. Avoiding the confusion that arises between data presentation and discussion/findings meant for Chapters Four/Five and Six; respectively, this study has distinguished between Chapters Four/Five and Six through the questions: "What I found" and "What judgement I have formed based on what I found" respectively as suggested by Saunders et al. (2016, p. 640).

Also, this chapter seeks to detail the responses to the research questions illustrated in chapter one in a possibly precise manner for the easy assimilation of the respective audience of this research. This study will endeavour to structure its findings accurately, coherently, and in a manner that the targeted audience can easily understand. The above is possible by referring to the research objectives as a guide for presenting the findings of this dissertation (ibid).

4.1 Data Analysis Process

According to Adèr (2008), as cited by Adjei (2012): Data Analysis is a process involving "editing, cleaning, transforming, and modelling data to highlight useful information, suggestion, conclusions, and supporting decision making". Data cleansing was done through editing to reveal errors and identify the questions left unattended. This study ensured synergy in the responses provided and spotted the correct answers from the inconsistent responses that

allowed editing. The coded responses were securely transferred onto a computer through data entry to pave the way for a comprehensive quantitative data analysis.

4.1.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

Data collected quantitatively are usually in a state best described as raw data and would typically require some level of processing, analysis and interpretation to make meaning out of them. The quantitative data analysis is courtesy of the Scientific Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 25). To achieve accuracy in this study and considering the structure of the questionnaire, this dissertation employs 'Descripto-Explanato-Evaluative' Statistics as the medium for data analysis.

4.1.2 'Descripto-Explanato-Evaluative' Statistics

'Descripto-Explanato-Evaluative' Statistics is a combined study of three different research purposes: descriptive statistics, explanatory statistics and evaluative statistics coined together as: 'Descripto-Explanato-Evaluative' Statistics. The above research purposes were carefully selected based on the study design and expected outcomes.

The first two purposes (descriptive and explanatory statistics) are used for the primary data analysis and presentation (Chapters Four and Five). The final purpose (evaluative statistics) is used in Chapter Six to evaluate some secondary data as part of the research findings. The descriptive statistics employed are a means to an end, not an end itself. It forms the basis for explanatory statistics through cross-tabulations, chi-square, correlation and regression analysis. The study later employs evaluative statistics to assess the effectiveness of SME policy documents of some selected countries that are ranked at the top of the doing business index in Africa.

According to Saunders et al. (2016, p. 175), “The Purpose of descriptive research is to gain an accurate profile of events, persons or situations”. These analyses are strengthened with evidence from journal articles and real-life examples (Adjei, 2012).

On the other hand, explanatory research emphasises the study of a situation to understand the relationships between the variables involved. The above is done through cross-tabulations and correlation analysis (Saunders et al. 2016, p.176).

Finally, evaluative statistics investigates how better something functions. In this context, evaluative statistics is centred on assessing the effectiveness of the SME policy documents of some African countries ranked on top of the 'Doing Business Index' and using that as a guide to making recommendations for Ghana's SME policy document (ibid).

4.1.3 Quantitative report writing

Writing reports on dissertations may take different formats. It may be the popular traditional method or an alternative outline recognising a chosen research strategy. This study employs the traditional structure for dissertation writing. The chosen traditional structure emphasises the logical system employed and the linear-analytic approach followed in conducting the deductive approach to the theory as in the case of this research work. The traditional approach was described by Charmaz (2006) as 'logico-deductive' according to (Saunders et al. 2016, p.633). Below is the structure of the chosen traditional approach for this dissertation writing:

Abstract

- 1. Introduction*
- 2. Literature Review*
- 3. Methodology/Method*
- 4. Data Analysis/Presentation*
- 5. Cross Tabulations: Testing for statistically significant relationships and differences*
- 6. Findings/Results /Discussion*
- 7. Conclusion/Recommendation, References/Bibliography And Appendices*

Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016 p.634

According to Yin (2014), the linear-analytic approach is one of the six underlying 'reporting approaches' to emphasize a chosen reporting structure (i.e., traditional or alternative). With the linear-analytic approach, a dissertation's structure reports logically to excogitate the research process. This approach is fundamental to the traditional approach and suits the deductive approach to the theory, as in the case of this thesis.

The remaining underlying 'reporting approaches', according to Yin (2014), are the comparative, chronological approach; theory-building approach; suspense approach and unsequence approach.

4.2 PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

This study has designed three questionnaires to solicit the correct data for analysis, presentation and discussion of findings. The questionnaires were designed based on the formulated research questions and their accompanying objectives in chapter one above. The first set of questionnaires, titled: *Questionnaire for SME Managers*, is primarily on SME management, which aligns with this study's first specific research question that seeks answers on *the managerial challenges SMEs face in Ghana*. The second set of questionnaires, titled: *Questionnaire for SME Financing Institutions*, is generally on SME credit accessibility and aligned to this dissertation's second specific research question, which assays answers for *the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana*. The third set of questionnaires is titled: *Questionnaire for SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions*. It is mainly on developing SME Policy Document for Ghana as stipulated by this study's third and final specific research question. The final research question looks for answers to the *guidelines that can enhance the management and financing of SMEs in Ghana*.

Specifically, the questionnaire for SME management is designed to gather demographic data of SME operators, the existing management practices employed by these SMEs, the kind of credit/bursaries available to SMEs, and their abilities/inabilities to access them. The questionnaire finally gathers data on developing a comprehensive SME policy document for Ghana.

The questionnaire for SME Financing Institutions is carved to solicit demographic data from the credit institutions; the specific products they have available for SME development and how accessible it has been so far; the kind of requirements they demand from SMEs before granting access to credits; and finally, their recommendation as far as developing a comprehensive SME Policy document for Ghana is concerned.

The third and final set of questionnaires is for SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes. These are the technical entities providing technical advisory services to SME operators. Their questionnaire is centred explicitly on gathering data on the kind of skill development training given to SMEs and how accessible they are. Also, they seek to gather data on the impact the pieces of training have had on the SMEs that have accessed them. Moreover, finally, their recommendations on developing a comprehensive SME policy for Ghanaian SMEs.

From the above, it is worth mentioning that each set of questionnaires is also designed to have at least some questions that solicit data for the three leading research questions. The questionnaires are divided into sections, each seeking data for the three specific research questions. Thus, a section gathers data on SME management challenges, a section on SME credit accessibility challenges, and a section that seeks the views of the various respondents on developing an SME Policy Document for Ghana. This is to say, one set of questionnaires could have been used for a study of this kind, but this study did resolve to use three different sets of questionnaires, as explained above, to increase the scope of the research.

4.3 DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF RESPONDENTS

This part of the questionnaire was designed to elicit information on the demographic statistics of the respondents using all three sets of questionnaires stated above. These data include sex, age, and highest educational level. For confidentiality and to ensure anonymity, the names and positions held by the respondents were not captured on the questionnaires. Descriptive data analysis and presentation for all three sets of questionnaires are done tripartitely to reflect all the data received. In alignment with the specific research questions and their corresponding objectives, as stated in chapter one of this thesis, the demographic data analysed will be presented in the following order: Analysed data on SME Managers, Analysed data on SME Credit institutions, and analysed data on SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes. The

first demographic question to be analysed in the above-stated format is the sex of respondents. It will be followed by the age and educational level of respondents, respectively:

4.3.1 Sex of Respondents

Contrary to (Abor and Quartey, 2010) and the 2010 Populations and Housing Census that reported that Women dominate SMEs in Ghana, this study has recorded more male (52.6%) respondents than their female (47.4%) counterparts. Question one (1) was responsible for gathering this data, which read "*Gender of respondents*". The question was more likely dichotomous, so only '*Male and Female*' provided possible answers for the respondents. From the data received, there were 5.2% more male respondents than females. Out of the 268 total questionnaires for SME operators, 141 were responded to by males, whilst females administered the remaining 127. Because of the culture of male dominance in the sampled area, there is still a chance that most of the SMEs are owned by women but only led by men, as documented by the literature review and the Ghana Statistical Service in their 2010 Population and Housing Census.

Elsewhere, the same question on gender was posed to the respondents from the SME Financing Institutions, and the narrative was not different. Of the nine (9) Credit institutions interviewed, seven (7) of them, representing 77.8%, were responded by males. The above implies that only two (2) Credit institutions had females among the top decision-makers. The two (2) female respondents translated into a worrying 22.2% in a sector that serves a significant number of women clientele.

Finally, the same question on gender was posed to the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions, and there was a more shocking revelation of 100% male respondents. This dominant male sector seeks to serve an industry with many females in a gender-segregated environment like Ghana. This partly explains why 50% of the SMEs Skill Development and

Advisory Institutions recorded less than twenty (20) clients in a year, as revealed by question six (6) of the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions.

4.3.2 Age of Respondents

Ensuring that every respondent falls within the acceptable age group for a study of this nature is very important. Because of the above, this study sought to document the ages of the sampled people to respond to the questionnaires. Question two (2) was designed to solicit data on respondents' age. The question was framed as "*Age of respondents*". For its corresponding answers, age was stratified as follows; 18-30, 31-40, 41-50, 51-60, 61-70 and Other (Specify).

The minimum legal age for participating in any essential national assignment in Ghana is 18 years. In line with that, this study pegged its minimum age for a respondent to be 18 years. From the responses gathered, the results outline the majority of respondents to be between the youthful category of 18-30 (40.7%), followed by those between 31-40 (27.8%), then by 41-50 (20%), before ending with those within the 51-60 (11.6%) age grouping. Interestingly, the youth form the majority in Ghana (2021 Populations and Housing Census: General Report Volume 3B, p103), and therefore not surprising that they form the majority of the respondents for the sampled SMEs.

The same question on age categories was presented to the operators of the Credit institutions, and the majority of their respondents fell within the middle age category of (41-50) years. Five (5) out of the sampled nine (9) respondents were people between the (41-50) age group. The youthful age category of (18-30) years recorded three (3) respondents, translating into 33.3% of the total sample. Lastly, those within the age group of (31-40) years recorded only one (1) respondent, which translates to 11.1% of the sampled population.

Ultimately, the same question, when tabled before the SME Advisory and Skilled Development Institutes, revealed that 50% of the respondents belonged to the youthful age group of (18-30)

years, whilst those between (31-40) and (41-50) categories both recorded 25% each of the responses.

4.3.3 Educational Level of Respondents

This part of the questionnaire for SME operators represents Question three (3). The question was framed as “*Indicate the highest level of education obtained*”. For impeccable responses, choosing respondents who had attained an appreciable level of education became necessary. Given this, the responses were grouped into: *No Formal Education, Primary Education, Junior High Education, Secondary/Technical/Vocational Educational, and Tertiary Education* to measure the level of education of the respondents for this research work. When the respondents did not have formal education, the interviewer explained the local language (Waale) to the respondent's understanding. It is also worth noting that although some respondents have no formal education, most are well-versed in English as a communication medium. Their ability to communicate in English is mainly due to students from the four tertiary institutions and eight Secondary/Technical/Vocational Schools in the Municipality. The SME managers interact with the students daily at their business centres.

Question three (3) of the SME managers questionnaire gathered responses on the level of education of the various respondents among the 268 sampled SMEs in the Wa Municipality. From the processed data, thirty-seven 37 (13.8%) have *no formal education* but can use English as a communication medium. Twenty-eight 28 (10.4%) only completed *primary education* and are also very good with English as a communication medium. Twenty-nine 29 (10.8%) completed *Junior High School*, and the majority of one hundred and one, 101 (37.7%) were *tertiary graduates*. The above affirms that the data was gathered from highly educated respondents who understood the questions very well. In a nutshell, it can be concluded that the solicited data is reliably accurate and deemed fit for its intended purpose.

The same question was asked to the staff of the Credit institutions, and an encouraging 100% of their respondents were graduates from tertiary institutions. The above, however, does not come as a surprise due to the sensitivity of the nature of the work carried out by credit institutions.

The Operators of the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes were asked the same question about the *highest level of education* obtained. 75% of the four (4) sampled respondents appeared to be graduates from *tertiary* institutions, and 25% had completed *secondary/Technical/ Vocational Institutes*. A further probe on the only one (1) respondent without a tertiary qualification revealed he joined the organisation as a trainee and has since graduated to the senior management level. Hence, he is well informed to guide SMEs and make any critical decisions on behalf of his organisation.

4.4 SME MANAGEMENT IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY OF GHANA

This section analysis and presents data from two sets of questionnaires (SME Managers Questionnaire and SME Skill Development & Advisory Institutions Questionnaires) that gathered pertinent data relating to the management constraints facing SMEs in Ghana. These questionnaires were created to answer and partly fulfil the first research question (*what are the management constraints facing SMEs in Ghana?*) and its corresponding objective (*To ascertain and address the managerial shortfalls of SMEs in Ghana*) respectively. It also ensures proper alignment running through all the sections of this research work. This section consists of questions four (4) to fifteen (15) on the SME Managers Questionnaires and questions four (4) to fourteen (14) on the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions Questionnaire. Some of the main issues that make up questions under this section include Firm/SME type, years in business, SME classification, the availability of qualified staff and the highest level of qualification on a management team. Others are: whether a management

member ever received any training and from which institution. The rest are the existence of a business plan and whether an SME practices standard bookkeeping. The percentage of profit an SME makes quarterly and whether it will welcome a comprehensive business management training centre in the region and possibly be willing to pay a token for training.

Under this section, all the questions for SME Managers (questions 4-15) will be analysed and presented before the questions for the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes (questions 4-14). The above makes it easy for readers as they are not the same and cannot be matched, as in the case of the demographic questions above.

4.4.1 SME Managers Questionnaire (refer to appendix)

4.4.1.1 The Legal Status of SMEs

Question four (4) of this survey solicited information concerning the legal status of SMEs in the Wa Municipality. The question was framed as *type of enterprise/firm*. The following was provided as the possible answers: *Sole Proprietor; Partnership; Family-Owned Business; Private Limited Company; and Public Limited Company*. The above was meant to inform the researcher and readers of the various legal ways the SMEs in the sample area were registered. It also helps during cross-tabulations with other questions. The cross-tabulations will be necessary for making informed decisions on how to address the management challenges facing SMEs, as suggested by the first objective of this thesis.

Table 4-1: Firm type and percentage of SMEs involved

Firm Type	Percentage SMEs
Sole Proprietor	89.2% (239)
Partnership	2.2% (6)
Family-Owned Business	6.7% (18)
Private Limited Company	1.9% (5)
Public Limited Company	0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

According to Table 4.1 above, more than three-quarters, 89.2% (239) of the SMEs are documented as *Sole Proprietors*. *Family-Owned Businesses* follow with eighteen (18) out of

the total two hundred and sixty-eight (268) responses, making just 6.7% of the sample. Six (6) SMEs were recorded under *Partnership*. The above represents 2.2% of the total 268 sampled questionnaires. *Private Limited Company* only managed five (5) tallies, representing 1.9% of the sample.

4.4.1.2 Number of Years SMEs Have Operated

It is common to see many start-up businesses fold up within the first few years of operating in developing economies (Blanks, 2013). Because of the above, Question number five (5) on the SME Manager’s questionnaire for this study was presented as; “*For how long has the firm (SME) been in business?*” The possible answers to this question were *Less than one year, between two and five years, between six and ten years, between eleven and fifteen years and over fifteen years*. The rationale behind this question is to allow for first-hand information on the years each sampled SME has been operating. Moreover, it would help further investigate the possible reasons behind their length of years of existence. The above-formulated question will further allow for cross-tabulations with other related questions to reveal information that will help this study make decisive conclusions.

Table 4-2: SMEs' number of years in business

Number of years in business	Percentage of SMEs
Less than one year	15 SMEs (5.6%)
between two and five years	97 SMEs (36.2%)
between six and ten years	96 SMEs (35.8%)
between eleven and fifteen years	39 SMEs (14.6%)
over fifteen years	21 SMEs (7.8%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

After a successful field visit, the data in Table 4.2 above show that most (36.2%) of SMEs have been operating *for two to five years* since their establishment. Moreover, a promising 7.8% representing twenty-one (21) respondents, have been operating for *over 15 years*. The above contradicts the findings by (2010); because most SMEs lack management skills, they fold up within two years of operation. Only 15 SMEs (5.6%) were still operating within a year of their

establishment. The remaining SMEs were operating between six and fifteen years, as illustrated in the Table above. The above defies the research by Mungal and Garbharran (2014); only one (1) out of ten (10) SMEs is likely to survive within ten (10) years of existence.

Interestingly, the data suggest that most SMEs prosper between their second and tenth year, indicating that SMEs are very active within this period. However, less than half of them can progress beyond ten years for obvious reasons like competition, lack of finance to expand, inadequate technology to innovate and inadequate managerial competencies to efficiently run the businesses (Abor and Quartey, 2010). The situation is further aggravated as they approach their fifteenth year of existence, as only half of those who made it beyond ten years can operate beyond fifteen years.

4.4.1.3 SMEs By Classification

Making an informed decision on how constrained SMEs are by their management strength and ability to access credit requires comprehensive data on their various classifications. Moreover, similar studies have reported different data on SME classification depending on their sample areas. Question six (6) was designed to request information on SME classification. The question was designed as "*How will one classify the organisation (SME)?*" Moreover, the following answers: *Micro (Between 1 and 5 employees)*, *Small (Between 6 and 30 employees)*, *Medium (Between 31 and 100 employees)*, and *Large (over 100)* were made available. The solicited data will be interpreted and cross-tabulated with similar questions to make concrete conclusions concerning this study's research questions and objectives. The question is centred on classifying the various SMEs in the Wa Municipality of The Upper West Region of Ghana. Amoah and Amoah (2018) purported that most SMEs are classified as Micro (employing between 1 and 5 staff). In the case of this study, a total of two hundred and twenty-one (221) responses, representing 82.5%, corresponding to this category. The second classification that received more responses was the Small SMEs (Between 6 and 30 employees), with forty-four

(44) responses, translating into 16.4%. Finally, only three (3) SMEs out of the two hundred and sixty-eight (268) sampled SMEs, responded in favour of medium size SMEs (Between 31 and 100), resulting in only 1.1% of the total responses.

The data reveals that most SMEs are stuck at the micro level. It is apparent that most of these SMEs are stagnated in growth and cannot transform into small, medium and large companies (Mungal and Garbharran, 2014) capable of creating the needed employment and contributing immensely to GDP. For a smooth and more effortless transition of SMEs into the various higher classifications, their management and credit accessibility deficiencies must be addressed, as suggested by this thesis's research questions and objectives.

4.4.1.4 Availability of Qualified Staff

The inability of SMEs to grow as expected has partly been attributed to their inability to hire the required number of qualified staff (ibid). Question seven (7) was designed to solicit the data from the sampled SMEs for analysis and presentation. The solicited data was meant to help abreast the researcher with information on the type of staff the sampled SMEs have managed to employ for their daily activities and the possible effects of that on the sustainability and growth of the SME. Question seven (7) reads as *"Are there the required number of qualified staff for the organisation (SME)?"* and the corresponding answers were: *Yes, there are qualified staff for all the roles; Yes, there are staff for all the roles, but they are not qualified; and No, one person performs multiple roles because there is no enough staff.* After a successful data collection exercise and analysis, only seventy (70) out of the two-hundred and sixty-eight (268) responses, representing 26.1% of the sampled SMEs, have the required staff for their roles. Also, sixty-two (62), representing 23.1% of SMEs, operate with unqualified staff. Interestingly, more than half (50.8%) of all sampled SMEs have only one person performing all the roles.

4.4.1.5 Highest Qualification on The Management Team

Question eight (8) was constructed to solicit responses from the SMEs on the highest qualification on the management team. The above allows the study to measure the impact of the level of education on the performance of SMEs through graphing and cross-tabulation using IBM SPSS 25. The processed data will further allow for recommendations in line with the outlined research questions of this study. The question was presented as follows: *What is the highest qualification on the management team?* The following were possible answers: *Senior High School Certificate, Diploma, Degree, Master, Primary Education, Junior High School Certificate and None*. It is important to note that, Question Eight differs from Question Three as the latter requested the respondent's educational level, which may not be the highest on the management team as the latter seeks to solicit. From the solicited data, the majority of one hundred SMEs representing 37.3% of the sampled respondents, have their most qualified staff to be *Senior High School Certificate* holders. That was possible because most school dropouts turned to establish a small business to survive. Finding decent employment as a school dropout in Ghana and most developing economies is almost impossible. The second-highest qualification that the SMEs documented is the diploma certificate. Fifty-four (54) SMEs representing 20.1% of the sampled SMEs, had *diploma holders* as the most qualified management team. Of the sampled data, the SMEs that documented *first degree* as the highest qualification on their team were forty-seven (47) SMEs, representing 17.5%.

Interestingly, twenty-eight (28), 10.4% of the sampled respondents documented that they did not have anyone with formal education on their management team. They run their businesses without any formal education. Also, twenty-five (25) SMEs representing 7.8%, recorded *Junior High School* as the highest qualification on their management team. The SMEs with *Primary School Graduates* as the most qualified, followed by twelve (12) responses, representing 4.5%. Lastly, the SMEs' highest qualification (master's degree) is the least

documented on the list. Only six (6) SMEs, representing 2.2% of the total sample, have master's degree holders as the most qualified staff on their management team.

4.4.1.6 Capacity Building Training for SME Management Team

Continued refresher training for SMEs is vital for their sustenance, growth, and competitiveness in local and global business environments. Nonetheless, most businesses often fall under the classifications of SMEs (Mungal and Garbharran, 2014). Ackah and Vuvor (2011) attributed the failure of these SMEs to the absence of the required skills among the staff of SMEs. In line with the above, this study seeks to determine whether SMEs in the sample area have the necessary training skills to transform their businesses into more viable and prominent entities. Question nine (9) was composed for this purpose. It reads: *Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service or financial management)?* As a dichotomous question, the following two answers were provided, *Yes and No*, to solicit the responses of the SMEs concerning the question asked. The responses gathered have been illustrated in Figure 4.1 below:

Figure 4-1: SME management that has received capacity-building training

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Figure 4.1 above is a pie chart illustrating the results on whether SMEs have ever received any form of training specifically tailored towards building their capacity for efficiency. Of the 268 sampled SMEs, only ninety-eight (98), representing 36.6%, documented that they have ever received capacity training to increase efficiency. Surprisingly, the remaining one hundred seventy (170), representing 63.4%, responded that they have never received any form of capacity training. The above is consistent with Mungal and Garbharran, (2014) deduction that most SMEs lack the required training.

4.4.1.7 Source of SME Capacity Building Training

As a follow-up to question nine (9), question ten (10) read as; *If yes to question 9, which institution offered the training? If no, skip questioning eleven (11)*. This was to inform the study about the type of SME training institutions available and how accessible they have been. The following multiple answers were provided for the respondents: *A University/College, An NGO, Government, Internal (CEO), and others*. From the data obtained, most respondents were trained by A university/college (46), representing 47%. NGOs are second on the list of institutions that provide training for SMEs. Forty-one (41) SMEs, representing 41.8%, were trained by NGOs. Surprisingly, the institution mandated by the government (NBSSI) to train SMEs managed only seven (7) SMEs, representing 7.1% of the total sample. Four (4) SMEs representing 4.1%, documented that they got trained internally by their CEOs.

4.4.1.8 The Existence of a Business Plan

Question eleven (11) was designed to solicit data on whether SMEs have an existing business plan that guides their operations. The question was posed: *Does the organisation (SME) have an existing business plan?* Dichotomous answers of *Yes* or *No* were provided to solicit responses from the sampled SMEs. The responses were meant to equip the study with relevant

information per the research objectives. The responses gathered are presented below in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4-2: SMEs with a business plan

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Figure 4.2 above is the summary of the results that were gathered on whether SMEs have an existing business plan. Of the 268 respondents, only eighty-eight (88) of the SMEs documented that they had existing business plans. The remaining one hundred and eighty (180), representing 67.2%, had no written plan for their businesses.

4.4.1.9 The Practice of Standard Bookkeeping

Mungal and Garbharran (2014) documented that most SMEs do not find bookkeeping necessary because they find it a means of time-wasting. In line with this, question twelve (12) was composed to determine the state of the sampled SMEs regarding bookkeeping. Thus the question read; *Does the organisation (SME) practice standard bookkeeping?* For the proper responses to be gathered, the following responses were presented to the respondents to make their choices: *Yes, all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly. Yes, but sometimes personal finances get mixed up with business capital. No, the organisation does not keep any accounting records at all.* One hundred and forty-four (144) SMEs representing

53.7%, responded to practising standard bookkeeping from the information received. Ninety (90) of the sampled SMEs, representing 33.6%, responded that they do not practice any form of bookkeeping. Thus, they do not keep any form of record for the businesses. Thirty-four (34) of the SMEs, representing 12.7%, also mentioned that they partially practice bookkeeping as sometimes the owner’s money gets mixed up with the business capital.

4.4.1.10 Quarterly Percentage of Profit on Investment Capital

The rationale of every SME is to maximise profit and minimise cost. Profit-making is necessary for the sustainability and growth of every business. Various studies suggest that SMEs struggle to manage their finances and cannot make profits. To ascertain the above accession, question thirteen (13) on the SME managers questionnaire was dedicated to soliciting information relating to the quarterly profit margins of SMEs in the sampled study region. The question was posed: *What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital?* Table 4.3 below is a summary of the results from the field visit:

Table 4-3: SMEs' quarterly profit

Quarterly profit	Number/percentage of SMEs
Less than 10%	22 SMEs (8.2%)
Between 10% and 20%	121 SMEs (45.1%)
Between 20% and 30%	77 SMEs (28.7%)
Between 30% and 50%	27 SMEs (10.1%)
Between 50% and 100%	21 SMEs (7.8%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

A glance through the data received and shown in Table 4.3 reveals that all sampled SMEs made some profits. The majority of one hundred and twenty-one (121), representing 45.1% of SMEs, make a quarterly profit between 10% and 20%. Seventy-seven (77) SMEs out of the sampled two hundred and sixty-eight (268), representing 28.7%, also made a quarterly profit between 20% and 30%. Also, twenty-seven SMEs representing 10.1% are documented to be making a quarterly profit of 30% and 50%. The remaining twenty-one (21) SMEs representing 7.8%, make a quarterly profit between 50% and 100%. Interestingly, No SME documented a loss and made more than 100% profit in a quarter.

4.4.1.11 *The creation of a well-structured business management training centre in the Wa Municipality*

Continual business development training keeps SMEs relevant to innovate and compete globally. These pieces of training may come in the form of technological advancement, bookkeeping, supply chain management, customer service, credit and general management. More importantly, when a significant number of SME operators do not have formal education, it is not just enough to run training courses but to run them in the local dialect to appreciate all parties involved. To seek the views of the SME managers on this subject matter, question fourteen (14) was designed to gather the required data. Question 14 reads: *Will the organisation welcome a well-structured business management training centre in the region accessible for practical business training/mentoring purposes with the capacity to train in the local dialect?* As a dichotomous question, the only answers provided were *True* and *False*. The result of the collated answers has been tabulated in Table 4.4 below.

Table 4-4: SMEs advocating for the creation of a business management training Centre

Role	Input	Output	Percentage
1	Yes	252	94.0%
2	No	16	6.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4.4 above shows the tabulated results on whether SMEs will welcome a structured business management training centre in the region. Of the two hundred and sixty-eight (268) sampled respondents, 94% documented; *Yes*, whilst the remaining 6% declined the proposal. The above is an emphatic endorsement of the proposal to establish a business management training centre to train SME managers in their local dialect.

4.4.1.12 The willingness of SMEs to pay a token for business management training

As a follow-up to creating a well-structured business management training centre for SME development, as stated above, question fifteen (15) was created to ask respondents whether they will be willing to pay a token for such essential training if the need arises. The question reads; *If yes, to question fourteen (14) above, will the organisation be willing to pay a token for their services?* The answers available to respondents are; *Yes or No*. This question seeks the SME operators' views on the possibility of a private person taking up the challenge of providing such services at a fee. The participation of the private sector will be vital as it will take a lot of political interventions to get the government to accept and fully implement the outcomes of this thesis to benefit SMEs in the country. Furthermore, when the government finally comes in to implement these suggestions, the private sector involvement is still critical in providing the needed competition necessary to bring out the best in both competitors to benefit the SMEs involved.

After analysing the responses from the field, the two hundred and fifty-two (252) respondents that initially agreed to create the SME training centre, as stated in question fourteen (14) above, were to choose *yes or no* as their answers. Out of the total sample of two hundred and fifty-two (252), two hundred and forty (240) of them responded that they would be willing to pay a token for the training should the need arise (yes). They constitute 95.2% of the respondents, while the remaining 4.8% represent those who do not want to pay for the training (no). They constitute only twelve (12) respondents of the total sample.

4.4.2 SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions Questionnaire (refer to appendix)

4.4.2.1 Products Offered to SMEs.

As a major stakeholder for SME Skill Development in Ghana, this dissertation finds out first-hand what specific products these institutions offer the SMEs that patronise their services to get the needed responses. Question four (4) was dedicated to that purpose. It reads; *What kind of products do the organisation offer SMEs?* For homogeneity and after comprehensive consultations, the following responses were generated as the most likely choices for the respondents: *Financial Management Training; Skills Development Training; Business Advisory Services; Referral Services; and Others (Specify)*. After data collection and analysis, 50% of the respondents said they offer Financial Management Training. Another 50% stated they offer General Business Advisory services to their clients. None of the four (4) sampled institutions offer Skill Development Training or Business Referral Services. This data comes in handy as it allows this study to make critical recommendations on the crucial SME training needs that the existing SME advisory institutions do not cover.

4.4.2.2 Details of the selected products in question four (4) above

question five (5) is a follow-up to question four (4) above to allow the respondents to elaborate on the product they offer their clientele. The question is presented as *Please explain your selected product in question four above*. The above is an open question and does not have any possible answers for them to make a choice. The respondents used their discretion and understanding of what makes up the selected products above. Sometimes, they referred to documents or sought clarifications from other colleagues before their desired responses. Nonetheless, after reviewing the responses received from the survey, it appears all four sampled institutions documented that: *Clients are trained based on their needs; we generally take clients*

through (Business Modules, Accounting Systems, and Business Growth Strategies). This question was necessary as it has brought to light exactly where this dissertation would focus when recommending comprehensive and practical SME management training modules.

4.4.2.3 The average number of clients that access the services of the organisation annually

The SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions' success largely depends on the number of SMEs that access their services. Given the above, a question was introduced to solicit data on this subject matter. The questions read: *How many clients, on average, access the organisation's services in a year?* The following possible answers were provided for the respondents: *Below 20; Between 21 and 50; Between 51 and 75; Between 75 and 100; and Above 100*. After the data collection and analysis, 50% of the total sampled respondents selected *Below 20* as their answer. In other words, two (2) out of the four (4) identified SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institutions attend to less than 20 SMEs annually in a region with an SME population of over 5000 (Ghana Statistical Service: 2010 Population and Housing Census, District Analytical Report, Wa Municipal, 2014 p36). For the remaining respondents, 25% documented that they serve *Between 21 and 50* SMEs a year. The last quarter of respondents did affirm that they receive *Between 51 and 75 clients* annually.

This question reveals many gaps between the SMEs and Skill Development & Advisory Institutions. The revealed gaps are grounds for the study to contribute to practice in chapter

five. The above is a worrying revelation as it confirms the existence of management challenges among SMEs in the sample area, as purported by earlier researchers.

4.4.2.4 Staying in touch with clients to monitor progress

Monitoring and evaluating SMEs' performance is necessary for their holistic growth, much so after they have undergone some skills development training. This study needed to establish this critical relationship between SME Skill development & Advisory Institutions and their clientele. Because of the above, question seven was a follow-up to question six. *Does the organisation follow up on its clients to monitor their progress after providing services? If no, to question nine, skip questioning ten.* The question was straightforward and required the following dichotomous answers; *Yes or No*. After collecting and analysing the data, 75% of the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions documented that they contact their clients after service provision to monitor their progress. The remaining 25% confessed they do not contact their clients after rendering services. They were, however, quick to add that the revelation by this study is a good idea and that it would be added to their packages moving forward. This gesture alone is a form of achievement for this dissertation as it has prompted service delivery improvement by an essential stakeholder in the SME industry.

4.4.2.5 How the progress of clientele is measured

Unravelling the mysteries of SME failures in Ghana requires consistency and the availability of factual data. In line with the above, this study gathers more factual data on SME management to help make the needed recommendation for the holistic development of the SME industry in Ghana and beyond. A question was introduced to probe further how exactly the 75% of SME

Skill Development & Advisory Institutions who responded yes to question seven (7) above measure their clients' progress. Question eight (8) was designed for this purpose, and it read: If yes to question seven (7) above, *how does the organisation measure its clients' progress?* For question eight (8), respondents could choose more than one answer. The following responses were available for the sampled respondents to choose from: *Annual turnover; Size of employees; Size of production; and Number of branches*. After collecting and analysing the data, it was revealed that 60% of the respondents documented that they measure their clients' progress through *Annual turnover and Size of production*. The remaining 40% of the respondents stated that they measure the progress of their customers by looking at their *Annual turnover, Size of employees, Size of production and number of branches*.

4.4.2.6 Annual average percentage improvement of Clientele

After measuring the progress of the SMEs, this study also sorts to measure precisely the percentage of progress made by these SMEs that received some form of technical assistance from the Skill Development and Advisory Institutions. Given the above, question nine (9) was designed purposely to source the required data, and it reads: *What average percentage of clients will the organisation consider having improved yearly? (Interviewer to assist with calculations when necessary)*. The following answers were provided as options for the respondents: *Less than 10%; Between 10% and 20%; Between 20% and 30%; Between 30% and 50%; Between 50% and 100%; and over 100%*. After conducting the data collection and analysis, it was revealed that 75% of the respondents stated that *Between 10% and 20%* of their clients improved after receiving technical assistance from them. The remaining 25% of respondents

also documented *Between 20% and 30%* as their clients' annual percentage range of improvement. The responses gathered from this question is a confirmation of the fact that regular technical training can increase the overall performance of SMEs.

4.4.2.7 The SMEs Skill and Advisory Institutions list of the common challenges faced by SMEs

In a direct response to the first research question, question ten (10) was designed to solicit responses on the challenges faced by the clients of the SME Skill Development & Advisory Institutions, and it reads: *As an advisory Institution, please list five common challenges faced by your clients (SMEs). Kindly list them in order of ranking.* After data collection and analysis, the following order of challenges facing SMEs have been realised by the Skill Development & Advisory Institutes; *Inadequate managerial skills; Inadequate capital; Inability to access credit, Mismanagement of funds and Lack of essential technical skills/Poor record keeping.* This was the aggregate order of responses given by all four respondents except in the last point, where only two documented a *Lack of essential technical skills* whilst the other two went in for *Poor record keeping*. The responses gathered by question ten confirm what most scholarly articles have documented and what was revealed during the pilot studies.

4.4.2.8 Suggested solutions to the above-listed managerial challenges faced by SMEs

After getting the views of the SME Skills Development & Advisory Institutions on what they think are the main challenges facing SMEs, this study thought it necessary to solicit further their responses on what they think are the corresponding solutions to the challenges listed

above in question ten (10). Because of the above, question eleven (11) was given to solicit the required data. It reads: *How can the challenges listed in question ten (10) above be solved as an advisory institution?*

After collecting and analysing the data, the following responses were aggregated from all the sampled respondents: *Easy and accessible training for SME managers; The introduction of a government policy to ease credit accessibility for SMEs; and the introduction of a government policy to absorb risk and to reduce lending rates for SMEs.* These responses are laudable and will be considered during this study's recommendations and conclusion session.

4.4.2.9 Financial management training as a requirement for credit accessibility by SMEs in Ghana.

Financial Management has been a significant nightmare facing SMEs in Ghana. Nkua et al. (2013) documented that small firms' managers do not possess the proper knowledge, so they easily mix their personal and business finances. The act above often affects the financial statements of SMEs and hence, their inability to access credit. To tackle the above-stated challenge, this study introduces a question to sort out the views of the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions, a primary stakeholder in the SME industry. Question twelve (12) was introduced as *Will this advisory institution recommends basic financial management training as a mandatory requirement for accessing credit by SMEs in the country?* The above-stated question only has two possible answers: *Yes or No.* After collecting and analysing the data, all the respondents had a unanimous decision with a 100% *Yes.* The above emphatic endorsement favoured introducing the essential financial management training requirement on SMEs before they can access any credit to ensure they would not mismanage the funds. This

revelation will be a significant milestone towards the success of the SME industry in Ghana and beyond.

4.4.2.10 Recommended training content to the question above

Probing further, the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutions were tasked to state the content they deem fit to feature in the fundamental credit accessibility training they recommended above as an essential requirement for SMEs to access credit. Because of the above, question thirteen (13) was introduced as *If yes to question twelve (12) above, what specific content will you recommend for the training? If no, skip to question fourteen (14)*. After the data collection and analysis, the following suggestions were compiled: *Loan/Capital management; Bookkeeping; Time management; General Management Skills; Customer relations; Enterprise development and sustainability; Business plan development; and Tax Calculations*. The above responses, if well implemented, will go a long way to improve the abilities of SMEs to access credit successfully and manage it as expected.

4.5 DATA ON SME FINANCING IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY

This section brings together all data concerning SMEs' financial constraints in the Wa Municipality of Ghana. The above is necessary for fulfilling the second research objective of *investigating the financial challenges facing SMEs in Ghana and beyond*. This section consists of Section C (questions 16 to 33) of the SMEs Managers Questionnaire and questions (4-16) of the SME Credit Institutions questionnaire. All data analysis and presentation of the SMEs Managers' questions (16-33) will be done first before that of the Credit Institutions (questions 4-16).

Some of the questions from the SME Managers questionnaire are: whether the SMEs do apply for business loans and, if so, where?; the relationship between the SMEs and their creditors; the requirement for loan application; whether an SME has ever been refused a loan and the reasons for the loan refusal; The remaining were about, the amount of money ever borrowed and purpose of the loan acquired; the information requested by the credit institution and whether the SMEs ever had challenges with loan repayment. There were also questions on the causes of the difficulty in loan repayment, how the debtors find the repayment period, the consequences of defaulting in loan repayment, and how SMEs raised their initial capital and sources of continuous funding.

With the SME credit institution's questionnaire, the focus was on: The type of credit facilities available to SMEs; the percentage that SMEs have accessed; the number of years that would qualify a start-up for credit; the requirements for SMEs to access credit; whether the Credit institutions occasionally train their clients (SMEs) on basic financial management techniques and if so, the specific contents for the training. The other questions centred on: whether the credit institutions will welcome any structured training centre for practical business management training; the organisation's loan recovery rates; the common credit default reasons; and what, in their view, will bridge the gap between the financial institution and the SMEs that do not want to access their credit facilities for various reasons.

4.5.1 SMEs Managers questionnaire

4.5.1.1 Loan Application (Credit Accessibility)

Working capital is the main ingredient in setting up a business. Although it has several sources, the most readily available and popular one is a credit facility from a Financial Institution. However, just like any commodity being sold in the market, it comes with a cost and, in this case, some requirements. Surprisingly, the said requirements are sometimes stringent and almost impossible for most SMEs to come to terms with. Hence, it has often been the main

barrier against most smaller businesses in accessing credit facilities. As a means of ascertaining and fetching first-hand information on the above-stated assertion, question sixteen on the SME Managers questionnaire was designed to solicit the required data. It reads: *Has the organisation ever applied for a loan facility?* The above is a direct question; the answers were dichotomous (*Yes or No*). After the data collection and analysis, hundred and forty-seven, representing 54.9% of the sampled SMEs, responded that they had never applied for loans from any Financial Institution. The remaining one hundred and twenty-one (45.1%) of the total sample of two hundred and eighty-six SMEs responded that they did apply for a loan facility from a Financial Institution. The revelation from question sixteen is interesting to this dissertation and will be probed further in the following questions.

4.5.1.2 Reasons why some SMEs do not apply for loans

After the revelations from question sixteen above, there was a motivation to follow up with a question that will further probe to reveal the possible reasons why most SMEs never applied for loans with credit institutions. Given the above, question seventeen was designed to address the above-stated situation, and it reads: *If no to question sixteen above, why not? If yes, skip questioning eighteen.* After reviewing the literature extensively, the following suggestions were provided as the most likely responses for the respondents to choose from: *It would not be considered for a loan facility; Fear of defaulting in repayment due to high interest; It does not have what it takes to get a loan (collateral); and not interested.* After the data collection and analysis, the data presented is as follows: Forty respondents (27.2%) were convinced their businesses *would not be considered for loans* and therefore decided not to apply for any credit facility. An alarming fifty-seven respondents (38.8%) went in for *fear of defaulting in repayment due to high-interest rates*. The third group of SMEs (30 respondents, 20.4%) went in for the response; *It does not have what it takes to get a loan (collateral)*. Collateralisation has been a significant standing block, especially with start-ups, when accessing credit, as

confirmed by the above group of respondents. The last group of SMEs selected *Not Interested* as their response. They were twenty in number, representing 13.6% of the total respondents. A further probe revealed that most of those who stated not interested above were mainly for religious reasons. These are exciting revelations that will be useful in decision-making.

4.5.1.3 SMEs' Sources of acquired credit

Question eighteen (18) is another follow-up to question sixteen (16) above. It is a follow-up on the one hundred and twenty-one (121) respondents who indicated that they did apply for a credit facility with a Financial Institution. The above is a further probe to know which type of Financial Institution the SMEs got their credit from. Question eighteen (18) was presented as *If yes to question sixteen (16) above, where?* The following Credit institutions were identified in the study area:

Table 4-5: Sources of SMEs credit

Source of Credit for SMEs	Number/percentage of SMEs
Bank	59 SMEs (48.8%)
Microfinance Institution	41 SMEs (33.9%)
Government (MASLOC)	5 SMEs (4.1%)
Venture Capital Trust Fund	0
Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	16 SMEs (13.2%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.5 above, fifty-nine (59) SMEs (48.8%) indicated that they got their loans from a bank. A group of forty-one (41) SMEs (33.9%) pointed to Microfinance Institutions as their source of credit. The third group of only five (5) SMEs (4.1%) indicated that they got loans from the Microfinance and Small Loans Centre (MASLOC), the official Government of Ghana's Microfinance Institute, responsible for providing credit facilities to smallholder businesses across the country. Sixteen other SMEs (13.2%) depended on the emerging and fast-growing Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA) for their credit needs.

4.5.1.4 Pre-conditions for credit acquisition

After identifying the various credit institutions, the study found out from the SMEs the various pre-conditions they had to fulfil before having access to their acquired credit facilities; given the above, question nineteen was drafted as *What were the pre-conditions the organisation fulfilled before being granted the loan?* The following were the possible answers provided for the respondents: *Collateral, Equity, Total Assets, Audited Financial Statement and Business Plan*. After data collection and analysis, it appeared that fifty-seven of the respondents representing 47.1% out of the total one hundred and twenty-one, documented that they had to present *collateral* before accessing their desired loan facilities. The next group of forty-nine SMEs representing 40.5%, also documented that they needed to show their *equity* before accessing a credit facility. The third group of only four respondents (3.3%) were asked to present their *total assets* before accessing their desired credit facility. The fourth group of respondents numbered only three, representing 2.5%. They mentioned *audited financial statements (Accounts)* as the pre-conditions they had to meet before being granted a loan. The final group of eight (8) SMEs mentioned *business plans* as evidence of getting credit facilities. This last group makes up 6.6% of the total respondents. The above-presented data are useful first-hand information necessary for SME policy formulation.

4.5.1.5 SMEs Loan Refusal

The dissertation further enquired from the SME managers who applied for loans in question sixteen (16) above whether they were instances their loan requests were ever denied. Question twenty (20) was drafted to solicit data: *Has the organisation ever been refused or denied credit from a bank?* As a direct question, the following options were available for the respondents: *Yes or No*. After data collection and analysis, thirty-eight (38) respondents representing 31.4% out of the one hundred and twenty-one (121) SMEs who applied for loans, admitted that they were ever denied access to a credit facility from a Financial Institution. However, it is

encouraging to note that the remaining eighty-three SMEs representing 68.6% of the respondents, never had their loan applications rejected.

To improve the current credit accessibility situation among SMEs, a question was designed to further inquire from the respondents who had their loans refused in question twenty above on the possible reasons their respective credit institutions relied on to deny them their loan request.

Question twenty-one reads: *If yes to question twenty above, why was the organisation refused the loan from the Financial Institution?* The following were the possible answers that the respondents were to select from *Bad credit history; No collateral security to pledge; No enough deposit or equity base; Lack of proper management practices, and Others (please specify)*.

After completing the data collection and analysis, the following was revealed: two out of the thirty-eight respondents to this question representing 5.3%, documented that they were denied access to credit because of their *bad credit history*. A majority of twenty respondents (52.6%) could not present *any form of collateral or security as a pledge* to the credit institutions that intended to grant them credit. Hence, they were denied access to their intended credit facility. The final group of sixteen SME loan applicants did *not have enough deposit or equity base*. Interestingly, none of the loan applicants was denied on a *lack of proper management practices*.

4.5.1.6 The highest amount of credit an SME ever borrowed

A question was further presented to the eighty-three SMEs who have successfully applied their loan applications in question twenty above. Question twenty-two was meant to extract data on the highest amount of loan money that has ever been approved for SMEs. The question reads:

What was the highest amount the organisation ever borrowed from a Financial Institution?

The following possible answers were presented for them to choose from (The exchange rate was averaged at £1 = GHC8 Sept 2021):

Table 4-6: Highest amount SME ever borrowed

Highest Amount Ever Borrowed	Number/Percentage of SMEs
Less than GHC10,000 (£1,250)	40 SMEs (48.2%)
Between GHC10,000 (£1,250) and GHC20,000 (£2,500)	29 SMEs (34.9%)
Between GHC20,000 (£2,500) and GHC30,000 (£3,750)	7 SMEs (8.4%)
Between GHC30,000 (£3,750) and GHC50,000 (£6,250)	5 SMEs (6.0%)
Above GHC50,000 (£6,250).	2 SMEs (2.4%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.6 above, a chunk of the SMEs (48.2%) stated *less than GHC10,000 (£1,250)* as their highest-ever credit ever accessed. The least among the respondents (2.4%) mentioned *above is GHC50,000 (£6,250) as their highest credit ever borrowed.*

4.5.1.7 The purpose of the above-acquired loan

Question twenty-three (23) was designed to follow question twenty-two (22) above. It seeks to find out from the SMEs what they did with the loans successfully acquired from the Credit institutions. The question reads: *What was the purpose of the loan acquired?* The responses made available to the respondents were: *Start-up Capital; Working Capital; Expansion of business; and Other (Specify).* After the data collection and analysis, the following revelation was made: thirteen of the respondents (15.7%) indicated that the loan they took was used as *start-up capital.* The other group of seventy respondents (84.3%) indicated using their acquired loan to *expand their business.*

4.5.1.8 Challenges in SMEs loan Repayment

Question twenty-four inquired whether the SMEs ever encountered difficulties repaying their loan. The question read: *Has the organisation ever had a problem repaying a loan?* As a direct question, the two possible answers were made available to the respondents: *Yes or No.* After a successful data collection and analysis, it was revealed that thirty-six respondents (43.4%) out of the eighty-three SMEs admitted that they ever had some difficulty repaying their loans. The

remaining forty-seven responses (56.6%) came from SMEs who never encountered any challenges in loan repayment. The data presented above could be handy for decision-makers and policy formulators in the SME industry.

4.5.1.9 Causes of Default in loan repayment by SMEs

The dissertation, at this point, dug deeper to enquire more about the causes of the default in payment of the loan acquired by a section of the SMEs, as indicated in question twenty-four. Because of the above, question twenty-five was designed to solicit the required data, and it reads: *If the response to question twenty-four above is yes, what created the problem?* After comprehensive research, the following were the proposed possible answers for the respondents: *short payment duration; a higher monthly instalment; High-interest rates; Low business turnover; and others (Specify)*. The collected data was analysed and presented as follows:

Table 4-7: causes of loan default among SMEs

Reason for default	Percentage defaulters
short payment duration	16.9%
Higher monthly instalment	19.4%
High-interest rates	47.2%
Low business turnover	16.7%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.7 above, the majority of 47.2% of SMEs defaulted mainly because of the *high-interest rates* charged by the credit institutes. *Low business turnover* was mentioned least (16.7%) among SMEs' reasons for credit default. The rest are shown in the Table above.

Furthermore, the SMEs that acquired loans were quizzed on the required repayment time. To that effect, question twenty-six was presented as: *What was the loan repayment period?* The following realistic responses were available for the respondents: *Up to 1 year; Up to 2 years; Up to 3 years; and Up to 5 years*. After a successful field visit, the analysed data were presented as follows: 21.7% indicated they were given only *UP to 1 year* to repay their loan. 34.9% of the respondents documented that they had *Up to 2 years* as their loan repayment period. Those SMEs *with up to 3 years* to repay their loans made up 36.1%. The SMEs with the lengthiest

repayment period of *Up to 5yrs* were just 7.2% of the sampled respondents. This data is necessary for the subsequent chapters of this study as it will guide the recommendations on the possible ideal period for loan repayments.

4.5.1.10 How SMEs find lending rates

Higher interest rates have been a barrier between most small businesses and credit institutions. Given the above, question twenty-seven (27) was designed to solicit data from the sampled SMEs. The question reads: *How does the organisation generally find lending rates amidst the interest charged?* The following were the available responses for the SMEs to select their answers from:

Table 4-8: How SMEs find lending rates

Lending rates	Percentage SMEs
Low (1% to 5%)	3.4%
Acceptable (6% to 10%)	6.7%
Average (11% to 15%)	8.6%
High (16% to 20%)	13.4%
extremely high (21% and above)	67.9%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.8, only 3.4% of the respondents indicated low lending rates (*1% to 5%*). 6.7% of the sampled SMEs also documented acceptable lending rates (*6% to 10%*). Another group of 8.6% of respondents believed that lending rates are *average (11% to 15%)*. In the fourth group, 13.4% of the sampled SMEs responded with high lending rates (*16% to 20%*). The majority of 67.9% of the sampled respondents revealed that lending rates were *extremely high (21% and above)*. The above data confirms that small businesses are bedevilled with high-lending rates from Credit institutions.

4.5.1.11 Consequences of SMEs Loan Default

The Fear of default in loan payments partly triggered by high-interest rates has been one of the factors blockading SMEs from accessing credit facilities. Also, the above fear could be occasioned due to the high penalties associated with default on a loan payment. Question

twenty-eight (28) was designed to solicit data from the sampled respondents on the consequences of defaulting on a loan payment. *What are the consequences of defaulting on loan payments?* After consulting widely, the following possible answers were produced for the respondents:

Table 4-9: Consequences of loan default

Consequences	Percentage default
Arrest	38.4%
Seizure of valuables	47%
Naming and shaming in the print media	11.2%
Blacklist	3.3%

Source: Filed survey, 2021

From Table 4.9 above, it is interesting to note that 38.4% of the sampled respondents stated *arrest* as the penalty for defaulting on credit payments. 47% documented *seizure of valuables* as the penalty for default in a loan payment. *Naming and shaming in the print media* had 11.2% of the sampled respondents rooting for it. The final 3.3% of the respondents documented *blacklist* as the possible penalty for defaulting on a loan payment, as illustrated in Table 4.3 below:

Figure 4-3: What happens if an SME defaults on loan repayment

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Figure 4.3 above graphically illustrates the consequences of loan defaults by the clients of the credit institutions in the Wa Municipality of Ghana. The most mentioned penalty is the seizure of valuables, whilst the least, according to the sampled SMEs, is a blacklist.

4.5.1.12 How the SMEs initial capital was raised

Question twenty-nine (29) was meant to investigate the SME operators and how they raised their initial capital to start their businesses. The question was: *How was the initial capital raised for the organisation?* The following answers were listed for the respondents: *personal savings; Bank credit; Friends and relatives; Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA), and Farming.* After completing the data collection and analysis, the majority of 64.9% of the total respondents documented that their initial capital was raised from *personal savings*. Interestingly, only 9.7% of the sampled SMEs said they accessed *bank credit* to start their businesses. A group comprising 22.8% of the sample declared they had their initial capital from *friends and relatives*. The newly emerging *Village Savings and Loans Association* helped raise start-up capital for 2.2% of the sampled SMEs. Finally, only 0.4% of SMEs raised their initial capital through their farm produce (*farming*) sales, as presented in Figure 4.4 below:

Figure 4-4: How the SMEs raised their start-up capital

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4.4 above is a graphical representation of how the sampled SMEs raised their start-up capital. Most of them started their businesses from personal savings, whilst the least resulted in farming to raise their initial capital.

4.5.1.13 Sources of continues funding of SMEs

Question thirty (30) was put forward as a follow-up to question twenty-nine (29) above on how SMEs sustain the financial needs of their businesses after the initial capital investment. The question was presented as follows: *What are the continued funding sources for the business?* The following were the possible answers for the respondents to make their choices from *Bank loans; Personal savings; Retained profit; Venture capital; Trade credit; Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA); Private Donors (NGOs); Family and friends, and Others (Specify)*. After data collection and analysis, it was revealed that: 5.5% of the SMEs continuously fund their businesses through bank loans. Also, 25.4% of the respondents mentioned that they result to their *savings* to fund their businesses continuously. Impressively, the majority of 61.6% mentioned *retained profit* as a continuous funding source for their businesses. However, 0.7% of the sampled SMEs seek support from venture capitalists to fund their businesses continuously. Again, 2.2% of the sampled respondents depend on their *Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA)* to continuously finance their businesses. Only 0.4% of the SMEs sampled get their source of continuous funding from a *donor (NGO)*, whilst the final 4.0% rely on *family and friends* to continuously sustain their business. Surprisingly, no one mentioned trade credit as their source of continuous funding.

4.5.1.14 Constraints to the Growth of SMEs

As a direct address to the first two objectives of this thesis, question thirty-one (31) was designed to reveal the constraints that hamper the development of SMEs. The question reads: *What are the significant constraints to the growth of the business?* The following possible answers were designed along with the question for the respondents to choose—*lack of finance;*

Competition; High-interest rates; High government taxes; and Inadequate managerial skills.

After conducting a successful data collection exercise, the data was analysed and presented: 16% of the SMEs *believed that lack of finance* had been their major constraint to growth. A group of 24.3% of the sampled respondents opined that *competition* had been their major hindrance to development. Expectedly, *higher interest rates* on bank loans topped the list of constraints, with 26.1% of the total respondents rooting for it.

Meanwhile, *higher government taxes* were stated as a significant setback by 16.4% of the sampled SMEs. Another much-anticipated constraint, *inadequate managerial skills*, got 12.7% of the sampled respondents. Finally, the *lack of required technology* was the primary constraint of 4.5% of the SMEs sampled for this survey, as shown below:

Figure 4-5: Constraints to SME growth.

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Figure 4.5 above is a graphical representation of the significant constraints hindering the growth of SMEs. It appears that *the SMEs have stated high-interest rates on bank loans* as the major setback to their development. The least mentioned constraint was the *lack of the required technology*.

4.5.2 SME Financing Institutions

4.5.2.1 The availability of a unique credit facility for SMEs

Question four (4) on the SME financing institution questionnaire was meant to sort information from the credit institutions on whether they have a designated financial product for SMEs. The question was presented to them: *Does the organisation have a unique facility for SMEs?* As a direct question, the possible answers were: *Yes or No*. After successfully collecting and analysing the data, the following revelations were made: encouragingly, there was an overwhelming 100% 'yes' as an answer. The above indicates that all the sampled credit institutions have special credit facilities for SMEs. This revelation is a step in the good direction as it makes it easier to focus on how to build SMEs' capacities to access those credit facilities whenever necessary.

4.5.2.2 Types of credit facilities available to SMEs

As a follow-up to question four (4) above, the study sort to dig deeper to reveal the specific type of facilities the Credit institutions have in place for their clients. Question five (5) reads; *if yes to question four (4) above, state the facility's name*. After the data collection and analysis, the most common product mentioned was *credit with education (CWE) and Susu loans (44.4%)*. The second most mentioned product among the sampled credit institutions was *SME loans and SSF loans/overdrafts (22.2%)*. The following responses all managed 11.1% each of the total responses: *high vehicle purchase for drivers; Market women savings and loans; and Village savings and loans plus susu*. The above revelations serve as a piece of first-hand information for stakeholders in the SME industry.

4.5.2.3 Percentage of credit accessed by SMEs

The dissertation further enquired about the percentage of the above-listed credit facilities accessed successfully by SMEs. Because of the above, question six (6) was designed to solicit the required data, and it reads: *What percentage of the organisation's credit facility has been*

accessed by SMEs? The following were the answers provided for the SMEs to select the choices.

Table 4-10: Percentage of credit SMEs accessed from credit institutions

Percentage credit accessed by SMEs	Number of credit institutes
Less than 50%	1
Between 51% and 60%	2
Between 61% and 70%	3
Between 71% and 80%	2
Between 81% and 90%	0
Between 91% and 100%	1

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.10 above, three (3) of the sampled nine (9) Credit institutions indicated that *61% and 70%* of the money reserved as an SME credit facility had been successfully accessed. Two (2) of the Credit institutions also documented that their SME credit facilities have been accessed *between 71% and 80%*. Two (2) respondents had their SME facilities accessed *between 51% and 60%*. The Financial Institution with the highest accessed SME credit facility was *between 91% and 100%*. Lastly, other credit institutions had their credit facility accessed for *Less than 50%*.

4.5.2.4 Can SME start-ups access the credit facility?

As a follow-up to question six (6) above, question seven (7) read: *Do you grant credit to start-ups/fresh business ideas?* The answers available were *Yes or No*. After a successful data collection and analysis, it was revealed that only three (3) out of the sampled nine (9) Credit institutions chose 'yes' as an answer. The remaining 66.7% of the respondents stated that they do not grant loans to start-ups which is a worrying revelation that needs to be addressed. A further probe was made through question eight (8): *If no to question seven (7) above, how many years would an SME have to be in business in order to qualify for a loan facility?* Interestingly, all six (6) respondents that responded to the above question stated *Between 1yr and 5yrs* as their response.

4.5.2.5 Requirements for Obtaining a credit facility by SMEs

Stringent requirements often accompany loan applications. Given the above, question nine (9) was presented to the respondents: *What are the requirements for SMEs to obtain credit from your institution?* After a successful data collection and analysis, Table 4.11 below the illustration of the responses gathered from the field:

Table 4-11: Credit accessibility requirements

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Valid ID, passport photo, GPS address, TIN, and group guarantees.	1	11.1
Turnover and Collateral	3	33.3
Group of 3 to 5; Four weekly meetings; 20% deposit; one-day financial management training.	1	11.1
Must operate the bank for at least six months	1	11.1
At least six months account; Cash collateral; Stock insurance; Joint and liability	1	11.1
Six months acc; Registered business with cooperative, MMDA and registerer general; Good cash flow; Good security	1	11.1
Good records keeping; Good cash flows; Demonstrable potential for growth; Minimal collateral	1	11.1
Total	9	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4.11 above reveals the requirements that SME managers have to show before accessing credit for their businesses. The most common requirement is *Turnover and Collateral*, which was mentioned by 33.3% of the respondents. Among others mentioned are good cash flow, good record keeping, at least 6 months active account, valid ID, and evidence of business registration.

4.5.2.6 Background Checks on basic skills before granting loans

As a commitment to ensuring that credit institutions grant loans to qualified debtors, question ten (10) was presented: *does this Financial Institution make a background check to ensure managers of SMEs have basic financial management skills before granting them credit?*

Respondents were to choose either a *Yes or No* as their answer. After the field survey and data analysis, 55.6% of the Credit institutions documented 'yes' as an answer. The above means five (5) out of the nine (9) sampled respondents make a little background check on the financial management capabilities of their clients before approving their loan requests. On the other hand, the remaining 44.4% of respondents stated that they do not conduct preliminary checks on their customers' financial management abilities before loan approvals.

Furthermore, after approving the loan request of their clients, this dissertation wanted to know whether the credit institutions have measures in place that continuously build the capacities of their clients to manage their loan portfolios better and, for that matter, their businesses. Question eleven (11) was presented as follows: *does this Financial Institution occasionally provide basic financial management training to your clients (SMEs) to increase their chances of surviving their businesses to pay back their loans?* The respondents had a simple task of responding either *Yes or No*. After the field visits and data analysis, it was revealed that 55.6% of the respondents stated 'yes' as their answer, whilst the remaining 44.4% of the sampled respondents mentioned 'no' as their response. This implies that five (5) of the total sampled credit institutions continuously train their clients to build their capacities, whilst four (4) of the sampled creditors do not carry out such capacity training exercises for their customers.

Moreover, in a quest to dig deeper into the training the five (5) credit institutions above give to their clients continuously, question twelve (12) was presented as *If yes to question eleven (11) above, what are some of the specific contents your outfit takes them (SMEs) through during the training?* As an open question, the following responses in Table 4.12 were gathered after the field visits:

Table 4-12: Occasional basic financial management training for SMEs

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Bookkeeping	1	11.1
Time management; Bookkeeping; loan mgt and repayment	1	11.1
Bookkeeping; dynamics of markets; risk components of various markets	1	11.1
Bookkeeping; customer care; saving regularly; regular loan payments	1	11.1
Bookkeeping; customer care; saving regularly; regular loan payments	1	11.1
Bookkeeping; cost containment; product pricing; revenue maximisation	1	11.1
Total	5	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.12 above, the most common training that Credit institutions continuously give their clients is bookkeeping, as stated by all five (5) respondents above. Some modules also mentioned are customer care, revenue maximisation, market dynamics, and staying liquid (regular savings).

Finally, as a measure to ensure the holistic growth of all SMEs without any language barrier, question thirteen (13) was presented to the credit institutions as *If no in question eleven (11) above, will the organisation welcome a well-structured SME management training centre in the region that is accessible by all, for practical business management training/mentoring purposes with the capacity to train in the local dialect?* The credit institutions were to either respond *Yes or No*. Interestingly, after visiting the field and analysing the data, all the respondents supported the idea by responding with 'yes' as their answer.

4.5.2.7 Annual SME loan recovery rates by the Credit Institutions

Default in paying loans has been a significant nightmare for most SMEs in developing countries like Ghana. A study of this nature would not be complete without finding out directly from the credit institutions about their loan recovery rates. Given the above, question fourteen (14) on the SME Financing Institutions Questionnaire read: *What is the organisation's annual loan recovery rate from SMEs?* The data collection and analysis were conducted successfully

and presented as follows: 33.3% of the sampled nine (9) credit institutions stated that their annual loan recovery rates from SMEs range *between 71% and 80%*. The second group of 33.3% respondents also documented their annual loan recovery rate *between 81% and 90%*. Also, those credit institutions that recovered *between 61% and 70%* of their SME loans were 22.2% of the sample population.

Interestingly, 11.1% of the Credit institutions reported claiming back *between 91% and 100%* of their SME loans. Generally, the loan recovery rates are impressive and possibly attributed to the stringent screening measures some credit institutions put before granting loans. It is also worth mentioning that the penalties for loan default are deterrent enough to prevent any loan default from SMEs. The multi-million question, however, remains whether SMEs get the value for the loans they take. This thesis will address this question in subsequent chapters.

Despite the impressive loan recovery rates, the study further quizzed the credit institutions on the common reasons for defaulting loans for the few recorded cases. Question fifteen (15) was presented as follows: *what are the common reasons for loan default among SMEs?* As an open question, the following responses were gathered after visiting the field. See Table 4.13 Below:

Table 4-13: Common reasons for SME loan default

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Funds not released on time; National disaster, e.g., COVID-19; Clients expected amount not parted in full	1	11.1
Poor financial management	3	33.3
Inadequate capital and client spending in the capital	1	11.1
Poor financial management and the use of loan funds in solving personal problems	1	11.1
Funds diversion	1	11.1
Multiple loans and bad sales	1	11.1
Too many diversions and frivolous expenditure	1	11.1
Total	9	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4.13 illustrates the common reasons for loan default according to the sampled credit institutions. The most common reason stated was *Poor Financial Management*, as was mentioned by 33.3% of the Credit institutions. As stated in the Table above, some other reasons were: Funds diversion, Multiple loans, bad sales, using business loans to solve personal problems and many more.

4.5.2.8 Bridging the Gap between Credit Institutions and SMEs

Finally, in this session, the study finds out the views of the sampled credit institutions on bridging the gap between the credit institutions and the SMEs. Question sixteen (16) was presented as follows: *As a Financial Institution, what can be done to bridge the gap between credit institutions and most of the SMEs who, for some reason, do not want to access your credit facilities?* It was an open question, and the respondents independently documented the following responses in Table 4.14 below:

Table 4-14: Bridging the gap between credit institutions and SMEs

Responses	Frequency	Percentages
Releasing credit funds on time since some businesses are seasonal and have lower loan requirement	1	11.1
Building the capacities of SMEs to manage loans and reduce interest rates	1	11.1
Bank of Ghana reducing policy rates so that local banks can also reduce interest rates.	5	55.6
Training SMEs on loan mgt and developing SME policy to guide their operations	1	11.1
Improving service deliveries to SMEs in other to facilitate their transactions	1	11.1
Total	9	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4.14 above contains the responses from question sixteen (16) above. A majority of 55.6% of the credit institutions mentioned that if the *Bank of Ghana could reduce policy rates so that local banks can also reduce interest rates*, it would help bridge the gap between some SMEs and credit institutions. Some of the suggestions also mentioned are: *Releasing credit funds on*

time since some businesses are seasonal and lowering loan requirements; Building the capacities of SMEs to manage loans and reduce interest rates; Training SMEs on loan management and developing SME policy to guide their operations; and Improving service deliveries to SMEs in order to facilitate their transactions.

4.6 THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON BUSINESSES

Since the eruption of the Covid-19 virus in January 2020, the SME industry across the globe has been severely affected. All forms of stimulus have been offered to support the resurgence of the SME industry globally (Lu et al., 2020). Nonetheless, most SMEs, especially those undocumented, either received little or no support and therefore have to face the full effect of the pandemic. Because of the above, most SMEs' survival and continuous operation are in a dilemma. This section of the questionnaires has been designed to directly get first-hand data on how the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus has impacted SMEs. As a global endemic, these questions cut across all three sets of the questionnaires for this study, as stated at the beginning of this chapter. Hence, the analysed data will be presented as, analysed data on SME Managers; analysed data on SME Credit institutions, and analysed data on SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes.

How has Covid-19 impacted your business? It is one of the few questions every respondent for this study had to respond to. The following possible responses were available for the respondents: *Negatively, Positively, and No Impact*. After a successful data collection and analysis:

For the SME Managers, expectedly, a mammoth 85.8% of the respondents lamented about their businesses being *negatively* affected by the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus. In contrast, only 0.7% of the sampled SMEs (2 out of 268) documented that the outbreak of Covid-19 *Positively* impacted their businesses. A check revealed that these two (2) SMEs were in the healthcare

industry, hence their fortunes. Nonetheless, another 13.4% of respondents stated that the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus had *No Impact* on businesses. As a follow-up, the following question was asked: *how do you see your business after Covid-19? Fully operating, Partially operating, Closed down; No impact* was presented to the respondents to make their desired choices. After the field visits and data analysis, an optimistic 44.4% of the responses suggested that the businesses they represent will *fully operate* even after the Covid-19 pandemic. The second group of 33.2% respondents stated that their businesses would *partly operate* after Covid-19. It was, however, worrying to note that 4.9% (13 out of the 268 SMEs) did mention that their businesses would *close down* as a result of the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus. In addition to the above, some other 17.5% of respondents who were mainly traumatised by the pandemic *could not predict* the future of their businesses. From the above data, it is apparent that a significant number of jobs could be lost, resulting in more pressure on the economy due to the outbreak of the Covid-19 virus.

The same question was presented to the SME Credit institutions, and the following revelations were documented after collecting and analysing the data: All nine (9) sampled Credit institutions bemoaned that the irruption of the Covid-19 virus has *Negatively* affected their businesses. The 100% negative impact recorded for the SME financing industry does not come as a surprise, considering the history of global pandemics of this nature (Abubakar, 2019).

As a further probe, the Credit institutions were asked *how do you see their business after Covid-19?* after the field visit and data analysis, a majority, 88.9%, of the respondents were optimistic about their businesses *fully operating* after the Covid-19 pandemic. Only 11.1% were unsure and therefore stated *partly operating* as an answer to the above question. None of the Credit institutions went in for *closed down* or *could not predict* answers to the question above. With the long-standing tradition of government bailouts (Quantitative Easing) after major pandemics (Abubakar, 2019), the responses from the credit institutions were as expected.

Lastly, the SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institutions were confronted with *how Covid-19 impacted your business*. Out of the three available responses, all the sampled respondents (100%) complained that their businesses would be affected *negatively* after the Covid-19 pandemic. The above is expected as these institutions solely depend on the SMEs as their clients and will therefore feel the trickledown effect as most SMEs are affected negatively by the outburst of Covid-19. On the follow-up question of *how do you see your business after Covid-19?* Despite being affected negatively, all (100%) of the sampled respondents were confident that their businesses would *fully operate* after the Covid-19 pandemic.

The above data will be handy to policymakers and the subsequent chapters of this study.

4.7 SME POLICY RECOMMENDATION DATA IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY

This study's third specific research question is: *What guidelines can enhance the effectiveness of managing and financing SMEs in Ghana?* In finding responses to the above question, a question on SME recommendation was drafted and presented to all the respondents to solicit their views on the above subject matter. Again, the presentation of the outcome of the data collection and analysis will be as follows: analysed data on SME Managers, analysed data on SME credit institutions, and analysed data on SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes.

The SME Managers' question was presented to them: *as a management member, what policy recommendations will the organisation want to see that will ensure a better environment for SMEs?* After visiting the field, the following responses were gathered, analysed and presented in Table 4.15 below.

Table 4-15: SME Managers' policy recommendations

	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Government intervention to make credit accessibility easier for SMEs	57	21.3%
2	Provide a platform for SMEs to build their capacity and network.	10	3.7%
3	SME management training should be made cheap and accessible to all	56	20.9%
4	Taxes on all goods should be reduced.	48	17.9%
5	There must be SME legislation that protects SMEs from bankruptcy and can bail out SMEs	3	1.1%
6	Provide loans for small-scale businesses with low interest	17	6.3%
7	Reduction of interest rate on bank loans for easy accessibility.	68	25.4%
8	Regulating the high cost of properties for business rentals	5	1.9%
9	Availability of technology to help in the growth of their business.	4	1.5%
	Total	268	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.15 above, the most commonly mentioned recommendation by SME managers is the *reduction of interest rates on bank loans for easy accessibility*. It was mentioned by 68 (25.4%) out of the sampled 268 respondents. Among some of the most recommended were: *Government intervention to make credit accessibility easier for SMEs* (21.3%); *SME management training should be made cheap and accessible to all* (20.9%); *Taxes on all goods should be reduced* (17.9%) among others. The least among the list of recommendations is *that SME legislation must protect SMEs from bankruptcy and can bail out SMEs* (1.1%).

Also, the same question was presented to the SME Financing Institutions: *as a financial institution, what policy recommendations will you want to see to ensure a better environment for SME growth in Ghana?* The results of the data analysed are shown in Table 4.16 below:

Table 4-16: SME Financing Institutions policy recommendations

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
There should be only 1% interest on SME credit to attract more interested people into entrepreneurship	2	22.2
Bank of Ghana policy rates should be reduced to 10%	1	11.1
NBSSI must step up SME support programs for the grassroots and reduce interest rates	2	22.2
A national SME policy to guide the operations of SMEs	2	22.2
Favourable credit policies; savings/deposit policies; sensitisation policies	1	11.1
All SMEs should identify their unique proposition (niche) and concentrate on the same. They should avoid overtrading	1	11.1
Total	9	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4.16 above illustrates the policy recommendations stated by the representatives of the SME Financing Institutions in the Wa Municipality of the Upper West Region of Ghana. The most widely suggested recommendations by the credit institutions were: *there should be only 1% interest on SME credit to attract more interested people into entrepreneurship (22.2%); National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI, now GEA) must step up SME support programs for the grassroots; and a national SME policy to guide the operations of SMEs (22.2%)*. Some other recommendations were: *Bank of Ghana policy rates should be reduced to 10% (11.1%)*, and *All SMEs should identify their unique proposition (niche) and concentrate on the same. They should avoid over-trading (11.1%)*.

Finally, the same question was presented to the SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institutions. *As an advisory institution, what policy recommendations will you want to see in place that will ensure a better environment for SME growth in Ghana?* Data collection was carried out, analysed and presented in Table 4.8 below:

Table 4-17: SME Advisory Institutions Policy Recommendations

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Government should aid SMEs in gaining the needed skills	3	75.0%
Government should intervene to reduce interest rates and make credit accessible to all SMEs	1	25.0%
Total	4	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 4.17 above, three (3) out of the four (4) sampled respondents recommended that *government should aid SMEs to gain the needed skills (75%)*. The remaining 25% of the respondent also suggested that *government should intervene to reduce interest rates and make credit accessible to all SMEs*.

In conclusion, the questionnaires employed by this study have succeeded in revealing some excellent recommendations above that will be helpful to the stakeholders in the SME industry.

CHAPTER FIVE: TECHNICAL ANALYSIS: CROSSTABULATION AND TESTING FOR CORRELATION, REGRESSION AND CAUSALITY

Berman, Brown and Saunders (2008) defined significance testing as examining the probability of a hypothesis or a pattern, like a relationship happening by chance between entities. To gain a deeper understanding of how SMEs are challenged with Management and Credit accessibility issues, a careful selection of some questions from this survey has been made and cross-tabulated. Furthermore, the study also tested Pearson's chi-square values and correlation coefficients between the cross-tabulated questions to help identify relationships and the level of correlations between the selected variables. Moreover, regression and causality were also computed in selected cases to further establish the ties between the chosen variables. The results revealed multiple pieces of information on the causes and effects of decisions some SME managers have made concerning their businesses.

In alignment with the previous chapter four, the results of the crosstabulations, correlation tests, regression and causality analysis will be presented in the following order. Analysis from the SME Managers questionnaires, the SME Financial Institutions questionnaire, and the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes questionnaires.

5.1 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FROM THE SME MANAGERS QUESTIONNAIRE

5.2 Crosstabulations

The selection and pairing of questions were chosen carefully, as shown in Table 5.1 below: Kindly refer to the appendix for the questionnaire.

Table 5-1: Selected questions for crosstabulation

No.	Paired questions	Reason for the crosstabulation
1	Q3 and Q5	To measure whether the level of education of the management team affects the years an SME can be in business (survived)
2	Q4 and Q5	To ascertain a possible link between the legal status of an SME and the number of years, it has been in operation (survived)
3	Q5 and Q6	To measure SME classification against the number of years, it has been operating
4	Q6 and Q7	To reveal which classification of SME has the required number of competent staff
5	Q9 and Q11	To measure SME managers capacity building training against the development of a business proposal
6	Q9 and Q12	To measure the impact of acquired training on proper bookkeeping by SME managers
7	Q12 and Q13	To measure the influence bookkeeping has on an SME's quarterly return
8	Q9 and Q13	To ascertain whether comprehensive SME managers' training has an impact on their quarterly returns
9	Q8 and Q13	To measure the impact of the educational level of the SME management teams on the returns of the business
10	Q14 and Q15	To ascertain the need for SME managers' capacity-building training versus their willingness to commit a token of their resources to the training.
11	Q5 and Q16	How loan acquisition has possibly affected the number of years SMEs have been in operation
12	Q13 and Q16	To measure the impact of acquired loans on the profit margin of SMEs
13	Q12 and Q20	To measure whether proper bookkeeping has a link with SME loan refusal
14	Q1 and Q22	To find out the gender of the SME managers/owners against the amount of credit they ever secured. This is to help get first-hand information on the level of risk male and female SME managers take and further find out between male and female SMEs which ones are doing well by the level of risk they take.
16	Q16 and Q27	Lending rate perception versus SMEs' interest in applying for credit
17	Q27 and Q29	The link between interest rates versus SMEs raising of initial business capital
18	Q29 and Q30	The correlation between SME initial capital versus their sources of continuous funding
19	Q32 and Q33	To measure the impact of Covid-19 on SME operations versus how SMEs could be seen after Covid-19.

Source: Author's creation, 2021

5.2.1 Definition of terms

5.2.1.1 Pearson's Chi-squared Test

In this context, the chi-square test determines the likelihood of independence of the selected variables from each other. Where their autonomy cannot be ascertained, it would be concluded that they depend on each other and hence, share some relationship. Figure 5.1 below shows the chi-square analysis outcome using IBM SPSS 25.

Figure 5-1: A sample chi-square test result

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.718 ^a	1	.010		
Continuity Correction ^b	4.951	1	.026		
Likelihood Ratio	7.032	1	.008		
Fisher's Exact Test				.014	.012
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.494	1	.011		
N of Valid Cases	30				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.53.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Source: EZ SPSS Tutorials, 2021

With the help of IBM SPSS 25, the automated p-value is compared to a standard alpha value. The chi-square statistic is the circled number (6.718) under 'Values' in the above Table, whilst the p-value is the circled figure (0.010) under "Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)". The P-value is to be compared to a standard alpha value of 0.50. Decisions are generally made on the following hypothesis:

Ho: The variables are independent of each other.

H₁: The variables are not independent of each other.

If the p-value is less than or equal to the alpha value of 0.50, we reject the null hypothesis and vice versa. In other words, where the p-value is rejected, we conclude that there is some relationship between the variables, as the data above suggests.

5.2.1.2 Pearson's Correlation Test

As Pearson's chi-square helps establish the relationship between variables, Pearson's correlation test makes it better as it reveals the level of correlation between the understudied variables.

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) linearly measures the strength of the association between two variables. Graphically, Pearson's correlation is represented by a line of best fit between entities' data, as shown in Figure 5.2 below.

Figure 5-2: Graphical representation of Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Source: Laerd Statistics, 2021

The data spread around the best-fit line describes the association level between the variables under consideration. Generally, the Pearson correlation coefficient, r , ranges between +1 to -1. The closer the value of the correlation coefficient r to 0, the wider the data away from the line of best fit and the closer r is to 1 or -1, the better the line of best fit, as shown in Figure 5.2 above.

Nonetheless, the following guidelines provided by Table 5.2 could be used to determine the strength of correlations between two variables without plotting a scatter diagram.

Table 5-2: A guide on the strength of correlation

Strength of Association	Coefficient, r	
	Positive	Negative
Small/Slight	0.1 to 0.3	-0.1 to -0.3
Medium	0.3 to 0.5	-0.3 to -0.5
Large	0.5 to 1.0	-0.5 to -1.0

Source: Laerd Statistics, 2021

Table 5.2 above will serve as a guide to the interpretation of Pearson's Correlation coefficients subsequently.

5.2.2 The impact of education on SMEs lifespan

According to King and McGrath (2002), proper education is essential in SME development. With the appropriate education, the staff of SMEs are equipped with the relevant professional skills required to adapt to emerging challenges from the business climate and identify and seize the right opportunities they need to develop. Given the above, questions 3 and 5 have been cross-tabulated to determine whether the highest level of education of an SME owner/manager impacts the lifespan of the businesses they operate. Table 5.3 below contains the automated results of the IBM SPSS 25 analysis.

Table 5-3: The crosstabulation of the educational level of the SMEs management team versus the length of time they have been operating.

For how long has the firm been in business? * Indicate the highest level of education obtained		Indicate the highest level of education obtained					Total
		No formal education	Primary education	Junior High school	Secondary/Technical/Vocational	Tertiary	
For how long has the firm been in business?	Less than one year	1 (6.7%)	1 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (46.7%)	6 (40.0%)	15
	Between two and five years	13 (13.4%)	11 (11.3%)	10 (10.3%)	32 (33%)	31 (32%)	97
	Between six and ten years	10 (10.4%)	9 (9.3%)	13 (13.5%)	36 (37.5%)	28 (29.2%)	96
	Between eleven and fifteen years	4 (10.3%)	7 (17.9%)	5 (12.8%)	20 (51.3%)	3 (7.7%)	39
	Over fifteen years	9 (42.9%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.8%)	6 (28.6%)	5 (23.8%)	21
	Total		37	28	29	101	73

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.3 above, the row for businesses operating for *less than one year* is dominated by SMEs led by owner/managers with Secondary/Technical/Vocational (46.7%) certificates and above. The same trend is shown in the row for the SMEs operating *between two and five years*. The majority of 33% of the SMEs have their owner/manager completed secondary/Technical/Vocational education and beyond. Additionally, the most dominant ones for the businesses operating *between eleven and fifteen years* remain those with Secondary/Vocational/vocational owner/manager (51.3%). Interestingly, in the case of the businesses operating over 15yrs, the trend of dominance swung to the SMEs with

owners/managers who have *no formal education* (42.9%), whilst the SMEs with Secondary/Technical/Vocational and tertiary recorded (28.6%) and (23.8%) respectively. This is a unique case of natural entrepreneurs who would likely perform well when supported with the needed technical educational support.

The above analysis has revealed that except in a few cases; most SMEs turn to the last longer when their owner/managers have some appreciable level of education.

Table 5.4 below is the chi-square and correlation test result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-4: Chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.3

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	33.044 ^a	16	.007
Pearson's R	-.156		
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.525	1	.011
N of Valid Cases	268		

a. 9 cells (36.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 1.57.

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The number of years an SME has been in operation is independent of the level of education of the SME's owner/manager

H1: The number of years an SME has been in operation is not independent of the level of education of the SME owner/manager.

From Table 5.4 above, the p-value of 0.007 is less than the standard alpha value of 0.50, so we reject the null hypothesis. This implies a relationship between the number of years an SME has been in operation and the level of education of the SME's owner/manager.

Also, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is -0.156, very close to 0 and suggests a small correlation as the data are widely spread around the line of best fit. Referring to Table 5.2 above, we conclude that there is a slight correlation between the educational level of an SME owner/manager and the number of years the SME has been in operation.

5.2.3 How SMEs 'type' affects their Lifespan

SME life expectancy has been an issue of concern to the stakeholders. There is no known research on the SME type that is likely to last longer or collapse earlier. This study makes a pioneering attempt to investigate the possible relationship between SME types and their potential lifespan. Table 5.5 below is the cross-tabulated data of questions 4 and 5 to determine whether SME type affects the number of years it has been in business.

Table 5-5: crosstabulations of a firm (SME) type and the number of years it's been in operation

		For how long has the firm been in business?					Total
		Less than one year	Between two and five years	Between six and ten years	Between eleven and fifteen years	Over fifteen years	
Type of firm	Sole Proprietor	14 (5.9%)	90 (37.7%)	83 (34.7%)	33 (13.8%)	19 (7.9%)	239
	Partnership	0 (0.0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	6
	Family-Owned Business	1 (5.6%)	3 (16.7%)	9 (50.0%)	4 (22.2%)	1 (5.6%)	18
	Private Limited Company	0 (0.0%)	2 (40.0%)	2 (40.0%)	1 (20.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5
Total		15	97	96	39	21	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

The data from Table 5.5 above reveals a regular trend of events between the type of firm and the number of years they have been in operation. The peak for all the types of firms is within the middle columns; *between two and five years and between six and ten years*, from 37.7% and 34.7%, respectively, on the sole proprietor row through to 40.0% and 40.0%, respectively on the private limited company's row. Meanwhile, data from the lateral columns (*Less than one year, between eleven and fifteen years, and over fifteen years*) reveal a flattened pattern. From

the above analysis, none of the firm types follows either an ascending or descending order with their number of years of operation. Table 5.6 below is the chi-square and correlation test result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-6: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.5

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.892 ^a	12	.921
Pearson's R	.056		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.847	1	.357
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 13 cells (65.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .28.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: How long a firm has been in operation is independent of its firm type.

H1: How long a firm has been in operation is not independent of its firm type.

From Table 5.6 above, the p-value of 0.921 exceeds the expected alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that there is no relationship between firm type and its years in operation.

Additionally, Pearson's correlation coefficient $r = 0.056$ is insignificant and out of range for the classifications of the levels of correlation (refer to Table 5.2). The above confirms no correlation between firm type and the years it has been in operation.

5.2.4 The impact of SME classifications on their lifespan

Similar to 5.3 above, this dissertation makes another pioneering attempt to determine how the number of years an SME has been in operation is likely affected by its classification. Because

of the above, questions 5 and 6 on the SME managers questionnaire have been cross-tabulated, and the result is shown in Table 5.7 below:

Table 5-7: Firm (SME) classification and the number of years it's been in operation

		For how long has the firm been in business?					Total
		Less than one year	Between two and five years	Between six and ten years	Between eleven and fifteen years	Over fifteen years	
How will one classify the organisation?	Micro (Between 1 and 5 employees)	15 (6.8%)	88 (39.8%)	78 (35.3%)	23 (10.4%)	17 (7.7%)	221
	Small (Between 6 and 30 employees)	0 (0.0%)	9 (20.5%)	15 (34.1%)	16 (36.4%)	4 (9.1%)	44
	Medium (Between 31 and 100 employees)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3
Total		15	97	96	39	21	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.7, The Micro (between 1 and 5 employees) SMEs surveyed have a majority (39.8%) of them *between their second and fifth years* of operating before their consistent decline in the years after, as displayed above. Contrarily, the SMEs in the small (between 6 and 30 employees) category grew steadily over the years until they had a majority (36.4%) of them operating *between their eleventh and fifteenth years*. The final classification of SMEs surveyed

was the medium (between 31 and 100 employees) SMEs, and they have all been operating *between their sixth and tenth years.*

From the above analysis, the highly classified SMEs (Small and Medium) primarily operate beyond 5yrs and up to 15yrs. However, the Micro SMEs have their majority living a maximum of 5yrs. Therefore, Small and Medium Enterprises are likely to operate for longer years than their Micro counterparts.

Table 5.8 below is the chi-square and correlation test result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-8: Chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.7 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.353 ^a	8	.000
Pearson's R	.209		
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.692	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 7 cells (46.7%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .17.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The number of years an SME has been in business is independent of the classification of the SME

H1: The number of years an SME has been in business is not independent of the classification of the SME

The Pearson chi-square in Table 5.8 above reveals a p-value of 0.000, which is lower than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Given the above, we reject the null hypothesis. The above implies a relationship between the number of years an SME has been in business and the classification of the SME.

More so, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is 0.209 and falls within the range of a slight correlation, as stated in Table 5.2 above. Therefore, we conclude that there is a small correlation between SME classification and the number of years it has been in business.

5.2.5 The effects of SMEs classification on their staff Strength

A firm's performance is mainly associated with its human resource (Ndiaye, 2018). Questions 6 and 7 have been cross-tabulated to reveal the various classification of SMEs and whether they have the required number of staff or not. Experienced and skilled employees and managers are the priorities of every well-performing firm (Olafsen and Cook, 2018).

Table 5-9: SME classification with their required number of staff

How will one classify the organisation? * Are there the required number of staff for the organisation? Cross tabulation					
		Is there a required number of staff for the organisation?			Total
		Yes, there are qualified staff for all the roles.	Yes, there are staff for all the roles, but they are not qualified	No, one person performs multiple functions because there is not enough staff	
How will one classify the organisation?	Micro (Between 1 and 5 employees)	53 (24.0%)	36 (16.3%)	132 (59.7%)	221
	Small (Between 6 and 30 employees)	15 (34.1%)	26 (59.0%)	3 (6.8%)	44
	Medium (Between 31 and 100 employees)	2 (60.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (40.0%)	3
Total		70	62	136	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.9 above, the first column *has qualified staff for all the roles*, revealing a trend as the SME classification changes from Micro to Small and Medium; the corresponding

percentage (24%, 34.1% to 60%) of qualified staff increases. The above implies that as SMEs grow, they recruit the required number of staff who, in turn, contribute to their growth.

In the second column, *yes, there are staff for all the roles, but they are not qualified*, following a similar but shorter trend. There is an increase in semi-qualified staff between the first two classifications and drops to zero for the medium SMEs.

In the third column, *no, one person performs multiple roles because there is insufficient staff*. However, it shows no consistency but reveals a significant reduction of the SMEs, with one team performing various functions as they grow in size. Thus, from 59.7% as micro to 6.8% as a medium.

Table 5.10 below is the chi-square and correlation analysis to determine the relationship and level of correlation between them.

Table 5-10: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.9

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	53.529 ^a	4	.000
Pearson's R	-.280		
Linear-by-Linear Association	20.876	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 3 cells (33.3%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .69.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

H₀: The required number of staff in an SME is independent of the classification of the SME.

H₁: The required number of staff in an SME is not independent of the classification of the SME.

From Table 5.10 above, the p-value is 0.000, as shown on Pearson's chi-square row under 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)', which is lower than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis. The above is an indication that there is a relationship between SME classification and the required workforce.

To measure the level of correlation between them, we compare Pearson's correlation coefficient of r is -0.280, to Table 5.2 above. The result reveals a slight correlation between SME classification and their required staff.

5.2.6 How refresher training can help SMEs develop a business plan

Continuous Professional Development training is essential for both employees and the development of SMEs. Moreover, drafting a business plan requires a certain level of technical competence. The above implies that SMEs without the necessary training will likely not possess a business plan. The inability of SMEs to draft a business plan is a significant hindrance to credit accessibility (Donga et al., 2016). To ascertain the above assertion questions 9 and 11 were cross-tabulated with their accompanied chi-square and correlation analysis and the results are shown in Tables 5.11 and 5.12 below:

Table 5-11: crosstabulation of continuous professional development training for SME staff and the existence of a business plan at the SMEs

Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management)? * Does the organisation have an existing business plan? Cross tabulation				
		Does the organisation have an existing business plan?		Total
		Yes	No	
Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management)?	Yes	56 (57.1%)	42 (42.9%)	98
	No	32 (18.8%)	138 (81.2%)	170
Total		88	180	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.11, the first column under the question, *does the organisation have an existing business plan?* 57.1% of SMEs with business plans also had their staff undergo business

management training. Meanwhile, only 18% of business plans were recorded for SMEs that did not have any of their team embark on any form of training. The SMEs that had their staff trained but did not have existing business plans in the second column were 42.9%. SMEs that did not have any of their team trained and did not have an existing business plan are 81.2%. From the above analysis, most SMEs that had their staff undertake capacity training do have existing business plans.

Table 5.12 below is the chi-square and correlation analysis to confirm the relationship and reveal the level of correlation between the training status of an SME management member and the SME having an existing business plan.

Table 5-12: The chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.11 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests					
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	41.390 ^a	1	.000		
Pearson's R	.393				
Linear-by-Linear Association	41.235	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	268				
a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 32.18.					
b. Computed only for a 2x2 Table					

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: An existing business plan at an SME is independent of the SME's staff's continuous professional development training.

H1: An existing business plan at an SME is not independent of the Continuous professional development training by SME staff.

From Table 5.12, the p-value of 0.000 is less than the standard alpha value of 0.50, and hence, we reject the null hypothesis. The above implies a relationship between the training status of an SME management member and the SME having an existing business plan.

Also, Pearson's correlation coefficient, r , is 0.393, compared to Table 5.2 above. It reveals a medium correlation between the continuous professional development of SME staff and a business plan. Therefore, we conclude that SMEs are better off having a business plan when their staff undergo capacity-building training.

5.2.7 The impact of refresher training on the practice of bookkeeping

Adjei (2014) purported that most SMEs are not privy to institutions that can support their growth, and even where they are, they lack the required skills in most cases to access these opportunities. Standard bookkeeping has challenged most SMEs in the Wa Municipality of Ghana and beyond. The above is made worse due to the SME staff's lack of continuous professional development training. Rogers (2002) documented improper record-keeping as one of the main factors causing SMEs to crash. Because of the above, questions 9 and 12 have been cross-tabulated to ascertain the importance of staff training in standard bookkeeping. Table 5.13 below is the IBM SPSS 25 crosstabulation results, supporting the above literature.

Table 5-13: crosstabulation of Continuous Professional Development training of SME staff and the practice of standard bookkeeping

Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management)? * Does the organisation practice standard bookkeeping					
		Does the organisation practice standard bookkeeping			Total
		Yes, all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly.	Yes, but sometimes personal finances get mixed up with business capital.	No, the organisation does not keep accounting records at all.	
Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management)?	Yes	58 (59.2%)	16 (16.3%)	24 (24.5%)	98
	No	86 (50.6%)	18 (10.6%)	66 (38.8%)	170
Total		144	34	90	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.13 above, 59.2% of the SMEs with their staff trained practice standard bookkeeping. Meanwhile, only 50.6% of the SMEs who have not provided training to their staff practice bookkeeping. The above indicates that if more opportunities are created for the staff of SMEs to have the proper Continuous Professional Development training, there will be more standard bookkeeping practices among the SMEs and easier access to credit.

Table 5.14 below is the chi-square and correlation coefficient analysis supporting the above revelation and determining the correlation level.

Table 5-14: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.13

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.271 ^a	2	.043
Pearson's R	.121		
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.911	1	.048
N of Valid Cases	268		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 12.43.

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The practice of standard bookkeeping by SMEs is independent of the Continuous professional development training obtained by the staff of the SMEs.

H1: The practice of standard bookkeeping obtained by SMEs is not independent of the Continuous professional development training by the staff of the SMEs.

Table 5.14 reveals the p-value under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' to be 0.043, which is less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis. This implies some relationship between the practice of routine bookkeeping by SMEs and the Continuous professional development training by the staff of the SMEs.

Moreover, Pearson's correlation coefficient r , of 0.121, as shown in Table 5.13, when compared to Table 5.2 above, suggests a slight correlation between the practice of standard bookkeeping by SMEs and the Continuous professional development training by the staff of the SMEs.

5.2.8 The effects of Bookkeeping on SMEs' profit margin

In a developing economy like Ghana, most SMEs are constrained to putting the best practices to work. Moreover, SMEs' lack of proper bookkeeping often mixes business and personal finances (Nkuah et al., 2013). As a result, their accounting records are often labelled unreliable. The lack of basic financial management skills to turn their businesses into profit-making ventures make SMEs victims of microfinance loans. Questions 12 and 13 have been cross-tabulated to ascertain preliminary information supporting the above literature. Here, we

measure how standard bookkeeping can influence the percentage of the quarterly profit of SMEs.

Table 5-15: The cross-tabulated results of the practice of standard bookkeeping by SMEs and their percentage quarterly profit

What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital? * Does the organisation practice standard bookkeeping					
		Does the organisation practice standard bookkeeping			Total
		Yes, all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly.	Yes, but sometimes personal finances get mixed up with business capital.	No, the organisation does not keep accounting records at all.	
What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital?	Less than 10%	7 (31.9%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (68.1%)	22
	Between 10% and 20%	55 (45.5%)	13 (10.7%)	53 (43.8%)	121
	Between 20% and 30%	47 (61.0%)	15 (19.5%)	15 (19.5%)	77
	Between 30% and 50	20 (74.0%)	4 (14.9%)	3 (11.1%)	27
	Between 50% and 100%	15 (71.4%)	2 (9.5%)	4 (19.0%)	21
Total		144	34	90	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Table 5.15 above is the crosstabulation of the percentage quarterly profit of SMEs versus their practice of standard bookkeeping. From the tabulated data above, the first column that says *that all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly* reveals an increasing profit trend as the percentage profit of SMEs increases until in the final row, where it drops slightly by just 2.6%. Thus, 31.9% of the SMEs who practice standard bookkeeping make less

than 10% of quarterly profits. Also, 45.5% make between 10% and 20% quarterly profit, 61.0% between (20% and 30%); and 74.0% between 30% and 50.

Conversely, the last column for SMEs that responded to *no, the organisation does not keep accounting records*, has their quarterly profit reducing as the percentages of profit increase under its columns. Thus, 68.1% of SMEs that do not practice standard bookkeeping make less than 10% profit. More so, 43.8% make between 10% and 20% of quarterly profit; 19.5% make between (20% and 30%) of profit, and only 11.1% make between 30% and 50% of the profit.

In summary, SMEs that practice standard bookkeeping make more returns than those that do not. Table 5.16 below is a chi-square and correlation analysis supporting the above research and revealing the level of correlation between them.

Table 5-16:chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.15

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	35.338 ^a	8	.000
Pearson's R	-.287		
Linear-by-Linear Association	21.928	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 3 cells (20.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 2.66.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: SMEs' percentage quarterly profit is independent of their practice of standard bookkeeping.

H1: SMEs' percentage quarterly profit is not independent of their practice of standard bookkeeping.

From Table 5.16 above, the p-value on the row containing Pearson's chi-square is 0.000, which is less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Because of the above, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between the practice of routine bookkeeping and the SME's percentage quarterly profit.

Moreover, Comparing the Person's correlation coefficient $r = -0.287$ to Table 5.2 above reveals a small to almost medium correlation between the practice of standard bookkeeping and the SME's percentage quarterly profit. In conclusion, all SMEs that practice routine bookkeeping are likelier to record a higher percentage of quarterly profit than those that do not.

5.2.9 The effects of refresher training on SMEs' profit margin

The primary aim of any business is to maximise profit and minimise cost. Investing in staff development would mean it is tailored to either profit-making or minimising wastage. Because of the above, questions 9 and 13 have been cross-tabulated to ascertain how the training status of an SME staff member can influence the quarterly profit margin of the SME. Table 5.17 below is the outcome of the crosstabulation.

Table 5-17: crosstabulation of the continuous professional development training of SME staff and SME's percentage quarterly profit

What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital? * Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management)?				
		Has any management team member ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management)?		Total
		Yes	No	
What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital?	Less than 10%	7 (31.9%)	15 (68.1%)	22
	Between 10% and 20%	45 (37.2%)	76 (62.8%)	121
	Between (20% and 30%)	28 (36.4%)	49 (63.6%)	77
	Between 30% and 50	10 (37.0%)	17 (63.0%)	27
	Between 50% and 100%	8 (38.1%)	13 (61.9%)	21
Total		98	170	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Table 5.17 above is the crosstabulation of continuous professional development for SME staff and the quarterly percentage profit of the SMEs. Interestingly, it reveals a trend where the SMEs who responded to not having any form of continuous professional development training make almost twice the profit of the SMEs with some professional development training. This raises questions about the kind and content of training given to SMEs as continuous development training. Although education plays a significant role in SME growth (King and McGrath, 2002), it must be the proper education. Table 5.18 below is the chi-square and correlation result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-18: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.17 above.

Chi-Square and correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.259 ^a	4	.992
Pearson's R	-.016		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.067	1	.796
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 7.68.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: SMEs' quarterly profit is independent of the continuous professional development training obtained by their staff.

H1: SMEs' quarterly profit is not independent of the continuous professional development training obtained for their staff.

In Table 5.18 above, the p-value on Pearson's chi-square row is 0.992. This figure is greater than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis. The above implies there is no relationship between the continuous professional development training of SME staff and the percentage quarterly profit of the SMEs.

Also, referring to Table 5.2, Pearson's correlation coefficient, r is -0.016, reveals no correlation between continuous professional development training of SME staff and the percentage quarterly profit of the SMEs.

The above is an exciting outcome and calls for a review of the training the SME management teams acquire for practice.

5.2.10 The impact of higher Education on SMEs' profit margin

Most SMEs fail primarily due to making the wrong choices when it comes to decision-making. The most educated on the management teams are mostly the decision-makers. Therefore, getting the proper education is critical in making the right decisions for the growth of SMEs.

Given the above, this thesis finds out through crosstabulation whether the highest level of education of an SME management team member impacts the percentage of quarterly profit SMEs make. Questions 8 and 13 have been cross-tabulated, and the result is shown below:

Table 5-19: crosstabulation of the impact of an SME management team member's highest educational qualification and its quarterly profit percentage.

What is the highest qualification on the management team? * What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital? Cross tabulation							
Count							
		What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital?					Total
		Less than 10%	Between 10% and 20%	Between (20% and 30%)	Between 30% and 50	Between 50% and 100%	
What is the highest qualification on the management team?	Senior High School Certificates	11 (11.0%)	44 (44.0%)	24 (24.0%)	9 (9.0%)	12 (12.0%)	100
	Diploma	4 (7.4%)	20 (37.0%)	22 (40.8%)	7 (13.0%)	1 (1.9%)	54
	Degree	0 (0.0%)	23 (48.9%)	15 (31.9%)	4 (8.5%)	5 (10.6%)	47
	Masters	0 (0.0%)	3 (50.0%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	6
	Primary School	1 (8.3%)	10 (83.3%)	1 (8.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	12
	Junior High School	4 (19.0%)	9 (43.0%)	4 (19.0%)	2 (9.5%)	2 (9.5%)	21
	None	2 (7.1%)	12 (42.9%)	10 (35.7%)	3 (10.8%)	1 (3.6%)	28
Total		22	121	77	27	21	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Table 5.19 above is the crosstabulation of the highest level of education on the management team of an SME versus the percentage quarterly profit the SME makes. It appears that all the listed types of qualifications, including those without formal qualifications, have most of their SMEs within the quarterly profit enclave of between 10% and 20%. Only those with diplomas have a majority in the profit brackets of between (20% and 30%). The above analysis reveals no particular trend between the highest qualification of a management team member and SME percentage quarterly profit. Table 5.19 is a chi-square and correlation result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-20: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.19

Chi-Square and correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.586 ^a	24	.113
Pearson's R	-.061		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.982	1	.322
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 20 cells (57.1%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .47.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The percentage quarterly profit of SMEs is independent of the highest qualification on its management team.

H1: The percentage of the quarterly profit of SMEs is not independent of the highest qualification on its management team.

From Table 5.20 above, the p-value under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' is 0.113, less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. This implies a relationship between the highest qualification of a management team member and SME percentage quarterly profit.

However, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is -0.061, which is not enough to reveal any level of correlation, as shown in Table 5.2. Because of the above, we conclude that although there is a relationship between the highest qualification of a management team member and SME

percentage quarterly profit, there is not enough evidence to reveal the level of correlation between them.

5.2.11 The impact of credit on SMEs lifespan

SMEs require credits to develop and grow. Nonetheless, not all credits have proven to be helpful to small businesses. Loans with unfriendly payment terms can be damaging to SMEs. Given the above, section 5.2.1 of this study seeks to determine how SME loan acquisition can affect the years it has been in business. Questions 5 and 16 were cross-tabulated, and the results are displayed in Table 5.21 below.

Table 5-21: crosstabulation of SME loan acquisition status and how long the SME has been in business

Has the organisation ever applied for a loan facility? * For how long has the firm been in business?							
		For how long has the firm been in business?					Total
		Less than one year	Between two and five years	Between six and ten years	Between eleven and fifteen years	Over fifteen years	
Has the organisation ever acquired a credit facility?	Yes	7 (5.8%)	45 (37.2%)	43 (35.5%)	17 (14.0%)	9 (7.4%)	121
	No	8 (5.4%)	52 (35.4%)	53 (36.0%)	22 (15.0%)	12 (8.2%)	147
Total		15	97	96	39	21	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.21 above, SMEs' loan acquisition status is cross-tabulated against their business years. Most SMEs who have ever taken loans are within their second and fifth year (37.2%) of operation, whilst most of those who have not taken loans are within their sixth and tenth year (36%). Nonetheless, the rest of the data is almost evenly distributed across both sides and shows no particular trait. Table 5.22 below is the chi-square and correlation analysis of the above data.

Table 5-22: chi-square and correlation analysis in support of Table 5.21

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.162 ^a	4	.997
Pearson's R	.024		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.154	1	.694
N of Valid Cases	268		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 6.77.

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

H₀: How long an SME has been in business is independent of its loan acquisition status.

H₁: How long an SME has been in business is not independent of its loan acquisition status.

From Table 5.22 above, the p-value under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' is 0.997, more significant than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis. In conclusion, no relationship exists between how long an SME has been in business and its loan acquisition status.

Additionally, the correlation coefficient $r = 0.024$, according to Table 5.20 above, indicates that there is no level of correlation between how long an SME has been in business and its loan acquisition status.

5.2.12 The Effects of Credit on SMEs' Profit Margin

Credit acquired by SMEs could be beneficial if well managed. However, misappropriation of funds comes with negative repercussions on the general well-being of an SME, including expected profit. Because of the above, questions 13 and 16 have been cross-tabulated to investigate how an SME's percentage quarterly profit is possibly affected by their loan acquisition status. The outcome of the crosstabulation is displayed in Table 5.23 below.

Table 5-23: crosstabulation of SME loan acquisition status and SME percentage quarterly profit

Has the organisation ever applied for a loan facility? * What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital?							
		What percentage of profit does the organisation make quarterly on its investment capital?					Total
		Less than 10%	Between 10% and 20%	Between (20% and 30%)	Between 30% and 50	Between 50% and 100%	
Has the organisation ever acquired a loan?	Yes	5 (4.1%)	64 (52.9%)	34 (28.1%)	13 (10.7%)	5 (4.1%)	121
	No	17 (11.6%)	57 (38.8%)	43 (29.3%)	14 (9.5%)	16 (10.9%)	147
Total		22	121	77	27	21	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Table 5.23 above is the crosstabulation of SMEs' loan acquisition status and their percentage quarterly profit. It is revealed that except for the column 'Between 10% and 20%', where more (52.9%) of SMEs that ever applied for loans made a profit than the SMEs who have not applied for loans, any other remaining column have more SMEs profit in the 'No' row than those in the 'Yes' row. The above reveals a relationship between SME loan acquisition and the percentage of quarterly profit. SMEs with loans to pay cannot make more profits than those without any debt to service. Table 5.24 below is the chi-square and correlation test result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-24: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.23 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.386 ^a	4	.023
Pearson's R	.056		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.826	1	.364
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 9.48.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

H₀: SMEs' loan acquisition status is independent of their percentage quarterly profit.

H₁: SMEs' loan acquisition status is not independent of their percentage quarterly profit.

From Table 5.24 above, the p-value under 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' is 0.023, less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis. Given the above, we confirm a relationship between SME loan acquisition status and their percentage rate of quarterly returns.

However, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is 0.056, which, compared to Table 5.2 above, shows insufficient evidence of correlation. Therefore, we conclude that although there is evidence of a relationship between SMEs' acquisition of loans and their quarterly percentage returns, the study did not find enough evidence to reveal the level of correlation that exists between them.

5.2.13 The impact of bookkeeping on SMEs credit application

Access to credit has been a significant constraint for most SMEs in the developing world. As part of the efforts to unravel the mystery behind the above challenge, this thesis discovers the effect proper bookkeeping can have on SME loan applications. Given the above, questions 12 and 20 have been cross-tabulated, as shown in Table 5.25 below.

Table 5-25: Crosstabulation of the practice of bookkeeping and SME loan application status

Has the organisation ever been refused or denied credit from a financial institute? *					
		Does the organisation practice standard bookkeeping			Total
		Yes, all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly.	Yes, but sometimes personal finances get mixed up with business capital.	No, the organisation does not keep accounting records at all.	
Has the organisation ever been refused or denied credit from a bank?	Yes	15 (39.4%)	10 (26.3%)	13 (34.2%)	38
	No	57 (68.7%)	8 (9.6%)	18 (21.7%)	83
Total		72	18	31	121

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25).

Table 5.25 above is the crosstabulation of the loan refusal status of SMEs against their practice of standard bookkeeping. From the first column, 'Yes, all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly,' it can be seen that more SMEs (68.7%) documented that they have not been refused loans because they practice standard bookkeeping. In the last column, where they do not practice bookkeeping, it can be seen that the percentage of SMEs whose loans were declined (34.2%) is more than those granted loans (21.7%). Because of the above, it is concluded that SMEs that practice standard bookkeeping stand a better chance of getting their loan application approved than those that do not practice bookkeeping. Table 5.26 below is the chi-square and correlation test results supporting Table 5.25 above.

Table 5-26: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.25

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.445 ^a	4	.009
Pearson's R	.035		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.324	1	.569
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. one cell (11.1%) has an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 4.82.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: SMEs' loan refusal status is independent of their practice of standard bookkeeping

H1: SMEs' loan refusal status is not independent of their practice of standard bookkeeping

From Table 5.26 above, the p-value under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' on Pearson's chi-square row is 0.009, less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between SMEs' loan refusal status and their practice of standard bookkeeping.

However, Pearson's correlation coefficient, $r = 0.035$, is not significant enough to reveal any level of correlation, according to Table 5.2 above. It is concluded that although there is evidence of a relationship between SMEs practising standard bookkeeping and their loan refusal status, as revealed by the chi-square test results, Pearson's correlation coefficient is not significant enough to disclose the level of correlation between them.

5.2.14 How the gender of SMEs owner/manager affects their credit amount

According to Lutz and Lutz (2017), women-owned SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa are more exposed to financial challenges than those owned by their male counterparts. It is reassuring that Wellalage and Locke (2017) did not find women-owned businesses discriminated against when they researched the south of Asia. However, Fjose et al. (2010) have listed the difficulty in accessing finance as a significant hindrance to the growth of SMEs in sub-Saharan Africa. Interestingly, despite the challenges SME owners/managers face, scholarly research has

suggested women are more risk-averse (Charness and Gneezy, 2012; Eckel & Grossman, 2008). Given the above, women SME owners/managers will likely shy away from making investment decisions with appreciable risk, thereby compounding their financial woes. These may include taking loans for business expansion.

In contrast, Sundheim (2013) purported that women take as much risk as men. In his view, the gender perception of risk could be balanced if risk-taking is defined beyond financial and physical terms. The definition of risk-taking should entail the risk of taking an ethical path and standing for the right decisions no matter the level of opposition and consequences. He believes women do better than men and are equally important in the holistic growth of a business. Nelson (2012), in her publication, 'Are women really more risk-averse than men?', concluded that there is a 'fundamentally metaphysical assertion about unobservable essences or characteristics' that cannot be either proven or disproven empirically.

Section 5.24 of this thesis is on the mission to find out whether the gender of an SME owner/manager has a relationship with the level of risk they take on credit acquisition.

Below is the crosstabulation of questions 1 and 22, with the results displayed in Table 5.27.

Table 5-27: Crosstabulation of the gender of SME owner and the highest amount of loan borrowed

What was the highest amount the organisation ever borrowed from a financial institution? * Gender of respondent				
		Gender of respondent		Total
		Male	Female	
What was the highest amount the organisation ever borrowed from a credit institute?	Less than GHC 10,000	18 (45%)	22 (55%)	40
	Between GHC 10,000 and GHC 20,000	19 (65.5%)	10 (34.5%)	29
	Between GHC 20,000 and GHC 30,000	5 (71.4%)	2 (28.6%)	7
	Between GHC 30,000 and GHC 50,000	5 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5
	Above GHC 50,000	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2
Total		49 (59.0%)	34 (41.0%)	83

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.27 above, it can be seen that the female-owned SMEs are more active (55%) in borrowing at *Less than GHC 10,000* (less risk) compared to their male counterparts. However, any amount borrowed above GHC 10,000 (high risk) is dominated by the male-owned SMEs, as shown from the second row of figures (65.5% males to 34.5% females) through to the last row, where the study recorded 100% for male SMEs who went in for loans above GHC50,000 (higher risk). Table 5.28 below shows a chi-square and correlation analysis results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-28: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.27 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.398 ^a	5	.044
Pearson's R	.003		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.003	1	.955
N of Valid Cases	268		

a. 6 cells (50.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .95.

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The highest amount of money an SME ever borrowed is independent of the gender of the SME owner/manager.

H1: The highest amount of money an SME ever borrowed is not independent of the gender of the SME owner/manager.

From Table 5.28 above, the p-value under 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' is 0.044, less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between the highest amount of money an SME ever borrowed and the gender of the SME owner/manager.

However, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is 0.003, suggesting that there is not enough evidence to indicate the level of correlation between the gender of SME owner/manager and the highest amount of money ever borrowed.

5.2.15 How SMEs' perception of lending rates affects their interest in credit

SMEs are mostly bedevilled with high-interest rates. For instance, a selected sample of Ethiopian enterprises rated high-interest rates on business loans as the second most worrying obstacle SMEs face (Amentie et al., 2016). High-interest rates, among other things, have scared most SMEs from taking loans with the fear of defaulting and getting prosecuted. To galvanise first-hand information on the above assertion, section 5.1.15 of this dissertation has cross-tabulated SMEs' perception of lending rates and their loan acquisition status. The results of the cross-tabulated questions 16 and 27 are displayed in Table 5.29 below.

Table 5-29: Crosstabulation of interest rates and the willingness of SMEs to apply for loans

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Has the organisation ever applied for a loan facility? * How does the organisation generally find lending rates amidst interest charges? Crosstabulation							
		How does the organisation generally find lending rates amidst interest charges?					Total
		Low (1% to 5%)	Acceptable (6% to 10%)	Average (11% to 15%)	High (16% to 20%)	Extremely High (21% and above)	
Has the organisation ever applied for a loan facility?	Yes	4 (3.3%)	15 (12.4%)	23 (19.0%)	31 (25.6%)	48 (39.7%)	121
	No	5 (3.4%)	3 (2.0%)	0	5 (3.4%)	134 (91.2%)	147
Total		9 (3.4%)	18 (6.7%)	23 (8.6%)	36 (13.4%)	182 (67.9%)	268

From Table 5.29 above, second row from the bottom, the majority (147 out of sample 268) of SMEs never applied for loans. Out of the above figure, 91.2% of the SMEs who never applied for loans think interest rates are incredibly high (21% and above) against the 39.7% of the SMEs who applied for a loan. Table 5.30 below shows the chi-square and correlation coefficient results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-30: chi-square and correlation test results support Table 5.29 above.

Chi-Square and correlation Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	88.840 ^a	4	.000
Pearson's R	.412		
Linear-by-Linear Association	45.266	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 2 cells (20.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is 4.06.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: SMEs' willingness to apply for a credit facility is independent of how they generally find lending rates amidst interest rates charged.

H1: SMEs' willingness to apply for a credit facility is not independent of how they generally find lending rates amidst interest rates charged.

Table 5.30 above reveals a p-value of 0.000 under 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)', which is less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between SMEs' willingness to apply for a credit facility and how they generally find lending rates amidst interest rates charged.

Moreover, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is 0.412, as shown above in the fourth row. According to Table 5.2 above, the value of $r=0.412$ means a medium correlation exists between SMEs' willingness to apply for a credit facility and how they generally find lending rates amidst interest rates charged.

5.2.16 SMEs' Perception of lending rates and how they raised their initial capital

Raising initial capital has been the main challenge for most businesses. Most brilliant business ideas could not see the light of day because their owners could not secure initial capital. More so when financial institutions are charging higher lending rates. Given the above, questions 27 and 29 have been cross-tabulated to get first-hand information on how SMEs raise their initial capital amidst the current lending rates. Table 5.31 below is the crosstabulation results on the effects of lending rates on raising initial money.

Table 5-31: Crosstabulation of how SMEs raise their initial capital and how SMEs find lending rates

How does the organisation generally find lending rates amidst interest charges? * How was the initial capital raised for the organisation?							
		How was the initial capital raised for the organisation?					Total
		Personal Savings	Bank credit	Friends and relative	Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	Farmin g	
How does the organisation generally find lending rates amidst interest charges?	Low (1% to 5%)	6 (60.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (30.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	9
	Acceptable (6% to 10%)	13 (72.2%)	3 (16.7%)	1 (5.5%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.5%)	18
	Average (11% to 15%)	17 (74%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (13.0%)	3 (13.0%)	0 (0.0%)	23
	High (16% to 20%)	22 (61.1%)	7 (19.4%)	6 (16.7%)	1 (2.8%)	0 (0.0%)	36
	Extremely High (21% and above)	116 (63.7%)	16 (8.8%)	48 (26.4%)	2 (1.1%)	0 (0.0%)	182
Total		174	26	61	6	1	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.31 above, most SMEs used *personal savings* and helped from their *friends and relatives* to raise their initial capital. For instance, 63.7% of the SMEs documented that they find interest rates extremely high under the personal savings column, hence their decision to use personal savings. The next higher group of SMEs under the *extremely High (21% and above)* row are those who got help from *family and friends* (26.4%). SMEs prefer other sources of funding to receive credit from the bank. The *bank credit* column confirms this assertion, with fewer SMEs than those who accessed credit through *personal savings* and *family and*

friends. Sources like the *Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA)* and *farming* were accessed. Table 5.32 below shows a chi-square and correlation test results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-32: chi-square and correlation test results support Table 5.31 above.

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	41.199 ^a	16	.001
Pearson's R	.022		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.132	1	.716
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 16 cells (64.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .03.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: How SMEs raise their initial capital is independent of how they generally find lending rates amidst interest charges.

H1: How SMEs raise their initial capital is not independent of how they generally find lending rates amidst interest charges.

From Table 5.32 above, the p-value is shown to be 0.001 under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' column, which is less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between how SMEs raise their initial capital and how they generally find lending rates amidst interest charges.

However, Pearson's correlation coefficient reveals a value of 0.022 on Pearson's R row. This figure, compared to Table 5.2 above, indicates no level of correlation. Therefore, we conclude that although there is evidence of relationships between how SMEs raise their initial capital and how they generally find lending rates amidst interest charges, there is not enough evidence to determine the level of correlation between them.

5.2.17 How SMEs raise their initial capital and their sources of continuous funding

Inadequate capital came up as the major challenge faced by SMEs and local artisans (Amegashie-Viglo and Bokor, 2014, 30-32) in a survey in Ghana's Volta and Oti regions. SMEs

need to be funded continuously to ensure the needed development and growth. However, stringent collateral requirements and complex bureaucracies, among others, have been the standing blocks to SMEs getting the required financial support to finance their growth (Anderson, 2017). After revealing the sources of funding and continuous funding of the surveyed SMEs in chapter four, this section aims at showing the relationship or differences between questions 29 and 30. Given the above, Table 5.33 below is the cross-tabulated results of how initial capital was raised against the sources of continued funding of the SMEs.

Table 5-33: How initial capital was raised versus continuous sources of funding SMEs

How was the initial capital raised for the organisation? * What are the sources of continuous funding for the business?									
		What are the sources of continuous funding for the business?							Total
		Bank Loan	Personal Savings	Retained Profits	Private Institutions	Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	Donor	Family/Friends	
How was the initial capital raised for the organisation?	Personal Savings	8 (4.6%)	50 (28.7%)	108 (62.1%)	1 (0.6%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.6%)	4 (2.3%)	174
	Bank credit	5 (19.2%)	3 (11.5%)	17 (65.4%)	1 (3.8%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	26
	Friends and relative	2 (3.3%)	15 (24.5%)	37 (60.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (11.5%)	61
	Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (66.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	6
	Farmin g	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1
Total		15	68	165	2	6	1	11	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.33 above, the first column reveals how the SMEs raised their initial capital, and the row on top shows the various sources of continuous funding. It can be seen that most SMEs have used the retained profit to fund their business more than any other source continuously. For example, 62.1% of those who used *personal savings* as *initial capital* resulted in *retained earnings* for continuous funding. 65.4% of those who used bank credit as initial capital turned to retained profit for continuous financing. In total, 165 SMEs out of the sampled 268 relied on *retained profit* for continuous funding. Only 15 (5.6%) SMEs out of the sampled 268 returned to *bank credit* as a continuous funding source.

Interestingly, 66.7% of the SMEs who raised their capital through VSLA returned to the same source for continuous funding. The above could be due to the little or no interest rates these associations charge and the fact that they give a relatively tiny amount of funds as loans. In conclusion, irrespective of the source of initial capital raised, most SMEs result in *retained profits* (61.6%) and *personal savings* (24.3%) as the primary sources for continuously funding their businesses. Table 5.34 below is the chi-square and correlation test result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-34: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.33

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	144.957 ^a	24	.000
Pearson's R	.205		
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.245	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. 27 cells (77.1%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .00.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: How SMEs continuously fund their businesses depends on how they raise their initial capital.

H1: How SMEs continuously fund their businesses is not independent of how they raise their initial capital.

From Table 5.34 above, the p-value of 0.000, shown under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' column, is smaller than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude that there is a relationship between how SMEs raise their initial capital and continuously fund their businesses.

Moreover, Pearson's correlation coefficient reveals a value is 0.205. The above depicts a slight correlation between how SMEs raise their initial capital and how they continuously fund their businesses.

5.2.18 The effects of covid-19 and owner/managers perceive their businesses post covid

The effects of covid-19 on the global economy have been enormous. SMEs have been most affected by their minor and mostly unprotected nature. This section of the thesis seeks to discover the relationship or differences between the current impact of covid-19 on SMEs and how the owners perceive their businesses after the covid-19 pandemic. Questions 32 and 33 were cross-tabulated and displayed in Table 5.35 below to achieve the above.

Table 5-35: Crosstabulation of the effect of covid 19 on SMEs and how the SME owners perceive their businesses after covid 19

How has Covid-19 impacted your business? * How do you see your business after Covid-19?						
		How do you see your business after Covid-19?				Total
		Fully operating	Partly operating	Closed down	Unable to predict	
How has Covid-19 impacted your business?	Negatively	85 (37.0%)	89 (38.7%)	13 (5.7%)	43 (18.6%)	230
	Positively	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2
	No impact	32 (88.9%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (11.1%)	36
Total		119	89	13	47	268

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.35 above, the second column is up against the third row. Most SMEs documented *negatively* to the question; *how has Covid-19 impacted your business?* Do perceive their firms to be *partly operating* (38.7%) after covid-19. This is closely followed on the same row by the SMEs who think their businesses will be *fully functioning* despite the current negative impact they face. These were followed by the SMEs who *could not predict* their future (18.6%) and those who believed that the present Covid-19 effects would lead to their businesses being *closed down* (5.7%).

For the SMEs who responded positively to the question, *how has Covid-19 impacted your business?* All of them believed their companies would *fully operate* after the covid-19 pandemic.

Interestingly, of the SMEs that responded *no* to the question, *how has Covid-19 impacted your business?* 11.1% of them cannot predict their future, and 88.9% believe they will *fully operate*.

In conclusion, the current effect of covid 19 on SMEs affects how the owners perceive their businesses after covid-19. Table 3.36 below shows the chi-square and correlation test results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-36: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.35 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	38.536 ^a	6	.000
Pearson's R	-.233		
Linear-by-Linear Association	14.508	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	268		
a. five cells (41.7%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .10.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: How SMEs see themselves after covid 19 is independent of the current impact of covid 19 on them.

H1: How SMEs see themselves after covid 19 is not independent of the current impact of covid 19 on them.

Table 5.56 above reveals a p-value of 0.000, less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between how SMEs see themselves after covid-19 and the current impact of covid 19 on them.

Also, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is -0.233, which, compared to Table 5.2 above, reveals a slight correlation between how SMEs see themselves after covid-19 and the current impact of covid 19 on them.

5.3 Regression

Two binary and one linear regression were calculated, as shown in the Table below: Binary regression was chosen because both dependent variables were dichotomous.

Table 5-37: Correlation and Regression test results on SME Owner/Managers

	R ²	ε	Regression	Residual	β_0	β_x	Df	F	Pearson's R
Independent Variables	Dependent Variable Has the SME ever applied for a loan? (Binary Regression)								
Loan conditions	0.870	0.187	57.112	9.258	0.518	β_1 0.047	F (1, 266)	886.446	0.928
Lending rates	0.861	0.180	57.739	8.630	0.518	β_2 0.201	F (2, 265)	1640.972	0.412
Independent Variables	Dependent Variable Has the SME ever been refused credit from a Financial Institution?								
Default history	0.685	0.407	95.862	44.001	0.366	β_1 0.627	F (1, 266)	579.517	0.828
Loan Purpose	0.714	0.388	99.923	39.939	0.366	β_2 0.224	F (1, 265)	331.498	0.727
SME Classification	0.728	0.380	101.784	38.007	0.366	β_3 -0.203	F (1, 264)	235.232	-0.255
Independent Variables	Dependent Variable What % profit does the SME makes quarterly on its investment capital?								
Source of loan	0.001	1.037	0.337	284.821	0.017	-	F (1, 265)	0.35	0.36

Source: Author's computations from IBM SPSS 25

5.3.1 Loan Application

Multiple linear regression was calculated from Table 5.37 above to predict the interest of SMEs in acquiring loans based on their perceptions of lending rates vis-à-vis the bureaucracies (conditions) involved in loan acquisition. The regression equation is outlined as follows:

$$\text{SMEInLA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{PLR} + \beta_2 \text{BLA} + \mathcal{E}$$

$$\text{SMEInLA} = 0.518 + 0.047 \text{PLR} + 0.201 \text{BLA} + 0.182$$

SMEInLA= SMEs interest in loan acquisition

β_0 = Constant

β_x = coefficients

PLR= Perception of lending rates

BLA= Bureaucracies involved in loan acquisition

\mathcal{E} = Standard error

From the Table above, significant regression equations were identified $F(1,266) = 1640,972$,

$P = (0.00)$ which explains 86.1% of estimates $R^2=0.861$ and $F(2, 265) = 886.446$,

$P = (0.00)$, which explains 87.0% of estimates $R^2=0.870$. From the above, very high variances have been explained by both perceptions of lending rates and the bureaucracies in accessing loans on this occasion.

Interestingly, the interest of SMEs in loan acquisitions increases by 0.047 points on a bureaucracy for loan acquisition and 0.201 points on a perception of lending rates.

5.3.1.1 Causality

Causality is based on the assumption that the value of an interdependent variable is the cause of the value of a dependent variable. However, “causality is very difficult to prove” (Warner, 2017). Indeed, others argue that causality can never be illustrated with finality and that the best researchers can do is to develop some progressively persuasive data that is compatible with causality.

There are two widely acknowledged preconditions for establishing causality: first, the variables must be associated (correlated); second, the independent variable must come before the dependent variable (temporal sequence); or there should be a theoretically valid and credible explanation explaining the causal relationship's direction (Warner, 2017).

Dependent variable: *The interest of SMEs in acquiring a loan.*

Independent Variables: From Table 5.37 above, there are significant regression relationships for both independent variables. Thus, *the perceptions of SMEs on lending rates* (Pearson's R= 0.412) and *the bureaucracies (conditions) involved in loan acquisition* (Pearson's R=0.928). Also, the predictors will happen before the criterion can take place. Thus, one's *perception of interest rates* coupled with *the bureaucracies involved in loan acquisition* will determine their *interest in acquiring the loan*. Hence, we conclude that there is a causal relationship between the predictors and the criterion.

5.3.2 Loan Refusal

A multiple linear regression (binary) was calculated to predict why *SMEs are often refused credit by Financial Institutions* based on their *history of loan default, the purpose of the loan being acquired, and SME classification*. The multiple linear regression equation is outlined as follows:

$$SMECrR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HLD + \beta_2 SMECl + \beta_3 PL + \varepsilon$$

$$SMECrR = 0.366 + 0.627HLD + 0.224PL - 0.203SMECl + 0.392$$

SMECrR= SME credit refusal

β_0 = Constant

β_x = coefficients

HLD= History of loan default

SMECl= SME classification

PL= purpose of loan

ϵ = Standard error

From Table 5.37 above, significant regression equations were identified $F(1,266) = 579.517$, ($P=0.00$); $F(2,265) = 331.498$, ($P= 0.00$); and $F(3, 264) = 235.232$, ($P = 0.00$). The above explains 68.5% of the variance ($R^2=0.685$), 71.2% of the variance ($R^2=0.712$) and 72.5% of the variance ($R^2=0.725$), respectively. The above variances explained are very high and thus confirm the significance of the independent variables on this occasion.

Moreso, the chances of an SME being refused credit are further appreciated by 0.627 points for every default in loan payment, 0.224 points for the purpose of loan acquisition stated and a decrease of 0.203 points for the SME classification.

5.3.2.1 Causality

Dependent variable: *Why SMEs are often refused credit by the Financial Institutions*

Independent Variables: From Table 5.37 above, there are significant regression relationships for all independent variables. *History of a loan default* (Pearson's $R= 0.828$); *the purpose of the loan being acquired* (Pearson's $R=0.727$); and *the classification of the SME* (Pearson's $R=-0.255$).

From the above, it is clear that the predictors will all be proven before the criterion takes effect. Thus, the SMEs *history of loan default, the purpose of the loan being acquired, and the classification of the SME involved* would be presented to a Financial Institution before the decision to *refuse the loan application by the Financial Institution* is taken (temporal

sequence). Hence, we conclude that independent variables have causal effects on the dependent variable.

5.3.3 SME Quarterly Profit

A simple linear regression was calculated to predict *the percentage quarterly profit of SMEs based on their source of loan*. The simple linear regression equation is outlined as follows:

$$\text{SMEQP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{SoL} + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{SMEQP} = 2.573 + 0.017 \text{SoL} + 1.037$$

SMEQP= SME Quarterly Profit

β_0 = Constant

β_x = coefficients

SoL= Source of Loan

ε = Standard error

From Table 5.37 above, a regression equation was identified $F(1,266) = 0.351$, ($P=0.554$). The above explains only 0.1% of the variance ($R^2=0.001$). Although the above variances explained are negligible, SME quarterly profit increases by 0.017 points for the choice of their source of loan. Table 4.5 reveals majority (48.8%) of SMEs to have taken their loans from the banks. Also, section 6.3 of this study mentioned that the banks give out loans for interest rates between (17.19 and 24) %. SMEs are advised to access loans from the banks with lower interest rates to enable them increase their quarterly profits.

5.3.3.1 Causality

Dependent variable: *What percentage profit does the SME makes on its investment capital quarterly?*

Independent Variables: *Where is the source of loan acquired?*

From Table 5.37 above, there is significant regression relationship between the predictor and criterion explained by Pearson's $R = 0.36$.

Also, it is clear that the independent variable would have happened before the dependent variable is determined. Thus, the SMEs' source loan and interest paid would have happened before the quarterly profit is calculated. Hence, we conclude that there is a temporal effect of SME loan source on the percentage quarterly profit they make.

5.4 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FOR SME FINANCING INSTITUTIONS

5.4.1 Crosstabulation

Table 5-38: selected questions from the SME financing institution's questionnaire for crosstabulation

No.	Paired questions	Reason for the crosstabulation
1	Q6 and Q14	To measure the correlation between the level of credit accessed from Financial Institutions against their recovery rates
2	Q10 and Q14	To ascertain the relationship between the FIs running a background check on SMEs before granting them loans versus their loan recovery rates.

Source: Author's compilations, 2021

5.4.2 The impact of the amount of credit accessed on the amount of credit recovered

Accessing credit is as challenging as credit recovery. This explains why financial institutions set stringent measures to ensure they grant SMEs credit that they can repay quickly. According to Amegashie-Viglo and Bokor (2014), only 27% of the 45 entrepreneurs, who had ever sourced for bank facilities, were successful in the Volta region of Ghana. To actualise the above assertion, questions 6 and 14 on the SME financing institute questionnaire were cross-tabulated, and the results are shown in Table 5.39 below.

Table 5-39: Accessed credit by SMEs versus recovered credit by the financial institute

What percentage of the organisation's credit facility has been accessed by SMEs? * What are the organisation's annual loan recovery rates for SMEs? Crosstabulation						
Count						
		What are the organisation's annual loan recovery rates for SMEs?				Total
		Between 61% and 70%	Between 71% and 80%	Between 81% and 90%	Between 91% and 100%	
What percentage of the organisation's credit facility has been accessed by SMEs?	Less than 50%	0	0	1 (100.0%)	0	1
	Between 51% and 60%	0	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	0	2
	Between 61% and 70%	1 (33.3%)	1 (33.3%)	0	1 (33.3%)	3
	Between 71% and 80%	0	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	0	2
	Between 91% and 100%	1 (100.0%)	0	0	0	1
Total		2 (22.2%)	3 (33.3%)	3 (33.3%)	1 (11.1%)	9

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.39 above, only the financial institutions among the groups who had *between 61% and 70%* of their credit consumed accessed by SMEs could recover *between 91% and 100%* of their loans. As shown above, the financial institutions that gave more credit to SMEs (*between 91% and 100%*) documented the lowest (*between 61% and 70%*) loan recovery rates. This implies that the more loans financial institutions give SMEs, the more difficult it is to recover. Table 5.40 below shows the chi-square and correlation test results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-40: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.39 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.000 ^a	12	.616
Pearson's R	-.459		
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.684	1	.194
N of Valid Cases	9		
a. 20 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .11.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: A financial institution's annual loan recovery rate is independent of the yearly percentage of its credit facility accessed by SMEs

H1: A financial institution's annual loan recovery rate is not independent of the yearly percentage of its credit facility accessed by SMEs

Table 5.40 above reveals a p-value of 0.616, above the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude there is no relationship between a financial institution's annual loan recovery rate and the annual percentage of its credit facility that SMEs have accessed.

Conversely, Pearson's correlation coefficient, r of -0.459, depicts a medium to almost strong correlation between a financial institution's annual loan recovery rate and the annual percentage of its credit facility that SMEs have accessed.

5.4.3 The impact of background checks before crediting SMEs on credit recovery

When SMEs access loans without basic managerial skills, they struggle to pay them back on time. Financial institutions have become essential to ensure well-trained SMEs access their credits. This part of the study seeks to empirically find out how running background checks on SMEs before granting loans could influence financial institutions' loan recovery rates. Given

the above, questions 10 and 14 have been cross-tabulated with the outcome displayed in Table 5.41 below.

Table 5-41: SME background checks before loans accessibility versus loan recovery rates

Does this financial institution make a background check to ensure SME managers have basic financial management skills before granting them credit? * What are the organisation's annual loan recovery rates for SMEs? Crosstabulation						
		What are the organisation's annual loan recovery rates for SMEs?				Total
		Between 61% and 70%	Between 71% and 80%	Between 81% and 90%	Between 91% and 100%	
Does this financial institution make a background check to ensure SME managers have basic financial management skills before granting them credit?	Yes	2 (40.0%)	2 (40.0%)	1 (20.0%)	0	5
	No	0	1 (25.0%)	2 (50.0%)	1 (25.0%)	4
Total		2 (22.2%)	3 (33.3%)	3 (33.3%)	1 (11.1%)	9

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.41 above, more loans were recovered by the financial institutions that do a background check on SMEs before granting them loans. 5 out of the 9 sampled financial institutions recovered above 60% of their loans. This is slightly higher than the four financial institutions that did not make background checks on SMEs before granting them loans. Table 5.42 below shows a chi-square and correlation test results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-42: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.41 above

Chi-Square and Correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.600 ^a	3	.308
Pearson's R	.632		
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.200	1	.074
N of Valid Cases	9		
a. 8 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .44.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: A financial institution's annual loan recovery rate is independent of the financial institution making background checks on SMEs before granting them loans.

H1: A financial institution's annual loan recovery rate is not independent of the financial institution making background checks on SMEs before granting them loans.

From Table 5.42 above, the p-value under the Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) column is 0.308, less than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between a financial institution's annual loan recovery rate and the financial institution making background checks on SMEs before granting them loans.

Moreover, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is 0.632, suggesting a significant correlation between a financial institution's annual loan recovery rate and the financial institution making background checks on SMEs before granting them loans.

5.5 Regression

A simple linear regression is calculated to predict a Financial Institution's loan recovery rate based on whether the FI makes background checks on SMEs to ensure they have basic financial management skills before granting them loans.

Table 5-43: Regression Analysis for SME Financing Institutes

	R ²	ε	Regression	Residual	β ₀	β ₁	Df	F	R
Independent Variables	Dependent Variable What is the Financial Institution's loan recovery rate?								
Background checks	0.4	0.828	3.200	4.800	2.600	1.200	F(1,7)	4.667	0.632

Source: Author's computations from IBM SPSS 25

The linear regression equation is outlined as follows:

$$FILRR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BC + \epsilon$$

$$FILRR = 2.600 + 1.2BC + 0.828$$

FILRR= A Financial Institution's Loan Recovery Rate

BC= Background checks on SMEs before granting loans

β₀= Constant

β_x= coefficients

ε= Standard Error

From Table 5.43 above, a significant regression equation is identified $F(1,7) = 4.667$, ($P=0.068$), which explains 400% of the variance ($R^2=0.400$). From the above context, the background checks by the Financing Institutions before granting SMEs loans are a great predictor of the estimates. The Financial Institution's loan recovery rate increased by 1.20 points anytime they carried out background checks before giving loans to SMEs.

5.5.1 Causality

Dependent variable: *A Financial Institution's Loan Recovery Rate*

Independent Variables: From Table 5.43 above, the independent variables show a significant regression relationship: *Background checks on SMEs before granting loans* (Pearson's $R=0.632$). Moreover, the independent variable precedes the dependent variable. Thus, Background checks before granting loans are done far before the loan recovery rate is measured (temporal sequence). From the above, the two basic requirements for causality have been fulfilled. Hence, we conclude that *Background checks on SMEs before granting loans* have a causal effect on a *Financial Institution's Loan Recovery Rate*.

5.6 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FOR SMEs SKILL DEV'T AND ADVISORY INSTITUTES

5.6.1 Crosstabulations

Table 5-44: selected questions from the SME skilled development and advisory institute's questionnaire for crosstabulation

No.	Paired questions	Reason for the crosstabulation
1	Q6 and Q7	To measure the correlation between the number of clients the Advisory Institute receive and the post-service follow-ups on clients
2	Q7 and Q9	To measure the relationship between post-service, follow-up on clients and the level of improvements of the clients.

Source: Author's compilations, 2021

5.6.2 The impacts of post-service follow-ups on the number of clients

Monitoring after-service delivery is crucial in all aspects of businesses. This part of the thesis seeks to find out how post-service follow-ups by SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institutes influence the number of clients they receive annually. Table 5.45 below is a crosstabulation of questions 6 and 7 on the SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institute questionnaire supporting the above assertion.

Table 5-45: post-service follow-up versus clients served

How many clients, on average, access the organisation's services in a year? * Does the organisation follow up on its clients to monitor their progress after providing your services? Crosstabulation				
		Does the organisation follow up on clients' progress after providing your services?		Total
		Yes	No	
How many average clients access the organisation's services in a year?	Below 20	1 (50.0%)	1 (50.0%)	2
	Between 21 and 50	1 (100.0%)	0	1
	Between 51 and 75	1 (100.0%)	0	1
Total		3 (75.0%)	1 (25.0%)	4

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.43 above, the SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institutes that practice post-service follow-ups on their clients are the majority (3 out of 4) and receive up to 75 clients annually. Also, the only SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institute that does not practice post-service follow-ups receive less than 20 clients annually. The above indicates that post-service follow-ups on SMEs by their Skilled Development Institutes have a relationship with the number of clients that access the services of those SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institutes. Table 5.46 below shows the chi-square and correlation test results on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-46: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.45 above

Chi-Square and correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.333 ^a	2	.513
Pearson's R	-.522		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.818	1	.366
N of Valid Cases	4		
a. 6 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum desired count is .25.			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The total number of clients an SME advisory institute receives annually is independent of the ability of the SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

H1: The total number of clients an SME advisory institute receives annually is not independent of the ability of the SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

From Table 5.44 above, the p-value is 0.513, shown under the 'Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)' column, which is more significant than the standard alpha value of 0.50. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no relationship between the total number of clients an SME advisory institute receives annually and the ability of the SME advisory institute to monitor its clients after service delivery.

Nonetheless, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is -0.522. Compared to Table 5.2 above, this value reveals a medium correlation between the total number of clients an SME advisory institute receives annually and the ability of the SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

In conclusion, although the chi-square analysis couldn't reveal any relationship between the above entities, Pearson's correlation coefficients suggest that post-service follow-ups could influence the number of customers.

5.6.3 The effects of post-service follow-ups on client improvement

Client improvement comes with much commitment; indeed, post-service follow-ups could be essential to ensure their development and growth. This part of the study has cross-tabulated questions 7, and 9 on the SME Skilled Development and Advisory Institute questionnaire, and the outcome is tabulated below in Table 5.47.

Table 5-47: post-service follow-up versus annual percentage client improvement

Does the organisation follow up on clients' progress after providing your services? * What average percentage of clients will the organisation consider having improved yearly? Crosstabulation				
		What average percentage of clients will the organisation consider having improved yearly?		Total
		Between 10% and 20%	Between 20% and 30%	
Does the organisation follow up on clients' progress after providing your services?	Yes	2 (66.6%)	1 (33.3%)	3
	No	1 (100.0%)	0	1
Total		3 (75.0%)	1 (25.0%)	4

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

From Table 5.47 above, the SMEs Skill Development and Advisory Institutes who documented that they practice post-service follow-ups are the majority (3 out of 4) and have seen their clients improve between 10% and 30%. The only SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes that do not practice post-service follow-up only managed a 10% to 20% improvement in its client. Table 5.48 below is the chi-square and correlation test result on whether there is a relationship and correlation between the above subjects.

Table 5-48: chi-square and correlation test results in support of Table 5.47 above

Chi-Square and correlation Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.444 ^a	1	.505
Pearson's R	-.333		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.333	1	.564
N of Valid Cases	4		
a. 4 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.			
b. Computed only for a 2x2 Table			

Source: Author's computations (IBM SPSS 25)

Ho: The percentage of clients that are considered to have improved annually by the advisory institute is independent of the ability of an SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

H1: The percentage of clients that are considered to have improved annually by the advisory institute is not independent of the ability of an SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

From Table 5.48 above, the p-value is 0.505, more significant than the standard alpha value of 0.50, so we accept the null hypothesis. In conclusion, there is no relationship between the percentage of clients that are considered to have improved annually by the advisory institute and the ability of an SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

Nonetheless, Pearson's correlation coefficient r is -0.333, which according to Table 5.2 above, depicts a medium correlation between the percentage of clients that are considered to have improved annually by the SME advisory institute and the ability of an SME advisory institute to monitor its clients.

Although the chi-square results did not reveal any relationship between the entities above, the correlation test above shows that SMEs' post-service monitoring helps them improve.

5.7 Regression

A simple linear regression was calculated to predict how many clients (SMEs), on average, access the services of the Advisory Institutes based on the highest level of education obtained by a staff of the Advisory Institute.

Table 5-49: Correlation and regression analysis for SME Advisory Institutes

	R ²	ε	Regression	Residual	β ₀	β ₁	Df	F	R
Independent Variables	Dependent Variable How many SMEs, on average, access the services of the Business Advisory Institute in a year?								
Highest level of education	0.273	1.000	0.750	2.000	0.750	0.250	F (1,2)	0.75	0.522

Source: Author's computations from IBM SPSS 25

The linear regression equation is outlined as follows:

$$\text{SMEsAccBusAdv} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{HLE} + \epsilon$$

$$\text{SMEsAccBusAdv} = 0.750 + 0.250\text{HLE} + \varepsilon$$

SMEsAccBusAdv = SMEs, on average, that access the services of the Business Advisory Institutes in a year

β_0 = Constant

β_x = coefficients

HLE = Highest level of education obtained by a Business Advisory Institute staff member.

ε = Standard Error

From Table 5.49, a significant linear regression was identified $F(1,2) = 0.750$, ($P=0.478$) which explains 27.3% of the variance ($R^2=0.273$). There was a substantial explanation of the variances by *the highest level of education obtained by a staff member of the Advisory Institute*. Moreover, the *number of SMEs that averagely access the services of the Advisory Institutes* increased by 0.25 points for each level of higher education attained by a staff of the Advisory Institutes. The above indicates that SMEs prefer the services of Advisory Institutes with highly educated staff.

5.7.1 Causality

Dependent variable: *SMEs, on average, that access the services of the Business Advisory*

Independent Variables: From the above, there is a significant regression relationship by the independent variable: *The highest level of education obtained by a Business Advisory Institute staff member* (Pearson's $R=0.522$).

From the above, the predictor precedes the criterion. Thus, staff members need some level of education before they can service SMEs. Hence, we conclude that the *Highest level of*

education obtained by a staff member of the Business Advisory Institute has a causal effect on the number of SMEs that averagely access the services of the Business Advisory.

CHAPTER SIX: RESEARCH FINDINGS: SME MANAGEMENT AND CREDIT POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Chapter Six presents the findings of this study and some recommendations based on the literature reviewed in chapter two, as well as the data collected and presented in Chapters Four and Five. Uniquely, this chapter adopts a consultancy approach by using business management models to present the findings and recommendations of this study. As Chapter One illustrates, SMEs' credit accessibility challenges can be viewed as a demand and supply scenario. On the demand side are the SMEs deemed risky and not competitive enough like the large corporations; On the supply side are the credit institutions that prefer to give credit to the less risky firms (large corporations). In between the two is a gap left to fill by this dissertation.

In alignment with the previous chapters, the outcome of this study will be presented in the following order: findings from the SMEs, findings from the SME Credit Institutes, and findings from the SME Skill Development and Advisory Institutes. Finally, a comparative study between Ghana and Mauritius will help shape Ghana's proposed policy guide. Strategic recommendations will accompany all the above.

6.1 THE SMEs- DEMAND SIDE

6.1.1 Diagnostic Analysis of SMEs in the Wa Municipality

6.1.1.1 Application of SWOT Analysis to SMEs

Conducting enquiries on the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats is common among business researchers in prominent industries. Most firms apply SWOT analysis when planning strategically. SWOT analysis is essential in developing regulations and policies for governments as it serves as a quality control tool (GURL, 2017). This study's SWOT analysis

focuses on the business management challenges facing the SME industry in the Wa Municipality of Ghana. Table 6.1 below shows the SME industry's SWOT analysis in Wa Municipality.

Table 6-1: SWOT Analysis of the SMEs industry

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
Well-known industry	Poor SMEs management skills
Large customer base	10.4% of SMEs do not have staff with any formal education (see section 4.4.1.5)
Highly educated staff (39.8% tertiary & 37.7% secondary (See section 4.4.1.5)	Only 38.2% do have business plans (see Figure 4.2)
High commitment towards professional development (94% see Table 4.1)	Low profit between (10 and 20) % among the majority (45.1%) of SMEs (See section 4.4.1.10)
The high educational level of an SME management team member leads to an increase in profit (See Tables 5.19 and 5.20)	Lack of well-equipped SMEs training centres
53.7% practice bookkeeping (section 4.4.1.9) which leads to higher profits (See Tables 5.15 and 5.16)	33.6% do not practice any form of bookkeeping (see section 4.4.1.9)
OPPORTUNITY	THREATS
Opportunity to align with other economies and compete globally	Existing SMEs in competing economies
Opportunity to create employment and contribute to GDP	Political Interference
Taking advantage of the AfCFTA	Global economic crisis

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From Table 6.1 above, the SME industry must tackle its weaknesses and threats with all seriousness whilst exploring its opportunities to the maximum.

6.1.2 Recommendations based on the WEAKNESSES revealed by the SWOT analysis

WEAKNESSES are the internal factors SMEs face within the industry, as illustrated in Table 6.1 above. The following are proposed solutions that are capable of dissolving the above-identified WEAKNESSES:

- A nationally recognised SME training (with well-equipped training centres) should be introduced across the country and be made a compulsory requirement for SME credit accessibility and SME ownership (to be discussed in detail later in the thesis).
- The concept of night schools (Adult Education) should be encouraged to enable SME owners without formal education to study and acquire the needed qualifications for their business development. The above is vital because Tables 5.19 and 5.20 from chapter five (5) do suggest that the educational level of an SME management team member can influence its profit margin.
- Continuous Professional Development and the Practice of bookkeeping should be encouraged across Ghana to help address the problem of low profitability among most SMEs. Tables 5.13 and 5.14 from chapter five (5) also attest that SMEs that give their staff Continuous Professional Development are more likely to practice standard bookkeeping. Importantly, Tables 5.15 and 5.16 from chapter five (5) discovered that SMEs practising standard bookkeeping are likelier to make enormous profits.

The above points will help solve the human resource challenges facing SMEs, as highlighted in the literature review in chapter two (see section 2.7.7)

6.1.3 Recommendations based on the THREATS revealed by the SWOT analysis

THREATS are the external factors identified to be negatively affecting the SME industry. They could be influences outside the SME industry but within Ghana (e.g., Political interference/instability-see section 2.7.5 of the literature review). Alternatively, occurrences outside of the country that has a more significant impact on the Ghanaian SMEs industry (e.g. global economic crises). Below are suggestions to tackle the above-listed THREATS:

6.1.3.1 Existing SMEs in Competing Economies

Government should form strategic alliances with countries that produce similar products like the Ghanaian SMEs industry. The above will help consolidate the efforts of both economies to create a bigger and stronger market capable of dictating product prices on the international market. For example, Ghana and Ivory Coast could be allies as the leading cocoa-producing economies. If the world knows that all cocoa-producing economies are speaking with one voice, it puts the producers in a better position to meet their price demands. The same can be done for all other products produced by SMEs.

6.1.3.2 Political Interference

This internal THREAT can be damaging because of the 'winner takes all' type of democracy Ghana practices. Elected governments control everything in the country and can easily overturn the policies of previous governments, no matter how good they may be to the economy. Given the above, there is a need for a multi-party approach when taking macroeconomic decisions that are likely to span over two or more political regimes. The above would see all parties commit to the same agenda when power changes hands.

6.1.3.3 Global Economic Crisis

Economic crises can be within a country, like the Ghanaian Banking Crisis in 2017 (Duho, 2019) or with a global effect, like the stock market crash in 1987 and the 2007/8 global economic crisis (Abubakar, 2019). Nonetheless, any of the above gravely affects the performance of SMEs. Meanwhile, the solutions to the above scenarios lie mainly in the hands of the ruling governments of the affected economies. Although economic crises are inevitable, according to this study, their solutions can be classified as short-term and long-term.

6.1.3.3.1 Short-Term Solutions-Quantitative Easing:

6.1.3.3.1.1 The *Hoover* Model

No government is happy with the economic crisis during their tenure and sees such occurrences as bad omens (Chwieroth and Walter, 2010) to their political fortunes because of its advert effect on the macroeconomy. Most democracies practice capitalism (trading forex and operating financial markets), business models that can easily trigger a financial crisis. The fear of losing political power (Achen and Bartels, 2004) leads to the introduction of 'romantic' economic measures that are primarily short-term and leave the crisis a good chance of reoccurring sooner than anticipated. During the 1987 Stock Market Crash, the US Federal Reserve made a supposed 'romantic' move to please SME owners by easing monetary policy and reassuring banks of their commitment to reviving the affected businesses. Money was made available to the banks while interest rates dropped by 1% (National Council on Economic Education's Learning, Earning, and Investing – High School publication). The above scenario creates a crisis loop (*Hoover Model*) with; Democracy, Capitalism, Financial Crises and Quantitative Easing as the coordinates (Abubakar, 2019).

The 'Hoover of financial regulations' presented below is the sole creation of the author of this study and was first published in *The Academia* in 2019:

Figure 6-1: The Hoover of Financial Regulation

Source: Author's creation first published in *The Academia*, 2019

Figure 6.1 above is the Hoover of financial regulations. Ruling governments often fall on the above loop. The loop is used to 'hoover' all stricter financial regulations and reforms meant to curb further crises for a considerably longer term but might come with immediate to medium-term hardships on SMEs. The haven for most governments in the above situation is Quantitative Easing. Q E is the easiest way of allaying the fears of governments becoming unpopular among business owners (Achen and Bartels, 2004) and eventually losing political power (Anderson, 2000; Lewis-Beck, 1988).

6.1.3.3.2 Long Term Solutions-Major Regulatory and Supervisory Reforms

The Ghanaian banking sector (48.8% SME credit provider; see Table 4.5), one of the primary financiers of SMEs, was hit hard with significant reforms and regulations in 2018. The above was necessitated by corporate governance failure (Torku and Laryea, 2021) and creative accounting (Aboagye, 2020), leading to a crash in the Banking Sector. Instead of resulting in the usual Quantitative Easing as discussed above, the government took the stricter decision of introducing major regulatory and supervisory reforms. The above resulted in the collapse of

nine (9) well-known banks, some merged and consolidated (Duho, 2019). Nonetheless, the reforms meant to secure the Ghanaian financial sector for a considerably longer term came with a cost of \$ 2.1 billion (Oxford Business Group), which many critics did not appreciate. Moreover, the reforms have left a chunk of SMEs struggling to access finance as the collapsed banks were their primary sources of credit. It is hoped that, shortly, the reforms will help stabilise the macro-economy of Ghana.

6.1.4 Recommendations on how to maximise the OPPORTUNITIES by the SWOT analysis

Opportunities are the external factors that could help increase the strengths of SMEs when adequately explored. The following are the elaborations on how the identified OPPORTUNITIES could help develop the SMEs industry in Ghana:

6.1.4.1 Opportunity to align with other economies and compete globally:

This has already been discussed in section 6.1.3.1 above

6.1.4.2 Opportunity to create employment and contribute to GDP

In Ghana, the main source of employment is the SME industry (see section 2.2.5 of the literature review), as they form the majority of businesses in the country. Chapter two (Literature review) of this study reported that SME-related jobs amount to 74.63% of all the jobs in the country (see Table 2.3). The above percentage amounts to 2,524,953 out of 3,383,206 filled vacancies throughout Ghana (IBES Summary Report, 2015, p41). Interestingly, the above milestone is achieved without a proper SMEs Policy Guide. According to the 2021 Population and Housing Census, Ghana has a labour force of 11,541,355. Some 9,990,237 are employed, whilst 1,551,118 are unemployed. Ghana's current rate of unemployment = (unemployed/labour force) *100 = (1,551,118/11,541,355) *100 = 13.4%.

Figure 6.2 below is a loop explaining the current employment state of the SME industry without a Policy Guide.

Figure 6-2: Employment by SMEs in Ghana without a Policy Guide

Source: Author's creation

From Figure 6.2 above, the industry currently revolves between SMEs, Credit Institutions and Technical/Advisory Institutions with a missing middle. The missing piece in the middle is government regulations (Policy) to govern the proper conduct of the above institutions. It is envisaged that with proper policy guidelines, there would be a free flow of credit and services between these institutions that would eventually translate into jobs and contributions to GDP.

Government intervention through the policy guide would ensure that risk is absorbed, allowing the credit institutes to lend money to the SMEs without the usual hustle. Nevertheless, before an SME can access a government intervened credit, the managers of that SME must have obtained a nationally recognised certificate of training from a government-recognised Business Advisory Centre (The Proposed Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development and Financing

Authority (GERDFA)-to be discussed later). The above guarantees that the managers of the SMEs in need of government-intervened credit have the capacity to properly manage the credit acquired to avoid causing any financial loss to the state. As a corporate social responsibility, the financial institutions should contribute financially (3% of their profit) to the development of the training centres, as they stand to benefit from their successful operations.

6.1.4.2.1 Further Employment Creation

With all the above interventions in place, and with SMEs fully embracing the Service/Product Lifecycle Model (see 6.2.1 below), Ghana could easily set a 10% increment target (within three years) on job creation by ensuring a proper transitioning of the SMEs from Micro to Small, Medium and Large. The above is achievable with proper commitment and systems in place. According to section 2.2.5 and figure 2.3 (Literature review) of this study, 1,137,611 jobs can be created annually through this proposal. With the above number of jobs created periodically, the 1,551,118 unemployed Ghanaians (see section 6.2.4.2) could soon find something doing, and unemployment in Ghana would have been resolved. Figure 6.3 below shows a 10% proposed increment on the current 74.6% of jobs created by SMEs, translating into 82.09% with the introduction of a comprehensive Policy Guide for the smooth operation of SMEs.

Figure 6-3: Employment by SMEs in Ghana with the proposed Policy Guide

Source: Author's creation.

6.1.4.3 Taking Advantage of the AfCFTA

Ghana hosts the headquarters of the historic Africa Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA), which makes Ghana a regional trade hub and epic economic centre (Kyeremanten, 2019). With a market size of \$ 3 trillion, the AfCFTA is envisaged to favour SMEs, which form 80% of businesses on the continent and significantly contribute to GDP. Specifically, SMEs are expected to benefit from eliminated trade barriers and the introduction of macroeconomic policies that lessen the burdens on imports and exports in the sub-region. Furthermore, lower tariffs and easy and free access to market information are among some benefits SMEs would gain from the agreement (Akeyewale, 2018).

6.2 THE LIFECYCLE OF SMES IN THE WA MUNICIPALITY

Nkuah et al. (2013), as discussed in this study's literature review, documented that most SMEs fold up because of mismanagement (Literature review- section 2.7.1). Through its first specific

objective (section 1.4.2), this study seeks to address the management challenges facing SMEs by introducing the Service/Product Lifecycle Model. The lifecycle of every business largely depends on the type of products or services it sends out to the consumer. The above makes the product's lifecycle critical for the survival of every business. There is an exciting revelation in the Wa Municipality, where 94.4% of SMEs operate beyond their second year of existence, with 22.4% (see Table 4.2) of them already gone past ten years of operation. The above SMEs are noticed for producing different products and services.

Although 82.9% of SMEs in the Wa Municipality are classified as sole proprietors, empirical evidence from this study (see Tables 5.5 and 5.6) suggests that the legal status (type) of SMEs does not affect the lifespan of SMEs. However, Tables 5.7 and 5.8 reveal that the lifespan of SMEs depends on their classification. Small and Medium SMEs mainly were above five years, whilst the Micro SMEs were typically below five years of existence.

6.2.1 Service/Product Lifecycle Model

The model anticipates the universal trends likely to be followed by the market's most popular services/products. Because no service/product is everlasting, it is critical to pinpoint where the service/product of an SME would be in their product life cycle. It is equally important not to introduce tomorrow's product for today's market. The product lifecycle for SMEs comes in four stages, as shown in Figure 6.4 below:

Figure 6-4: Service/Product Lifecycle

Source: Business Set Free Ltd 2013

Figure 6.1 above is the service/product lifecycle, a sales graph against time. From the above graph, sales increase or decrease concerning time. The product lifecycle graph comprises four stages: Introduction, Growth, Maturity and Decline.

To begin with, in the 'Introductory' stages of every business, the model predicts an initial loss due to the high initial cost of bringing the business on board and low sales because it is still new on the market.

Also, at the 'Growth' stage, the product mostly gets accepted on the market. Sales increase as a result, and the cost of production per unit drops because of the economics of scale. At this point, break-even is achieved, followed by possible profit-making.

Moreover, there is a higher demand for the service/product at the Maturity stage, culminating in more profit. Significantly, production costs drop further because of the availability of qualified and efficient staff. The above is consistent with empirical research evidence; the right staff are recruited as SMEs grow from Micro to Small and Medium Enterprises. Tables 5.9 and 5.10 show that Smaller (93.1%) and Medium (60%) SMEs operate with adequate and qualified staff. On the same Table, only 40.3% of Micro SMEs operate with adequate and qualified staff.

Lastly, competition is introduced at the Decline stage because of businesses' profit margins at the 'Maturity' stage. Similar products and services are introduced, leading to a reduction in sales and hence a decline in profit, and where care is not taken, the business folds up.

6.2.2 Recommendations Based on the Product Lifecycle Model

Although the product lifecycle does not auspicate future sales, it determines a product's contribution to an SME's profit and how well a product has performed over time. For SMEs to stay in business and make a profit, they should introduce multiple products and ensure a timely transition of the products through the stages of the product lifecycle as discussed below:

6.2.2.1 Multiple Products

Creativity and innovation are critical in introducing multiple products and creating a run for the products through the various cycle of the model. The above will ensure a different product at each stage of the product cycle. As a product moves from 'introduction' to 'maturity' and the 'decline' stages, another product follows in that direction. The above will prevent a situation where the business would not be making enough income because all its products are in the 'decline' state, hence not making enough sales due to competition. Similarly, if a business has all its products in the introductory stage, it would require more spending to onboard them onto the market and with lower sales because they are not favoured to sell fast. Therefore, keeping a balance with products is vital in staying in business and ensuring the business stays liquid.

6.2.2.2 Stage Timing of Products

After ensuring multiple services/products, the primary aim is to move them as fast as possible through the stages. The 'Introductory' and 'Growth' stages into the money-making zone (Maturity), where the business can make as much money as possible. Otherwise, the trooping in of competitors would eventually push the product to the 'Decline' stage. Whilst at the 'Decline' stage, it is essential to face the product to avoid loss as soon as it is confirmed that it cannot be revived.

6.2.3 Increasing SMEs Profitability Through Product Management

6.2.3.1 Ansoff Matrix

The rationale behind every business is to maximise profit and minimise cost. However, according to the literature reviewed in chapter two of this study (section 2.6), Ghanaian businesses struggle to make profits. Profit-making has been challenging due to the high cost of inputs and the lack of markets and equipment (Amegashie-Vaglo and Bokoe, 2014). This thesis provides a remedy to the above challenge by introducing the Ansoff Matrix to Ghanaian SMEs.

The matrix is a two-by-two representation of the possibilities available to SMEs looking to increase revenue or profitability. Igor Ansoff first described the matrix in his book 'Strategies for Diversification (Harvard Business Review, September-October 1957, p. 114). The matrix is helpful since it gives a concise framework incorporating an organisation's strategic directions in one analytical instrument.

6.2.3.2 Application of Ansoff Matrix to SMEs

The matrix's dimensions focus on the most crucial connection the SME industry must manage: providing customer products. Products can be tangible or intangible and can be offered for sale in exchange for money or as a form of societal benefit. In the latter situation, monetary gifts or collaboration will be exchanged. In either case, the product will be an existing offering or pioneering to the SMEs involved. Customers, accordingly, will either be members of an existing market or members of a market that the SMEs have not yet addressed and are thus unfamiliar to them (Meldrum and McDonald, 1995).

As a result, the SMEs industry has four options for action:

- Focusing on existing products for existing markets.
- Finding new products to sell in existing markets.
- Identifying new markets for current products.
- Expanding into new markets with new products.

Table 6.2 below is a matrix of markets against products regarding the above-listed 'four (4) options for action'.

Table 6-2: The Ansoff Matrix illustration of the SMEs industry in Ghana

		Product	
Market	Existing	Existing	New
		Market Penetration	New Products and services
		The Ghanaian SMEs sector aggressively strives to position itself and take advantage of the AfCFTA. SMEs are more engaged now because of the opportunities they can enjoy as SMEs in a country that hosts the headquarters of the AfCFTA. The introduction of the AfCFTA will help SMEs freely penetrate other markets in the sub-region.	SMEs continuously produce to sustain the economy is a plus for the industry. Although there is still a lot to be done, successive governments have done a lot to ensure SMEs become innovative and productive enough to compete globally. Eg.1D1F and the one region, one industrial park. (Kyeremanten, 2019) The above and many more can help SMEs increase their customer base.
	Market Development	Diversification	
	New	With the existing colossal market potential in the SME industry (\$ 3 trillion), according to Akeyewale (2018), introducing the African Continental Free Trade Agreement is timely and will help the industry access the Opportunity among many more.	Over 53 economies came together to sign the AfCFTA agreement. The above undoubtedly comes with a massive human, tangible and intangible resource pool for SMEs to tap and compete appropriately (Kyeremanten, 2018).

Source: Meldrum and McDonald, (1995).

From Table 6 above, the SME industry is poised to take advantage of the AfCFTA with its uniquely broader market platform and size. Revenues are expected to rise with a corresponding increase in market shares. More so, it is anticipated that more resources (investors) would come to SMEs through the inflow of foreign direct investors to Ghana as the headquarters of the AfCFTA. SMEs are therefore expected to turn that into good use by networking and partnering

with investors to produce competitively to penetrate the international markets and ultimately record higher profits.

6.3 THE FINANCIERS OF SMEs – (CREDIT INSTITUTES)

6.3.1 Sources of Credit for SMEs

The leading SME credit providers in the Wa Municipality are commercial banks (48.8%). The Microfinance Institutes (33.9%), The promising, Microenterprises and start-up friendly Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA) (13.2%) and MASLOC (4.1%) (see Table 4.5).

6.3.1.1 Commercial Banks

Per the literature reviewed in chapter two, the high-interest rate has been cited as a significant constraint to SME development (see section 2.6.1). Moreover, the data collected by this study revealed that Ghana houses about 23 commercial banks, of which only ten (10) operate in the Wa Municipality, with an average lending rate of 25.05% (BoG, 2021). Known for their primary purposes of credit provision, Commercial Banks have struggled to maintain and increase their credit-customer base from the SME sector because of the difficulty in managing credit risk (Boahene et al., 2012). Although Commercial Banks remain the major credit providers to SMEs in the Wa Municipality, 13.4% and 67.9% of the sampled SMEs for this study documented that they find lending rates high and highly high, respectively. Because of the above, 43.4% of the SMEs that ever went in for bank credit admitted encountering difficulties repaying their credit. However, Tables 5.21 and 5.22 empirically suggest that bank credit, among others, does not affect SMEs' lifespan. Nonetheless, Tables 5.23 and 5.24 reveal that credit borrowing could partially affect the profit margins of SMEs. Table 6.1 below shows the average lending rates of the universal banks in the Wa Municipality as of 31st July 2021.

Table 6-3: Average lending rates of universal banks compiled by Bank of Ghana, July 2021.

Source: Bank of Ghana, July 2021.

From Table 6.1 above, Agricultural Development Bank has the highest lending rate of 24.89%, making it practically difficult for most SMEs to borrow and honour their credit obligations. Bank of Africa Ghana Limited has the lowest lending rate of 17.19%, which is still considered relatively high for most SMEs to service their debts and grow as expected. There is significant scholarly evidence suggesting banks have a more robust credit risk management system in place. However, any attempt to implement the above suggestions would only maximise the banks' profits (Boahene et al., 2012) and add up to the already daunting rules the SMEs have to deal with in accessing credit. This thesis suggests a government intervention in credit risk management that will benefit SMEs and banks profitably. Given that lending rates are affected by policy rate, inflation, exchange rate, treasury bill rate, bank size and GDP (Adoah, 2015), the government should implement a deliberate policy that allows for the reduction in the lending rates across the country.

6.3.1.2 Microfinance Institutes

Microfinance Institutes are semi-formal and serve the populace that cannot access formal Financial Institutes (Boateng, 2015). They make up 33.9% of sampled respondents of this survey and are the second largest provider of credit to SMEs in the Wa Municipality. Like the banks, the Microfinance Institutes have failed to address the credit needs of SMEs due to higher

lending rates and stringent bureaucracies before they lend credit to SMEs. A governmental intervention to mitigate the risk and allow easy credit accessibility is paramount.

Table 6-4: Average lending rates of Microfinance Institutes in Wa Municipal

No	Name of Microfinance Institute	Lending rate%
1	Ultra-Savings and Loans	29
2	Wa Workers Credit Union	19.5
3	Teachers Credit Union	
4	Snapi Aba Trust	
5	Sungbawiara Susu and Loans	
6	Rawas Susu Loans	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From Table 6.4 above, most Microfinance Institutes have refused to state the official lending rates they charge on credit to SMEs.

6.3.1.3 Microfinance and Small Loans Centre (MASLOC)

MASLOC is the official Microfinance Institute for the Government of Ghana. It was formed in 2006 to help bridge the gap in credit accessibility among SMEs whilst reducing poverty and creating jobs and wealth. Whilst there is evidence of the positive impact of MASLOC on its beneficiaries (Philomina et al., 2012), much more evidence points to the politicisation and discrimination against women (Naami, 2017) when granting loans. MASLOC provides 4.1% credit to the sampled respondents for this study and charges 2% as lending rates. Unfortunately, only one active MASLOC office serves all the districts in the Upper West Region, including the Wa Municipality. Government should ensure a proper decentralisation of MASLOC across the country through GERDFA and ensure women and the youth are particularly favoured in credit accessibility.

6.3.1.4 Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLA)

A VSLA is a Savings and Credit Association built solely on continuous savings and requires no external donations or borrowing to the primary loan portfolio. It shies away from all the bureaucracies that a formal Microfinance Institute employs. VSLAs are more user-friendly to

the micro-enterprises, the uneducated and rural folks who would otherwise be unable to access formal credit from a regular Credit Provider. With a VSLA, there is no limit to savings redraw, and loans come in variable terms, lower interest rates and friendly payment methods (Brannen, 2010).

There are enormous success stories from the VSLAs in the Upper West Region of Ghana, where Wa Municipal is the capital. One such is the Greater Rural Opportunities for Women (GROW) project, financed by Global Affairs Canada and implemented by Mennonite Economic Development Associates (MEDA) in 2017 with the help of some local partners.

The project identified and supported 21,500 women farmer entrepreneurs to improve food security among their families. Thirteen thousand six hundred forty-three (13,633) hectares of soybeans were cultivated, which yielded 14 632 metric tons with combined revenue of GHC 22.3 million, approximately GBP 3.7 million from their harvest sales.

6.3.1.4.1 The GROW VSLA Model

With the help of Key Programme Facilitators (KPIs), women groups of 15 to 30 are formed. Members, by default, make a weekly contribution of GHC 5-10 (approximately £1.0), which is accumulated and serves as a credit facility for any member who wants to borrow. Additionally, members could opt for an informal insurance package of just GHC 1.0 a week and redeemable in case of contingencies like funerals and sicknesses.

6.3.1.4.2 Hybrid financial model

Typically, VSLAs save money in a box because they are popularly called 'small box' groups in the local dialect (daka bille). However, the GROW project identified and worked with some rural Microfinance Institutes (MFIs) in their operational areas. They encouraged the VSLAs to be safe with the MFIs for the mutual benefit of accessing more credit as their savings could

serve as a deposit, whilst the MFIs also expand their customer base through onboarding the VSLAs.

Figure 6-5: Proposed hybrid SMEs banking framework

The terms and conditions for a VSLA loan are much friendlier than any other sources, as rules are collectively determined in the members' best interest. The above has made VSLAs popular among low-income earners and start-up primary women in rural communities. Whilst the MFIs charge 3% interest on loans, VSLAs only charge 1% on their membership loans. A member can only access a maximum of three times their savings as a loan. Interestingly, the accumulated interest is shared among all members at the end of a chosen cycle or financial year.

Although the GROW project is typically for women farmers, it can be replicated in other business sectors in the SME industry. The VSLA concept could be helpful among rural folks and start-ups who could not access traditional loans. The GROW project shows that 24% of the VSLAs upgraded from keeping money in a secured box to depositing it in a formal bank account. Moreover, some members (41%) from the VSLAs groups went ahead to open their bank accounts, and as their businesses grew, 6% accessed traditional loans through their deposits with MFIs.

6.4 THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CREDIT INSTITUTES (CIs) AND SMES

In section 2.8 of the literature review, credit accessibility challenges have been linked to the improper management practices exhibited by most SMEs (Nkuah et al., 2013). Moreover, SMEs and CIs have long shared a demand-and-supply relationship. The CIs are the suppliers

of funds and often perceive SMEs as not equipped enough to merit the supply of funds compared to the large corporations. Conversely, SMEs needing credit perceive the FIs as bureaucratic, demanding and protective of their products. For instance, 38.8% of SMEs in the Wa Municipality never applied for credit because of the *fear of default due to high lending rates* (refer to section 4.5.1.2). Bridging the gap between SMEs and CIs is crucial for job creation and economic growth. See section 6.8 for the recommended solutions for bridging the gap between SMEs and CIs.

6.5 THE PROVIDERS OF TECHNICAL SUPPORT TO SMES

6.5.1 Types of SME Advisory Services

One of the four identified SMEs Advisory Institutes in the Municipality is the Ghana Enterprise Agency (GEA), formerly the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI), formed in 1985 to provide Business Development Services and Financial Support to SMEs on behalf of the government of Ghana. Operating in 190 districts across Ghana, the GEA has successfully formalised 2,825 MSMEs and disbursed GHC 200m (£23m). They currently deal with 28,245 clients across the country (gea.gov.gh).

6.6 THE GOVERNMENT, COVID-19 AND SMES

Governments in most nations have taken two crucial roles during the COVID-19 pandemic. First, to stop the disease from spreading and to help small businesses (SMEs) improve their operations. In Ghana, Soft loans, guarantee support, and statutory payment interventions were the three most successful government interventions in speeding up SMEs' operations post-covid-19 (Tuffour et al., 2021). Most SMEs were affected to various degrees, whilst others

made some fortunes due to the covid-19 pandemic. Tables 6.5 and 6.6 below show how Covid-19 affected some Stakeholders and their perception post-covid-19, respectively.

Table 6-5: Effect of Covid-19 on some Stakeholders in the SMEs industry

STAKEHOLDERS	Negatively %	Positively %	No Impact %
SMEs	85.5	0.7	13.4
Credit Institutes	100		
Skill & Advisory Institutes	100		

Source: Field Survey, 2021 (refer to section 4.6)

Table 6-6: perception of SMEs Stakeholders post covid-19

STAKEHOLDERS	Fully Operating	Partly Operating	Closed
SMEs	44.4	33.2	4.9
Credit Institutes	88.9	11.1	
Skill & Advisory Institutes	100		

Source: Field Survey, 2021(refer to section 4.6)

6.6.1 The 'Mandala' Analysis of the Ghanaian SMEs Industry

Mandala, a product of the Sanskrit language, is mainly patronised by Hindus and Buddhists as a religious symbol representing the integrated organisational structure of life (Ancient-symbols.com). Overall, the Mandala demonstrates that no circumstance is perfect.

Looking at the covid-19 crisis with a “Mandala lens”, it can be seen that they were not all negative omens, as we are led to believe. SMEs could learn valuable lessons or, better still, take advantage of the circumstances to make good financial selections. From Table 6.5 above, 0.7% of SMEs reported that the pandemic was a blessing in disguise to them as they made fortunes. Another, 13.4%, documented that Covid-19 did not impact their operations. Even the Credit Institutes and Skill & Advisory Institutes, who purported to be 100% affected by Covid-19, also stated that they would be fully operational after the Covid endemic (See Table 6.6).

Moreover, the covid-19 pandemic has helped in restructuring most economies. Fig 6.6 below is the Mandala symbol illustrating the good and bad of the Covid-19 Pandemic crisis.

Figure 6-6: Yin and Yang's Mandala Symbol

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.
Please contact the author for further information.

Source: PNG Library

From the figure above, the dark side with a small white spot on the right-hand side depicts that, although the Covid-19 crisis did cause monumental destruction, there was little room for positivity (represented by the little white spot). Conversely, the white side with a black spot explains that when the SMEs were doing well without the Covid-19 crisis, one could still trace some elements of doom (depicted by the black spot). These small losses could be explained as the daily losses some SMEs encountered due to mismanagement, high-interest rates, and lack of a ready market. In all, no condition is permanent; SMEs are encouraged to quickly adapt to new changes and forge on instead of giving up.

6.7 PROPOSED STRATEGIC CHANGE FOR SMES MANAGEMENT AND CREDIT ACCESSIBILITY

The SMEs sector has vast potential and can transform the economy of Ghana through job creation and contributing to GDP. Nonetheless, the current state of affairs does not help bring out the best in the SME industry. Because of the above, the following strategic directions have been proposed to be implemented by the Government of Ghana

Figure 6-7: A proposed strategic framework for SMEs Management and Credit Accessibility

6.7.1 Merging RGD, MASLOC & GEA

Among the most common challenges SMEs face is the duplication of services by the service providers. The Registrar General Department (RGD), Microfinance and Small Loans Centres (MASLOC) and The Ghana Enterprise Agency (GEA) are all Governmental Agencies responsible for SMEs' registration and technical and financial support across the country. The RGD, regrettably, is underrepresented (present in 4 out of the 16 regions). MASLOC has offices in 10 of the 16 regions, and GEA is represented highly in all 16 regions and beyond (190 out of the 216 districts in Ghana). All the above agencies play a duplicated role in business registration – a role that the RGD should only carry out. Also, as MASLOC and GEA both render technical and financial services to SMEs, MASLOC specialises in SME financing, and GEA is focused on SMEs' technical development. Teaming the agencies together will reduce duplication of services and create a more robust and one-stop governmental agency for SMEs. Moreover, a merger would mean that the RGD, GEA and MASLOC are represented in 190 districts across Ghana. The merged agencies should be backed by a legislative Instrument and upgraded into an authority to function appropriately. Hence, the proposed new name for the merged agencies should be Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development and Financing Authority (GERDFA).

6.7.1.1 Cost and Benefits

- GERDFA, when operationalised, will significantly reduce the administrative cost of servicing three different agencies and their CEOs to just 1.

- The presence of GERDFA will immediately be felt in at least 190 districts of the country after the merger.
- SMEs will significantly benefit from the capacity building and credit accessibility benefits that GERDFA offers.

6.7.2 National SMEs Training and Certification

In the literature reviewed in Chapter 2 of this study, SMEs are bedevilled by severe management constraints (Nkuah et al., 2013). Proactively, the first specific objective of this thesis is to address the management challenges SMEs face. Moreover, Inadequate resources have been a significant setback facing most government agencies (Nyaaba et al., 2018). The efficient use of limited resources is paramount in national development. Because of the above, this study proposes a nationally recognised SME training with a certificate to be issued by the proposed Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development and Financing Authority (GERDFA). All GERDFA offices nationwide should include well-equipped training centres to facilitate nationally recognised training content (refer to section 4.4.2.10). The content should be uniform across all centres and available in local dialects to benefit those unfamiliar with English. The above is necessary because Ghana is a multi-ethnic country, where most SME owners and their customers trade in the various local dialects. Moreover, training in the local dialects would attract more business owners and potential entrepreneurs with less or no formal education but who want some skills to venture into business.

The nationally recognised training certificate should be the primary requirement for accessing any form of credit in the country since it proves that an individual or SME has the basic skills to manage a credit portfolio. The above, if properly implemented, will equip SME staff with the required technical knowledge. Moreover, it will reduce credit default rates among businesses and reduce the risk level among small business owners. It would further position SMEs in a better position to attract credit from other sources.

6.7.2.1 Cost and Benefits

- SMEs owner/managers are to benefit from cost-free training sponsored by the government through GERDFA with a nationally recognised certificate.
- The proof of training (certificate) provided by GERDFA will be used as collateral for SME credit accessibility.

6.7.3 Publicity and Commitment

In the world of business, publicity is a catalyst for success. More so, pushing through a national strategy requires even more aggressive publicity whilst staying committed to the original plan. In a country like Ghana, where traditional media is still an essential part of most of the population, it is relevant to employ the services of all forms of media, information services and centres across the country. The above publicity should continue until GEDFA becomes a household name in the country.

6.7.3.1 Cost and Benefits

Although this might come at a cost to the media houses involved, the long-term benefits far outweigh the cost.

- More SMEs will be formalised and subsequently pay taxes to the state.
- Capacities of SMEs will be built and eventually leads to job creation.

6.7.4 Effectiveness and Usefulness of the Proposed Strategies

6.7.4.1 SAFe Criteria Model

After successfully formulating the above strategies, it has become eminent to choose a criterion to assess the effectiveness and usefulness of the strategies. Because of the above, this study has cross-checked the Suitability, Acceptability and Feasibility (SAF) of the above-formulated

strategies (Ansoff et al., 2018). The SAF strategy model is necessary; as Wu (2010) documented, SAF must be the benchmark for every strategy.

Table 6-7: Applying the SAF criteria to the proposed strategies

STRATEGY	SUITABLE?	ACCEPTABLE?	FEASIBLE?
Merging RGD, GEA & MASLOC	Yes	Yes	Yes
National SMEs Training and Certification	Yes	Yes	No
Publicity and Commitment	Yes	Yes	Yes

Source: Author's creation

Table 6.3 above applies the SAF criteria to the proposed strategies for SME management and credit accessibility.

Strategy 1: Merging the RDG, GEA & MASLOC is SuiTable because it overcomes the long-existed problem of duplication and incoordination of services. Acceptability of the strategy would not be a problem as all agencies are for the government, and hence the usual resistance arising from mergers involving different owners would not exist in this case. Moreover, the merger is cost-effective as it will reduce the costs of maintaining three agencies into just one authority. Lastly, the merger is Feasible as the government would be the sole stakeholder in charge. The government has to pool all the needed resources to facilitate the merger.

Strategy 2: National SMEs Training and Certification is Suitable because it directly solves SMEs' managerial and credit accessibility challenges. Strikingly, the above challenges form the first two objectives of this study. The Acceptability of this strategy has been confirmed by section 4.3.1.11 of the study, where 94% of SMEs from the survey indicated they would welcome a well-structured training centre capable of training SMEs staff in both English and the local dialects. Interestingly, 95.2% (see section 4.3.1.12) pledged their willingness to pay a token for the above-stated training. However, the second strategy is not feasible due to

inadequately qualified staff, office impress, well-equipped training centres and material resources. Nonetheless, the above is possible with the proper prioritisation from the government.

Strategy 3: Publicity and Commitment. A common complaint is that most SME owners do not know about the existence of RGD, GEA and MASLOC (to be known as GERDFA). The above assertion makes strategy three very suitable in ensuring that all SMEs become aware of the newly proposed Ghana Enterprise Registration, Development and Financing Authority (GEDFA). The above strategy would be accepted as a government policy. The government could easily direct the National Commission for Civic Education (NCCE) and all government media houses to champion the publicity. Also, as corporate social responsibility, all private media outlets through the National Media Commission could be lobbied to devote a few minutes to the above national assignment. Lastly, strategy 3 is Feasible because the resource needed to implement the above strategy are available to the government. However, more concerted efforts, regulations and monitoring would be required to ensure the stakeholders stay committed to the above strategies.

6.7.5 Implementation of the Proposed Strategies

6.7.5.1 Kurt Lewin's Vs Kotter's 8 Models

With the strategies in place and explained above, it is time to effect a lasting change, and this is where Tanner (2018)'s proposal becomes handy. In his proposal, Tanner (2018) combined Kurt Lewin's model with Kotter's eight models to persuade the leadership of the need for an orderly change implementation process.

To begin with, all stakeholders in the SME industry would have to be convinced to support the proposed changes fully. Also, the government will lead the change implementation and must

be fully committed to the proposed strategic change above. Lastly, the effected change must be adopted as part of Tanner's organisational culture (2018).

6.7.5.2 Critical Analysis of Kurt Lewin's and Kotter's eight models

Although highly revered as a management change tool, Kurt Lewin's (unfreezing, changing and refreezing) method of change (also known as CATS) has received backlashes for its simplicity as well as recommendations for its robustness (Cummings, Bridgman, and Brown, 2016).

Despite Tanner (2018) describing Kurt Lewin's model as too fundamental in the modern-day work environment, Sonenshein (2010) documented that the CATS is the primary tool for change management. Schein (1988) referred to Kurt Lewin as 'the intellectual father of contemporary theories. Most interestingly, Kurt Lewin's change model has been viewed by academia as the summary of all change models (Hendry, 1996). 'The most powerful tool in my toolbox is Kurt Lewin's simple three-step change model' (Cummings, Bridgman, and Brown, 2016).

On Kotter's eight-change model, a group of CEOs purported that the framework is ideal for successfully implementing change while ensuring an organisation's perfect cultural mix. They, however, criticised the model for its lack of clear understanding in matters of further change implementation. They argued that the framework lacked "components in identifying and implementing a clear measure for estimating the effectiveness of change implemented" (Mira-Bohigas, 2021)

Figure 6.8 below illustrates how Kotter's eight change models explain Kurt Lewin's model of change.

Figure 6-8: KURT Lewin's vs Kotter's eight models of change

Kurt Lewin	John Kotter
<i>Unfreeze</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish a Sense of Urgency 2. Create the Guiding Coalition 3. Develop a Vision and Strategy 4. Communicate the Change Vision
<i>Change</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Empower Broad-Based Action 6. Generate Short Term Wins 7. Consolidate Gains & Make More Change
<i>Refreeze</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Anchor New Approaches in the Culture

Source: Tanner, 2017

From Table 8 above, Tanner (2018) explained the first step of Kurt Lewin's change management of Unfreezing with the first four steps of Kotter's model of change. Also, implementing the change as the second step of Kurt Lewin's model means empowering broad-based action, generating short-term wins, and consolidating gains that form the fifth, sixth, and seventh steps of Kotter's model. Finally, refreezing is explained by Kotter's anchoring of new approaches in the culture, according to Tanner (2018).

6.8 COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN GHANAIAN AND MAURITIAN SMEs

Mauritius was chosen for a comparative study with Ghana because it is the best business-friendly economy in Africa (Doing Business, 2020). Nonetheless, Mauritius strives to improve its macroeconomy by creating and implementing robust SME] Strategic Plans that are constantly updated. Moreover, 1992 is significant in the history of both countries. Ghana transitioned from military rule to becoming a democracy, whilst Mauritius became a republic, joining the commonwealth nations. Post-1992 gave both countries complete democratic control

over their economies, and it would be interesting to see how both fared in the last three decades with their macroeconomic drivers (SMEs).

6.8.1 Ghana's Draft SMEs Policy

6.8.1.1 overview

The Registrar General's Department remains Ghana's most recognised business registration body. Nonetheless, it is woefully underrepresented (in just 4 out of the 16 administrative regions). The above situation largely contributes to the so many unregistered businesses in the country. Insofar as it can be ascertained, 90% of the registered businesses with the Registrar General Department are SMEs (Ministry of Trade and Industry, 2019). Identified as the sole agent for holistic growth and the transformational agenda, the Government of Ghana (GoG) has shown some strides towards developing SMEs. However, the agenda to champion job creation and economic empowerment of the Ghanaian populace through SMEs is highly impacted because Ghana has no comprehensive SME Policy. Stakeholders in the SME sector rely on regulations captured under sections of other government policies.

Characteristically, SMEs in Ghana are not tagged with a particular business category. They cut across all employment sectors, from manufacturing to services—nonetheless, the urban and peri-urban parts of the country house most SMEs in the service sector. The rural areas typically have SMEs that are into manufacturing. SMEs in Ghana provide 14% more employment than the global average of 67% and contribute 18% more to GDP than the 52% global average (D'imperio, 2012).

6.8.1.2 Institutional Framework

Institutionally, the GoG established the NBSSI in 1985, now the GEA, to champion the development of SMEs. The 1990s saw the birth of the Cottage Industries and Rural Housing Department and the Ghana Enterprise Development Corporation. In 2005, MASLOC was

added to the list of government agencies that target the development of SMEs. However, these organisations have struggled to achieve their mandates on SME development across the country, primarily due to inadequate funding and resources. These agencies are not adequately decentralised and hence, only active in the urban areas, where they were mostly criticised as being politically biased in the discharge of their mandate. Also, the past 1.5 decades saw the influx of more uncoordinated, fragmented and poorly structured SME-focused agencies and programmes across both private and government sectors. The above agencies also face resource limitations and funding crises and are primarily unable to discharge their duties as scheduled.

6.8.1.3 Regulatory Framework

Legally, starting a business in Ghana takes eight procedures in 13 days and 12.3% of income per capita. These regulations and the bureaucratic and centralised nature of the institutions have burdened most SMEs and discouraged some people from wanting to start a business, especially in rural areas. Table 6.8 below compares Ghana to the sub-regional average for starting a business.

Table 6-8: Starting a Business in Ghana

	Ghana	Sub Saharan Africa	OECD High Income	Best Regulatory Performance
Procedure(number)	8	7.4	4.9	1
Time (days)	13	21.5	9.2	0.5
Cost (% of income per capita)	12.3	36.3	3.0	0

Source: Doing Business, 2020

From Table 6.8 above, it takes just a procedure in a half-day at no cost to start a business in the best regulatory country. Meanwhile, registering a business in Ghana takes eight procedures in 13 days at 12.3% of income per capita. Also, it takes 4.9 procedures in 9.2 days for 3% of income per capita to start a business in an OECD High-Income country. Lastly, starting a business in the sub-region takes an average of 7.4 procedures in 21.5 days at 36.3% of income

per capita. The above perhaps has contributed to why many SMEs are undocumented in Ghana (2010 population and housing census).

6.8.1.4 Strategic Direction

Strategically, Ghana's drafted SMEs Policy document seeks to address the following identified challenges (on the left of Table 6.9). The identified thematic areas on the right-hand side of the Table will potentially dissolve the challenges identified through the strategic directions. Each point has a detailed policy context, objectives, and prescriptions backed by the government's will.

Table 6-9: Strategic directions and thematic areas

Strategic Direction	Thematic Areas
Feeble Legal and Regulatory Framework	Enabling Environment: Institutional, Legal and Regulatory Framework
Finance Accessibility Difficulty	Financing for MSMEs Local Economic Development
Infrastructural deficit	Technology, Innovation, Research and Development
Institutional duplications	Cross-cutting issues
Access to Skill and Advisory Services	Entrepreneurship Development Business Development Services
Inability to access market intelligence	Market Facilitation

Source: Ghana SMEs Draft Policy

1.0

6.8.1.5 Implementation arrangements

The draft policy document is yet to be backed by an action plan and budgetary requirements for its implementation. A single coordinating body has been proposed as the primary governing structure. There are also plans for comprehensive communication alongside monitoring and evaluation strategies.

6.9 Ten-Year Master Plan for The SMEs Sector in Mauritius

6.9.1 Overview

The Macroeconomic policies of Mauritius have proven to be outstanding in Africa over the last few decades. They have consistently topped the business index by the world bank in Africa for some time now. The above has helped push their real GDP growth to 6%, significantly above the African average of 2.4% for the last 20 years (Doing Business, 2020). After severe IMF-backed structural reforms and a 15% inflation in the late 1970s, the government of Mauritius instituted policies that ended its macroeconomic instabilities. Import substitution industries, tourism and Export Process Zones were promoted to boost the macroeconomy.

Furthermore, fiscal adjustments became necessary to make credit accessibility easier for the growing SME sector. Interest rates and other taxes were lowered, paving the way for the textile export-oriented economy in Mauritius today. Like a domino, other sectors, including tourism and finance, benefited from the economic soundness.

Surprisingly, the graduate unemployment and under-employment adversities created out of the macro-economic instability became an incubator of the entrepreneurs for the new macro-economic drive.

In all the above, the birth of the Ebene Cyber City was crucial towards the Mauritian Service economy—nonetheless, pragmatic economic growth measures championed by the Mauritian government's Vision 2030. The above agenda focuses on biomedical services, the marine industry, ICT, seafood, and making Mauritius a Financial Hub linking Africa to Asia. There are also plans to develop more intelligent cities and the 'ocean economy' to champion tourism and high-tech manufacturing.

6.9.2 Institutional Framework

Six institutions support SMEs in Mauritius. Each institute plays a vital role in the holistic development of SMEs to compete globally. Table 6.10 below lists institutions and their primary roles towards SME development.

Table 6-10: SME Support Institutes in Mauritius

	SME SUPPORT INSTITUTION	PRIMARY ROLE
1	SMEDA & MyBiz	The Apex Body for SMEs
2	National Women Entrepreneur Council	Support Body for female entrepreneurs
3	National Institute for Corporative Entrepreneurs	Support Body for Cooperatives
4	Enterprise Mauritius	National Export Promotion Agency
5	National Productivity and Competitiveness Council	Support and Promotion Body for Productivity and Competitiveness
6	Board of Investment	National Investment Promotion Agency

Source: 10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

Each of the above-listed SMEs Support Institutes performs some or all of the following roles:

- Business Advisory and Counselling
- Capacity Building
- Business Networking and Collaborations
- Support for Market Access
- R&D and Innovation
- Financial Facilities and Support
- Infrastructure Facilities

6.9.3 Regulatory Framework

The government of Mauritius, in the year 2015, set up MyBiz as the one-stop shop for all business registrations. Nonetheless, inadequate human and material resources have hindered the operations of MyBiz, leaving SMEs in the usual hustle of applying for business permits from different institutions. Multiple governmental agencies and ministries are involved in approving the 614 available business licences and permits. The above could be addressed with

the effective operation of MyBiz. Nonetheless, Mauritius has one of the best business environments in Africa. Table 6.11 below illustrates the procedures, time and cost of starting a business in Mauritius.

Table 6-11: Starting a Business in Mauritius

	Mauritius	Sub Saharan Africa	OECD High Income	Best Regulatory Performance
Procedure(number)	4	7.4	4.9	1
Time (days)	4.5	21.5	9.2	0.5
Cost (% of income per capita)	0.8	36.3	3.0	0

Source: Doing Business, 2020

Table 6.4 above takes four procedures in 4.5 days at 0.8% of income per capita to start a business in Mauritius. The above figures represent the unique business environment in Africa and above the OECD High-Income averages. Nonetheless, Mauritius' targets are the figures from the Best Regulatory Performance Countries, which they hope to achieve through this 10-Year SME Development Strategy. Because of the above, Mauritius has identified the following regulatory gaps that need to be improved:

- Number of procedures to start a business
- Number of days to get a construction permit
- Cost of getting electricity
- Cost to register a property
- Number of days to enforce contracts
- Border compliance when exporting (Time & Cost)
- Border compliance when importing (Time & Cost)

6.9.4 Strategic Directions

The following six strategic driving forces form the main pillars of the framework that seek to develop the primary constraints to SME development in Mauritius: Each has been adequately elaborated in the Master Plan.

- Improving the Institutional and Regulatory Framework.
- Instilling an Entrepreneurial Attitude.
- Reinforcing Human Capital and Skills Development.
- Encouraging Innovation, Technology Transfer and Greening of SMEs.
- Improving Access to Finance and Equity Participation.
- Improving Marketing and Regional Exports Capacity.

6.9.5 Main Constraints and their implementation strategies

Stakeholders' meetings and SMEs survey revealed worrying challenges Mauritian SMEs face across the above performance drivers. The need to formulate policies geared towards addressing the constraints became eminent. Because of the above, proper scrutiny of the challenges (left) is done and paired against their corresponding proposed strategic policies (right) for implementations and presented in the Tables below:

Table 6-12: Challenges and strategic policies on regulatory & institutional framework of SMEs

Regulatory and Institutional Framework	Improving the Institutional and Regulatory Framework
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lack of a consistent national definition for SMEs ➤ Challenges with Easily Doing Business ➤ Untapped Facilities and Lack of Adherence to the Existing Rules ➤ Duplication of Services and disjointed supports ➤ Low Services Usage and Poor Institutional Awareness ➤ Limited Technical knowhow and weak Organisational Structure ➤ Lack of Mechanisms for Systematic Impact Assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Improve by Rationalising SME support - Set up SMEs in Mauritius ➤ Beef up SME advisory and technical services – put together a competent SMEs Intervention Team ➤ Enhance SMEs' usage of technical advisory services and ensure their effectiveness - Develop a Professional Assistance Voucher Scheme (PAVS) ➤ Develop E-licencing and Business Passports for SMEs ➤ Ensure Alternate Dispute Resolution Mechanisms for SMEs ➤ Ensure the relevance of SME policies and Initiatives

Source:10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

Table 6-13: challenges and strategic policies on national entrepreneurship

National Entrepreneurship Strategy	Instilling an Entrepreneurial Attitude
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Prevalence of Subsistence Entrepreneurship ➤ Lack of Entrepreneurial Skills ➤ Poor Entrepreneurial Performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Highlight Successful Entrepreneurs for a National Recognition ➤ Develop Pro-Women Infrastructures & Business Environment ➤ Upgrade Young Professionals and Support Starters - Set up Performance Driven Incubators and Industrial Parks ➤ Enhance the Monitoring and Evaluation of Entrepreneurship Policies and Initiatives

Source:10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

Table 6-14: challenges and strategic policies on human capital & skill Development

Human Capital & Skills Development	Reinforcing Human Capital and Skills Development
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Unavailability of Adequately Skilled Employees ➤ Ill-Investment in Skill Training ➤ Lack of HR Competencies ➤ Prevalence of Skill Mismatch ➤ Low Learning Achievements ➤ Absence of Technical Skills ➤ Insufficient Entrepreneurial Talents ➤ Poor Employability ➤ Inadequate Education & Training Expenditure from the Government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ascertain and Review SME Skills Requirements and Needs ➤ Transform, Rebrand TVET and Apprenticeship among SMEs ➤ Encourage “On the Job” Learning by Reinforce SME day-to-day Capacities. ➤ Review the Curricula for Entrepreneurship at all levels & Capacity Building of Teachers.

Source:10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

Table 6-15: challenges and strategic policies on innovation technology transfer & Green SMEs

Innovation Technology Transfer & Green SMEs	Encouraging Innovation, Technology Transfer and Greening of SMEs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Weak Innovative Capacities ➤ Inadequate R&D Activities in the Private Sector ➤ Limited Intellectual Property Framework ➤ Il-equipped Facilities for Incubation ➤ A Low Productivity ➤ Lack of Greening of SMEs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Enhance SMEs to build new products and embrace IP rights to protect their inventions. ➤ Promote Public Research to concentrate on National socio-economic priorities and areas of interest to Industry and SMEs ➤ Facilitate SME collaboration: Set up Clusters for SMEs' Design and Innovation. ➤ Encourage MNCs and Large Corporates Technology Transfer. ➤ Encourage more Green SMEs ➤ Support Technology Transfer and Improve Product Quality ➤ Encourage Foreign Investment in Mauritius ➤ Build a robust Strategy for Communication through an integrated IT approach. ➤ Promote online support, enhance exchanges and consolidate public-private dialogues.

Source:10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

Table 6-16: challenges and strategic policies on Access to Finance & Equity

Access to Finance & Equity	Improving Access to Finance and Equity Participation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Difficulties in Raising Finance ➤ Dependence on Traditional Financing Instruments ➤ Closing the Valley of Death ➤ disjointed Schemes of Government Financing ➤ High Lending Fees Imposed by Banks and Collateralisation ➤ Lack of Financial Planning and Business Capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ameliorate the Financial Literacy of SMEs ➤ widen SMEs Funding Sources – Revise Regulation to Facilitate Private Investors' Participation

Source:10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

Table 6-17: challenges and strategic policies on Marketing and regulatory exports capacity building

Marketing and Regional Exports Capacity Building	Improving Marketing and Regional Exports Capacity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ A Relatively Smaller Domestic Market with Vertically-Integrated Conglomerates ➤ Inadequate Marketing Capability ➤ A Poor Export-Oriented Manufacturing Base ➤ Inauspicious Effects of the Duty-Free Island Concept ➤ High Export Concentration ➤ Untapped Multilateral, Regional and Bilateral Trade Agreements ➤ Increasing Exports of Services ➤ Lack of Cooperation among SMEs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Making Sure Product Quality Meets International Standards ➤ Improve SMEs Export Capacities ➤ Promote product development, marketing and investments towards Africa

Source:10-Year Mauritius SMEs Development Plan

6.9.6 Observations from the SMEs policy documents of Ghana and Mauritius

A dive into the SMEs Policy Guides for Ghana and Mauritius points out that both countries' enviable progress in macroeconomic development did not happen fortuitously or by luck. The two economies have pursued significant institutional and regulatory reforms since the 1970s till recently. Significant reforms were triggered by the emergence of the *Doing Business Index* by the World Bank, which forces participating economies to reform their business legislations to match that of the best-practising countries in the world. Mauritius has, since the 2000s, been coherently pursuing macro-economic regulatory reforms that have placed them on the top of the chart of the most business-friendly environment in Africa and 13th in the world (*Doing Business*, 2020). On the other hand, Ghana did make some strides, but not enough to be at the level of Mauritius. Ghana, in 2020, was ranked 17th in Africa and 118th globally (*Tradingeconomics*, 2022).

6.9.7 Comparing the Vision, Mission and Objectives of SMEs Policies of Ghana and Mauritius

6.9.7.1 Vision Statements

Ghana and Mauritius are both focused on making SMEs their primary driver for economic growth. However, whilst Mauritius is specific with what they want to achieve (A High-Income Economy), Ghana is silent on its target. Table 6.11 below is the vision statements for the SME Policy Guides for both countries.

Table 6-18: SMEs Policy Vision Statements for Ghana and Mauritius

Vision: - Mauritius	Vision: -Ghana
SMEs as the Engine of Growth to Position Mauritius as a High-Income Economy.	To create a significant pool of modern, globally competitive, sustainable MSMEs that drive growth and development.

Source: Ghana & Mauritius SMEs Policy Guides

6.9.7.2 Mission Statements

Table 6.12 below is the SMEs Policy Mission Statements for both economics. Mauritius is looking to foster Innovative, Sustainable and Globally Competitive SMEs. Conversely, Ghana's mission (which is supposed to be short term) is to stimulate the growth of all 635,696 MSMEs (see figure 2.1 in Chapter 2), which is unrealistic and not achievable. Again, Ghana's Mission Statement did not explicitly point out the targeted results at the end of the day. However, a careful study confirms that if Ghana's Mission Statement can pull through, as documented below, it will eventually lead to the Job Creation, Value Addition and Economic Independence that the Mauritian Mission Statement has targeted.

Table 6-19: SMEs Policy Mission Statements for Ghana and Mauritius

Mission: -Mauritius	Mission: -Ghana
Foster the Emergence of Innovative, Sustainable and Globally Competitive SMEs for Job Creation, Value Addition and Economic Democratisation.	To stimulate the growth of MSMEs to produce world-class products and services that can compete locally and internationally with a supportive enabling environment and interventions of technology transfer, entrepreneurial culture, skills development, access to finance, market facilitation and research and development.

Source: Ghana & Mauritius SMEs Policy Guides

6.9.7.3 Objectives

Mauritius' objectives are time-bound and lead to what is referred to as 'Target 2026 of the Master Plan. In line with their Vision Statement, the objectives aim to create employment, add value, and increase export and GDP growth.

Ghana's SMEs Policy Guide's Objectives are also linked to its Vision Statement and targets contributing to the economy through job creation and income generation. However, unlike Mauritius, Ghana's SME Policy objectives are not time-bound and will be irrelevant over time and much more likely not to see the light of the day.

In all, Ghana's nine (9) SMEs Policy Objectives have been strategically paired with the five (5) drafted SMEs Policy Objectives of Mauritius and presented in Table 6.20 below:

Table 6-20: Objectives of the SMEs Policy Guides for Ghana and Mauritius

Objectives-Mauritius	Objectives-Ghana
Improve SME competitiveness and growth by transforming SMEs into agile players with improved productivity, better quality products and resiliency to compete globally.	To improve the productivity of the MSME sector; To improve access to finance.
Foster high-growth potential SMEs by nurturing start-ups, fostering entrepreneurship, supporting knowledge-based activities and disruptive (innovators) SMEs.	To facilitate the building and promotion of a dynamic, viable and promising MSME sector that encourages an innovative entrepreneurial culture and supports high-growth start-ups; To drive the formalisation of the informal sector.
Upgrade skills and job opportunities by supporting SMEs to address skill mismatch and upgrade human capital to respond to new market demands.	To enhance Local Economic Development by strengthening NBSSI and other relevant institutions towards job creation.
Improve design and value addition by supporting SMEs in research and development, innovation and brand identity to move into niche markets.	To promote Research and Development. To promote the spatial distribution of industries to reduce urban and peri-urban imbalances.
Increase market access and exports by providing SMEs with intelligence, market development support, and logistics to integrate the global supply chain.	To promote enterprises with high-value addition, export-oriented or import substitution focus and encourage the use of local raw materials;

Source: Ghana & Mauritius SMEs Policy Guides

6.9.8 Proposed Strategic Policy Guide for Ghanaian SMEs with Insight from Mauritius

Figure 6-9: Strategic guide for Ghanaian SMEs regarding Mauritius

6.9.8.1 Realistic Mission and Vision

As demonstrated by Mauritius, Ghana's Mission and Vision Statements must be reconstructed to include realistic targets. Mauritius has a clear and precise conscience, Mission and Vision Statements. They are transparent with what they want to achieve on the macroeconomic ladder.

Ghana should consider reframing its Mission and Vision statement in line with a strategy that would quickly help achieve the above.

6.9.8.2 Strategic Action Plan

As a matter of urgency, Ghana needs to back its proposed SMEs Policy Guide with a strategic Action Plan and implementation. KPIs and timelines should back the proposed action plan. Priority must be given to the identified interventions when delivering the reforms over an agreed timeline. Actions that can immediately impact the process and can be visualised by stakeholders are essential to start with. Quick wins (less than a year) are easy to start with as their requirements are not daunting and can easily trigger the mobilisation of the needed resources. The above is also intended to tackle any attitudinal or wrong mindset that might affect the target population. The outcome of the Quick Wins is expected to be felt throughout the project timeline.

6.9.8.3 Three-Tier & Specific Action Plan

Ghana's proposed Strategic Action Plan above should be in 3-tiers; Short Term (0-2 years), Medium Term (2-5 years), and long-term (5-10 years), with each trimester targeting some specifics of the Action Plan. A 10-year period is enough to start and achieve a target realistically. The proposed timeline would also keep the policy implementers on their toes as their work would be measured by the end of the period. A thorough review should be conducted at the end of every term to identify the loopholes for redress.

6.9.8.4 Improving the Doing Business Indicators

Ghana should make conscious efforts by developing and implementing strategic plans to improve the indicators set out by the Ease of Doing Business Index. Tackling the seven strategic gaps (see section 6.9.2.3) would eventually create an enabling business environment that will benefit local SMEs and attract foreign investors into the Ghanaian economy. Mauritius

has been on top of the game because they constantly work towards improving the seven strategic gaps proposed by the world bank.

6.9.9 Justification of the Proposed Strategic Guide

6.9.9.1 Strategic Map of Ghanaian SMEs

The Map below vividly shows how the proposed SME policy guide could increase the SME industry's revenues if well implemented.

Figure 6-10: The Strategic Map of SMEs

Source: Author's creation

The strategy map above (Figure 6.10) uses the bottom-up approach to achieve the proposed SMEs Policy Guide's aim of increasing revenue. The strategy suggests that if policy implementers monitor new macroeconomic trends and consumer tastes, it would internally trigger the increase in core competencies among SMEs through implementing the proposed strategies. More so, the lost customer (SME) loyalty would be restored, and premium charges would be dropped. The above would reduce operating expenses (economics of scale) whilst profits soar. Ultimately, revenue increases as a result.

6.9.9.2 Implementation of the Proposed Strategies

This thesis employs the application of KURT Lewin's vs Kotter's eight models of change, as explained in section 6.8.4 above.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter marks the final part of the dissertation. Although various recommendations were already stated in chapters four and six, chapter seven will present a brief list of some recommendations to complement the already suggested ones in the previous chapters. However, this chapter starts with the concluding remarks of each chapter, outlining, in summary, the achievements and synergy that exist through the main chapters. References and appendices follow this chapter.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the au

7.1 CONCLUSION

7.1.1 Chapter One

Briefly, all the crucial aspects of this thesis have been introduced in the first chapter. The chapter did provide a background review that this research is designed to address. The SME sector has been in business for a long time but has yet to receive enough attention and investment in developing economies. With a growing population spiced by unemployment, the SME sector has been challenged to turn this around because of its potential. Nonetheless, inadequate credit and technical support hinder achieving the above task. An introduction to dealing with challenges was made and discussed in subsequent chapters. Research objectives and accompanying questions were explicitly presented to ensure proper research alignment and were the guiding principles throughout the study. Finally, the structure of the remaining thesis has been outlined as part of chapter one.

7.1.2 Chapter two

A detailed review of extensive literature was done according to the research alignment in the preceding chapter. Extant literature on financial and non-financial constraints facing the SME sector was reviewed and presented so that the targeted audience of this research could quickly

assimilate. Various SMEs' definitions worldwide were presented and spiced with an operational definition to be adopted for this thesis. SMEs were identified into various classifications, and the number of jobs each classification contributes to the country. This study presented SMEs as the panacea to Ghana's unemployment situation through the reviewed literature. In this chapter, a preliminary revelation suggests that paying attention to the Ghanaian SME industry could create some 1,137,611 jobs periodically to service the unemployed 1,546,542 Ghanaians actively seeking jobs, according to the Ghana Population and Housing Census, 2021. The chapter ended by outlining the research gap for this study and presenting a conceptual framework that informed the direction of the study.

7.1.3 Chapter three

The research methodology, philosophy, design, and theory development approach are explained in this chapter. Moreover, the strategy for this research, time horizon and research coverage, and its justification were discussed in chapter three. Also, stakeholder analysis, the employed data collection method with its accompanied limitation and population sampling were explicitly explained in this chapter. Issues bordering the Objectivity, reliability and validity of data were also digested and presented. Finally, ethical issues concerning this study were discussed, approved, and presented in line with the University of the West of Scotland research principles.

7.1.4 Chapter four

Three sets of questionnaires were designed for the data collection process. Questionnaire for SME Managers/owners, questionnaire for SME Credit Institutions and questionnaire for SME Skill and Advisor Institutes. The collected primary data was analysed through descriptive and explanatory statistics with the help of IBM SPSS 25. The analysed data was presented under the four different sections of this chapter. Data on SME Management, SME Financing, Data

on the impact of Covid-19 on SMEs and Data on SME Policy Recommendations. Under each section, the data sequencing was done using the same format. Thus, the SME Manager's questionnaire data was analysed and presented first. The above was always followed by the data from the SME credit institutes before the data from SME Skill and Advisory Institutes. The above format was to ensure synergy in line with the objectives of this thesis, as explained in chapter two.

7.1.5 Chapter five

This chapter presents a more technical analysis of the collected data. They employed Pearson's Chi-Square and Correlation Coefficients. Moreover, chapter five presented nineteen (19) cross-tabulations from the SME manager's questionnaire, two (2) cross-tabulations from the SME financial Institution questionnaire and two (2) cross-tabulations from the SME Skill and Advisory Institutes questionnaire. Pearson's Correlation Coefficients and Chi-Square test were used to establish relations between the cross-tabulated questions to understand further and analyse SMEs' constraints regarding management and credit accessibility. It is important to note that the presentations in this chapter were done in alignment with the previous chapters. Interestingly, the revelations were in line with the research objectives and were crucial in the presentation of research findings in the chapter.

7.1.6 Chapter Six

The much-anticipated chapter six, which comes in the form of a consultancy report, is created to re-ignite the reader's interest to the point that they may get bored with data. A considerable number of business management models were employed as an act of creativity and in response to the final specific objective of this dissertation. For alignment purposes, the format of chapter six also followed the same format as the previous chapters. Thus, the presentation of findings on SME managers, the findings on SME Creditors, and the findings of SME Skill and Advisory

Institutes. The above outcome was a complete proposed strategic change for SME management and credit accessibility. The above is a direct response to the first two objectives of this study. Moreover, evaluative statistics were used to compare Ghana and Mauritius, which resulted in the recommendation of a strategic policy guide for Ghanaian SMEs. Again, the above responds directly to the third objective of this dissertation.

In a nutshell, this thesis stated in chapter one that it will ascertain and address the managerial shortfalls encountered by SMEs in Ghana and beyond, which was achieved in chapter six. Also, it mentioned that it would investigate the credit accessibility challenges facing SMEs in Ghana and beyond and address them, which has been achieved in chapters four, five and six. Finally, it documented that it will develop guidelines to enhance the effectiveness of financing SMEs in Ghana and beyond, as done in chapter six. In conclusion, as stated in chapter one, all the objectives of this study have been achieved as expected.

7.2 RECOMMENDATION

7.2.1 Recommendations for SME Managers/Owners

- SMEs manager/owners should take advantage of adult education to improve their numeracy and writing skills.
- SME managers/owners should improve their IT skills to use social media and other online marketing platforms for advertising their goods and services.
- SME managers/owners should avoid mixing their finances with their business capital to measure their profits and losses without difficulty and monitor the progress of their businesses.
- SMEs manager/owners should commit more to IT and human resources to enhance the efficiency of their management process.

7.2.2 Recommendations for SME Credit Institutions

- Credit institutions should introduce basic financial management training for their clients (SMEs) to manage the credit they acquire efficiently.
- After introducing the above training, SME credit institutes should simplify their credit accessibility procedure since some risks would have been eliminated by equipping the SME manager/owners with technical abilities.
- Positive discrimination for women and persons with disabilities PLWDs: The credit institutes should prioritise women and PLWDs since they are the most vulnerable and less likely to access credit in the mainstream.
- Ghana's loan repayment terms are usually short-term, while SMEs need long-term credit and working capital.
- The Village Savings and Loans Associations should be formalised and encouraged to include the hybrid (see Fig. 6.5) financing strategy in the rural communities.
- The lack of women's participation at the highest decision level is limited to household and corporate levels. Only 22.2% of females work at the decision-making level among credit institutions. Credit institutes have to appoint women to the decision-making levels to promote the proposed positive discrimination against women and PLWDs.

7.2.3 Recommendation for SME Skill and Advisory Institutes

- The SME Skill and Advisory Institutes are 100% male at the decision-making level. A dominant male sector will most likely discourage a good number of the 42% of female SMEs from seeking advice. The existing SME Skill and Advisory Institutes should include some women at their decision-making level.

REFERENCE

- Aboagye, A.Q., 2020. Ghanaian banking crisis of 2017-2019 and related party transactions. *African Journal of Management Research*, 27(1), pp.2-19.
- Abor, J. and Biekpe, N., 2006. Small business financing initiatives in Ghana. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 4(3), pp.69-77.
- Abor, J. and Quartey, P. (2010), "Issues in SME Development in Ghana and South Africa" *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*. Issue 39, pp.218-228.
- Abubakar. Learning from the 1987 Financial Crisis: Academia, March 2, 2022. https://www.academia.edu/41372943/Learning_from_the_1987_Financial_Crisis
- Achen, Christopher H. and Larry M. Bartels, 2004. "Blind Retrospection: Electoral Responses to Drought, Flu, and Shark Attacks." *Estudio Working Paper* 2004/199.
- Ackah, J. and Vuvor, S., 2011. The Challenges Faced by Small & Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Obtaining Credit in Ghana.
- Adèr H. J.Helmsing. (2008). Small Enterprises and Changing Policies. In: Smith, A and Peter
- B
- Adjei, D.S., 2012. *Micro, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Ghana: Challenges and Prospects: A Case Study Of Sekondi-Takoradi Metropolis* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Adoah, I., 2015. *Determinants of universal bank lending rate in Ghana* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Ghana).
- Adomako, S., Danso, A. and J. O. Damoah. (2016). The moderating influence of financial literacy on the relationship between access to finance and firm growth in Ghana. *Venture Capital*, 18: 1, 43-61. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13691066.2015.1079952>
- Africaway, 2021: <https://www.istockphoto.com/photo/large-kumasi-central-market-ghana-west-africa-gm458346981-23076852> Accessed [05/12/2021]
- Agwu, M.O., and Emeti, C.I., 2014. Issues, challenges, and prospects of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Port-Harcourt city. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 3(1), pp.101-114.
- A.G.I Newsletter (2011) Cause of Credit in Ghana, *AGI Business Barometer* (March 2011) P 3
- Akeyewale, R., 2018. Winners and losers in Africa's Continental Free Trade area. In *International Trade Forum* (No. 4, pp. 14-15). International Trade Centre.
- Alauddin, M.D. and Chowdhury, M.M., 2015. Small and medium enterprise in Bangladesh- Prospects and challenges. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*.

Ali, A.H., Abu-Hadi, A.O. and Ali, A.Y.S., 2013. The Accessibility of Microfinance for Small Businesses in Mogadishu, Somalia. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(11), pp.172-180.

Amegashie-Viglo, S. and S. K. Bokor. (2014). Entrepreneurship development and opportunities for skills training for job creation in the informal sector of the Volta Region in Ghana. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(17), 22-38.
www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JEDS/article/download/15348/15565

Amentie, C., Negash, E. and L. Kumera. (2016). Barriers to growth of medium and small enterprises in a developing country: case study Ethiopia. *Journal of Entrepreneurship & Organisation Management*, 5: 3. <https://www.omicsonline.org/open-access/barriers-to-growth-of-medium-and-small-enterprises-in-developing-country-case-study-ethiopia-2169-026X-1000190.pdf>

Amoah, S.K. and Amoah, A.K., 2018. The role of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to employment in Ghana. *International Journal of Business and Economics Research*, 7(5), pp.151-157.

Anderson, W. (2017). Factors affecting small and medium enterprises (SMEs) start-up and growth in Tanzania. *The Pan-African Journal of Business Management*, 1:1. <https://pajbm.out.ac.tz/PAJBM%20Vol%201.pdf#page=6>

Anderson, S. (2000). A history of the past 40 years in financial crises: International Financial Review. Available from <http://www.ifre.com/a-history-of-the-past-40-years-in-financial-crises/21102949.fullarticle>

ANDRIOF, J. et al., 2002: *Unfolding Stakeholder Thinking: Theory, Responsibility and Engagement*. Sheffield: Greenleaf Publishing. ISBN 978-187471952.

Aryeety, E., Kayanula D, and Quartey P. (1994). Supply and Demand for Finance of Small Enterprises in Ghana. *World Bank Discussion Paper*. (No.251).

Ancient symbols.com

Ansoff, H.I., Kipley, D., Lewis, A.O., Helm-Stevens, R. and Ansoff, R., 2018. *Implanting strategic management*. Springer.

Ansoff, H.I., 1957. Strategies for diversification. *Harvard business review*, 35(5), pp.113-124.

Association of Ghana Industries. <https://www.agighana.org/>

Aterido, R., Beck, T. and L. Iacovone. (2013). Access to finance in Sub-Saharan Africa: Is there a gender gap? *World Development*, 47, 102-120.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2013.02.013>

Australian Fair Work Act 2009

Ayyagari, M., Demirgüç, A., Maksimovic, V., 2011. Small vs. Young Firms Across the World — Contribution to Employment, Job Creation, and Growth. Policy Research Working Paper 5631 (The World Bank Development Research Group).

BBS (2004). *Report on the Census of Manufacturing Industries* (Dhaka: BBS).

Bank of Ghana: Average lending rates of universal banks as at 31st July 2021. <https://www.bog.gov.gh/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/AVERAGE-LENDING-RATES-AS-AT-JULY-2021.pdf>

Bager, Torben & Wickstrøm, Kent & Nielsen, Pia & Larsen, Tue. (2015). Enrollment of SME Managers to Growth-oriented training programs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*. 16. 578-599. 10.1108/IJEER-12-2014-0224.

Bajaj, N., (2019) Can blockchain unlock the potential of SME financing? Available from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/can-blockchain-unlock-potential-sme-financing-nishika-bajaj/>

Beck, T. Demirgüç-Kunt, A. and Levin, R. (2003). SMEs Growth and Poverty: Cross-Country Evidence. *World Bank Working Paper*

Beck, T. Demirgüç-Kunt, A. and Levin, R. (2003). SMEs Growth and Poverty: Cross-Country Evidence. *World Bank Working Paper*

Berman-Brown, R. and Saunders, M., 2008. *Dealing with statistics: What you need to know*.

Blank, S., 2013. Why the lean start-up changes everything. *Harvard business review*, 91(5), pp.63-72.

Boahene, S.H., Dasah, J. and Agyei, S.K., 2012. Credit risk and profitability of selected banks in Ghana. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 3(7), pp.6-14.

Boateng, A.A., 2015. An examination of challenges and prospects of microfinance institutions in Ghana. *Journal of Economics and sustainable development*, 6(4), pp.52-60.

Bourne, L. and Walker, D.H., 2006. Visualizing stakeholder influence—Two Australian examples. *Project Management Journal*, 37(1), pp.5-21.

Brannen, C.F., 2010. An impact study of the Village Savings and Loan Association (VSLA) program in Zanzibar, Tanzania.

Bryman, A., 2006. Integrating quantitative and qualitative research: how is it done? *Qualitative research*, 6(1), pp.97-113.

The University of Surrey.

Business Set Free Ltd (2013). <https://businesssetfree.com/small-business-product-life-cycle/> Accessed on [02/10/2021]

BUYSSSE, K. and A. VERBEKE, 2003: Proactive Environmental Strategies: A Stakeholder Management Perspective. *Strategic Management Journal*. 24(5), 453- 470. ISSN 1097-0266.

Chang-Yong Sung, Ki-Chan Kim & Sungyong In (2016) Small and medium-sized enterprises policy in Korea from the 1960s to the 2000s and beyond, *Small Enterprise Research*, 23:3, 262-275, DOI: [10.1080/13215906.2016.1269665](https://doi.org/10.1080/13215906.2016.1269665)

Charmaz, K., 2006. *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*. sage.

Charness, G. and Gneezy, U., 2012. Strong evidence for gender differences in risk-taking. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 83(1), pp.50-58.

CHINYIO, E. et al., 2010: *Construction Stakeholder Management*. Chichester (United Kingdom): Blackwell Publishing. ISBN 978-1-4051-8098-6.

Chowdhury, Md & Golam Azam, Kazi & Islam, Serajul. (2013). Problems and Prospects of SME Financing in Bangladesh. *Asian Business Review*. 2. 109-116. 10.18034/abr.v2i2.111.

Chwieroth and Walter, (2010): *Financial Crises and Political Turnover: A Long Run Panoramic View*. Available from <http://personal.lse.ac.uk/chwierot/images/Panoramic.pdf>

Cirera, X. and Maloney, W. F. (2017). *The Innovation Paradox*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/28341/9781464811609.pdf>

Citi Population, 2020: Wa Municipal. Available from http://www.citypopulation.de/en/ghana/admin/upper_west/1002_wa_municipal/. [Accessed on 09/05/2022]

Cummings, S., Bridgman, T. and Brown, K.G., 2016. Unfreezing change as three steps: Rethinking Kurt Lewin's legacy for change management. *Human relations*, 69(1), pp.33-60.

Curran, E., (2019). India was likely to surpass the U.S. to be the world's second-largest economy by 2030. *The Economic Times*. Bloomberg. Available [//economictimes.indiatimes.com/articleshow/67448036.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst](https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/articleshow/67448036.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst). [Accessed on, 10/01/2019]

Collier, P., 2009. Rethinking Finance for Africa's Small Firms in "SME Financing in SSA," *Proparco Magazine on Private Sector and Development*, Issue 1 May 2009

Crotty M (1998) *The Foundation of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process*. Sydney, Australia: Allen & Unwin.

Damoah, O.B.O., Ashie, A. and Kekesi, E.K., 2016. The propensity to participate in formal training programmes: Evidence from small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*.

Dana, L.P., 1998. Small but not independent: SMEs in Japan. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 36(4), p.73.

Daniels, L. and Ngwira, A. (1993), 'Results of a Nation-wide Survey on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Malawi', GEMINI Technical Report No 53. PACT, Publications, New York

De Lima, P. et al., (2016). What's holding back the private sector in MENA? Lessons from the Enterprise Survey. Washington, DC: The World Bank. http://www.eib.org/attachments/efs/econ_mena_enterprise_survey_en.pdf

Donga, G., Ngirande, H. and K. Shumba. (2016). Perceived barrier to the development of small, medium and microenterprises: a case study of Thulamela Municipality in the Limpopo Province. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 14: 4, 61-66. https://businessperspectives.org/images/pdf/free/8023/PPM_2016_04_Donga.pdf

Doing Business 2019 Fact Sheet: Sub-Saharan Africa. Available from https://www.doingbusiness.org/content/dam/doingBusiness/media/Fact-Sheets/DB19/FactSheet_DoingBusiness2019_SSA_Eng.pdf

Doing Business 2020 p18. Available from:

<file:///C:/Users/abapu/Desktop/SMEs/doing%20business%20in%20Ghana%202020.pdf>fbid

Duho, K.C.T., 2019. Does the Ghanaian Banking Crisis Signal the End of Accounting?

Eckel, C.C. and Grossman, P.J., 2008. Chapter 113 Men, Women and Risk Aversion: Experimental Evidence. *Handbook of Experimental Economics Results*, 1061–1073.

EZ SPSS Tutorials, (2021): calculate and interpret chi-square in SPSS, <https://ezspss.com/calculate-and-interpret-chi-square-in-spss/> [Accessed on 20/11/2021],

Fjose, S., Grünfeld, L.A. and SQW, C.G., 2010. Identifying SME roles and obstacles to SME growth. *MENON-publication*, (14).

Fowowe, B. (2017). Access to finance and firm performance: Evidence from African countries. *Review of Development Finance*, 7, 6-17. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1879933717300106>

FREEMAN, R. E., 1984: *Strategic management: A Stakeholder Approach*. London: Pitman. ISBN 0-273-001913-9
FREEMAN, R. E., 2010: *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN 978-0521151740.

Gea.gov.gh

Ghanaweb, (2018). Government works on national micro, and SME policies to boost the economy. Ghana News Agency. Available from <https://www.ghanaweb.com/GhanaHomePage/business/Government-works-on-national-micro-SMEs-policy-to-boost-the-economy-700210>

Ghana 2021 Population and Housing Census: General Report, Volume 3E. Accessed on March 3, 2022.

[http://statsghana.gov.gh/gssmain/fileUpload/pressrelease/2021%20PHC%20General%20Report%20Vol%203E Economic%20Activity.pdf](http://statsghana.gov.gh/gssmain/fileUpload/pressrelease/2021%20PHC%20General%20Report%20Vol%203E%20Economic%20Activity.pdf)

Ghana Statistical Service: 2021 Population and Housing Census: General Report 3B: Age and Sex Profile. <https://census2021.statsghana.gov.gh/>

Gockel, A.G. , Akoena, S.K. (2002). Financial Intermediation for the Poor: Credit Demand by Micro, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Ghana. A Further Assignment for Financial Sector Policy? International Labour Organisation, IFLIP Research Paper 02-6 [Google Scholar](#)

GSS (Ghana Statistical Service), 2014. 2010 Population and Housing Census: District Analytical Report, Wa Municipality.

Ghana Statistical Service: 2021 Population and Housing Census, General Report Volume 3A. Population of regions and districts: census2021.statsghana.gov.gh

GSS, Integrated Business Establishment Survey, Regional Spatial Business Report, Ghana Statistical Service, 2016 <https://s3-eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/aaimagestore/essays/1767810.001.png>

Ghana Statistical Service, 2015. Ghana poverty mapping report.

GURL, E., 2017. SWOT analysis: A theoretical review.

Haider, H., 2018. Constraints to business growth in low-and medium-income countries.

Hasan, F. and Jamil, G.M.H., 2014. Financing Small and Medium Enterprises in Bangladesh-Issues and Challenges. *The Asian Journal of Technology Management*, 7(1), p.45.

Hendry, C., 1996. Understanding and creating whole organizational change through learning theory. *Human relations*, 49(5), pp.621-641.

IBES Summary Report (2015): *Ghana Statistical Service*: www.statsghana.gov.gh

Hollweck, T., 2015. Robert K. Yin. (2014). Case Study Research Design and Methods.

Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. 282 pages. *Canadian Journal of Program Evaluation*, 30(1).

IBESS Regional Spatial Business Report, (2016): *Ghana Statistical Service*: www.statsghana.gov.gh

International Trade Centre (2018). *Promoting SME competitiveness in Africa*: Data for de-risking investment. ITC, Geneva.

Irwin, D. and Scott, J.M., 2010. Barriers faced by SMEs in raising bank finance. *International journal of entrepreneurial behavior & research*, 16(3), pp.245-259.

Kashuliza, A.K. and Kydd, J.G., 1996. Determinants of bank credit access for smallholder farmers in tanzania: a discriminant analysis application/facteurs influençant l'accès au crédit bancaire pour les agriculteurs en tanzanie: application d'une analyse discriminante. *Savings and Development*, pp.285-304.

Kayanula, D. and Quartey P. (2000), The Policy Environment for Promoting Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Ghana and Malawi, Finance and Development Research Programme, Working Paper Series Paper No. 15, IDPM, University of Manchester.

King, K. and McGrath, S. (2002). Globalization, Enterprise, and Knowledge: Educational Training and Development. *International Review of Education*. Vol.50 (1), 74-76(3).

Kumar, R. (2017). Targeted SME financing and employment effects: What do we know and what can we do differently? Washington, DC: The World Bank Group.
<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/577091496733563036/Targeted-SME-financing-and-employment-effects-what-do-we-know-and-what-can-we-do-differently>

Kuntchev, V., Ramalho, R., Rodríguez-Meza, R., and J. S. Yang. (2012). *What Have We Learned From the Enterprise Surveys Regarding Access To Finance by SMEs?* Washington, DC: The World Bank.
<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/958291468331867463/pdf/682920WP0Box360s0to0finance0and0SME.pdf>

Kuwahara, S., Yoshino, N., Sagara, M. and Taghizadeh-Hesary, F., 2016. Role of the Credit Risk Database in Developing SMEs in Japan: Ideas for Asia. *SMEs in Developing Asia*, pp.297-323.

Kyerematen, A., 2019. African continental free trade agreement (AfCFTA).

Laerd Statistics, (2021): Pearson Product-Moment Correlation.
<https://statistics.laerd.com/statistical-guides/pearson-correlation-coefficient-statistical-guide.php>. [Accessed on 20/11/2021]

Lewis-Beck, Michael S., 1988. *Economics and Elections: The Major Western Democracies*. (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press)

Lorenz, E. and Pommet, S. (2017). *Innovation, credit constraints and national banking systems: a comparison of developing nations*. GREDEG Working paper series.
<http://www.gredeg.cnrs.fr/working-papers/GREDEG-WP-2017-16.pdf>

Lu, Y., Wu, J., Peng, J. and Lu, L., 2020. The perceived impact of the Covid-19 epidemic: evidence from a sample of 4807 SMEs in Sichuan Province, China. *Environmental Hazards*, 19(4), pp.323-340.

Lutz, M. B. and Lutz, S. (2017). *Financing and performance of female-owned firms in Middle Eastern and African economies*. Instituto Complutense de Analisis Economico, working paper.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2907977

Meldrum, M. and McDonald, M., 1995. The Ansoff Matrix. In *Key marketing concepts* (pp. 121-126). Palgrave, London.

Miller, R. L. and Brewer, J. D. (2003). A–Z of Social Research. SAGE Publication Ltd. London. *Structural Adjustment, Financial Policy and Assistance Programs in Africa*. London: ITS Publication. P25-34

Ministry of Trade and Industry, 2019: Final Draft, National Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) Policy Ghana. Available from [https://www.bcp.gov.gh/acc/consultation/docs/DRAFT%20MSME%20-%20FINAL%2026.02.2019%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.bcp.gov.gh/acc/consultation/docs/DRAFT%20MSME%20-%20FINAL%2026.02.2019%20(1).pdf) Accessed on [09/05/2022]

Mira-Bohigas, Y., 2021. *Perspectives of Change Management Among Mid-Level Administrators in Higher Education* (Doctoral dissertation, St. Thomas University).

Msoka, E.M. (2013). Do entrepreneurship skills have an influence on the performance of women-owned enterprises in Africa? Case of micro and small enterprises in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*, 3:3, 52-62. https://www.ijbhtnet.com/journals/Vol_3_No_3_March_2013/6.pdf

Mungal, A. and Garbharran, H.L., 2014. The perceptions of small businesses in the implementation of cash management techniques. *Journal of Economics and behavioral studies*.

Musabayana, J., 2012. *Small enterprise growth: The critical role of the owner-manager: A case study of the construction sector in Gauteng, South Africa* (Doctoral dissertation, University of South Africa).

NAAMI, A., 2017. Effects of the microfinance and small loans centre on rural enterprise growth among women beneficiaries in the Brong-Ahafo Region of Ghana. *Review of Social Studies*, 4(2), pp.69-88.

Nyaaba, D., Atintono, F. and Anaba, S.A., 2018. Poverty Reduction in Ghana: Microfinance and Small Loan Centre (MASLOC) in Perspective. *Arch Bus Adm Manag: ABAM-119*. *JDOI*, 10.

NBSSI (1990), "Supporting Micro & Small Scale Enterprises". *A handbook on Enterprise Development Part 1*. NBSSI, Print Solutions, Accra.

Ndiaye, N. Razak, L. A., Nagayey, R. and A. Ng. (2018). Demystifying small and medium enterprises (SMEs) performance in emerging and developing economies. *Borsa Istanbul Review*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214845018300280>

Nelson, J.A., 2012. Are women really more risk-averse than men?

Nkuah, J.K., Tanyeh, J.P. and Gaeten, K., 2013. Financing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana: challenges and determinants in accessing bank credit. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 2(3), pp.12-25.

Olafsen, E. and Cook, P. A (2016). *Growth entrepreneurship in developing countries: a preliminary literature review*. Washington, DC: The World Bank Group. https://www.infodev.org/infodev-files/growth_entrepreneurship_in_developing_countries_-_a_preliminary_literature_review_-_february_2016_-_infodev.pdf

Onubedo, G. and K. M. Yusuf. (2018). *Finance and firm productivity in Africa: Background study from World Bank Enterprise Data Survey*. Abuja. Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa. <https://www.africaportal.org/publications/finance-and-firm-productivity-africa-background-study-world-bank-enterprise-survey-data/>

Oxford Business Group. Ghana's banking sector clean-up has created a more sustainable industry <https://oxfordbusinessgroup.com/overview/restoring-confidence-sector-clean-led-regulators-has-resulted-smaller-more-sustainable-industry>. Accessed on March 2, 2022

Parker R.L, Riopelle R, Steel W.F (1995), `Small Enterprises Adjusting to Liberalisation in Five African Countries', World Bank Discussion Paper No. 271, African Technical Department Series.

Philomina, Q., Emmanuel, A. and Emmanuel, A., 2012. Influence of microfinance and small loan centre (MASLOC) on the development of small-scale enterprises in the Wa Municipality. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(1), pp.1-10.

Piabuo, S.M., Baye, F.M. and Tieguhong, J.C., 2015. Effects of credit constraints on the productivity of small and medium-sized enterprises in Cameroon. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*.

Quartey, P., Turkson, E., Abor, J.Y. and Iddrisu, A.M., 2017. Financing the growth of SMEs in Africa: What are the constraints to SME financing within ECOWAS? *Review of development finance*, 7(1), pp.18-28.

Quaye, I., Abrokwah, E., Sarbah, A. and Osei, J.Y., 2014. Bridging the SME financing gap in Ghana: The role of microfinance institutions. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 2(04), p.339.

Reid, J., (2019): SMEs diversifying business travel routes, British Airways data shows. Business Traveller. Available from <https://www.businesstraveller.com/business-travel/2019/01/10/smes-diversifying-business-travel-routes-british-airways-data-shows/>. [Accessed on 10/01/2019]

Rogers, B.A. (2002). Funding of SMEs: Sourcing of Funds and Problems Limiting Access, *ICAN journal. Nigerian Accountant* Vol. 35 No. 1 January/March.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P.H.I.L.I.P. and Thornhill, A.D.R.I.A.N., 2016,p124. Research methods. *Business Students 7th edition Pearson Education Limited, England*.

Schein, E.H., 1988. Organizational socialization and the profession of management. *MIT Sloan management review*, 30(1), p.53.

Schmidt, R.H. and Kropp, E. (1987), *Rural Finance: Guiding Principles*. Rural Development Series, BMZ/GTZ/DSE, Rossdorf, TZ-Verlagsgesellschaft

Schmitz, H. (1982). Growth Constraints on Small Scale Manufacturing in Developing Countries: A Critical Review, In *World Development*, 10 (6): 429 – 450.

Šimberová, I. and Pollard, D., 2008. STAKEHOLDER RELATIONS FOCUS IN MARKETING CONCEPTS OF COMPANIES. *Economics & management*.

Slabá, M., 2016. Stakeholder profile and stakeholder mapping of SMEs. *Littera Scripta*, 9(1), pp.123-139.

Steel, W. F. and Webster, L. M. (1991), "Small Enterprises in Ghana: Responses to Adjustment Industry", Series Paper, No. 33, the World Bank Industry and Energy Department, Washington DC.

Snodgrass, D. R. and J. P. Winkler (2004). *Enterprise Growth Initiatives*. USA: Bethesda.

Sonenshein, S., 2010. We're changing—Or are we? Untangling the role of progressive, regressive, and stability narratives during strategic change implementation. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(3), pp.477-512.

Sundheim, D., 2013. Do women take as many risks as men? *Harvard Business Review*, 91(2).

Saunders, M., Lewis, P.H.I.L.I.P. and Thornhill, A.D.R.I.A.N., 2016. Research methods. *Business Students 7th edition Pearson Education Limited, England*.

Tanner, R., 2017. Unfreeze, change, refreeze: is this a child's game? *Taken from: <https://managementisajourney.com/unfreeze-change-refreeze-is-this-a-childs-game/at> October, 26(2017)*, pp.09-20.

Taylor, A. W., and Adair, R. G. (1994), "Evolution of quality awards and self-assessment practices in Europe: a case for considering organization size", *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 5 No. 4.

Tetteh, E. K., and Essegbey, G. O. (2014). Firm-level innovation: The case of Ghanaian firms. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 2:2, 1-18. www.eajournals.org/wp.../Firm-Level-Innovation-The-Case-of-Ghanaian-Firms.pdf

The global economy.com; Business and economic data for 200 countries https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/Ghana/labor_force/

Trading Economics: Interest Rates, Africa. <https://tradingeconomics.com/country-list/interest-rate?continent=africa> Accessed on [04/12/2021]

Trading Economics: <https://tradingeconomics.com/country-list/ease-of-doing-business?continent=africa>

Torku, K. and Laryea, E., 2021. Corporate governance and bank failure: Ghana's 2018 banking sector crisis. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, pp.1-21.

Tuffour, P., Opoku-Mensah, E., Asiedu-Ayeh, L.O. and Darko, D., 2021. Assessing governments response to exogenous shocks: Considering the COVID-19 pandemic in the Ghanaian context. *Journal of Public Affairs*, p.e2755.

Tunde, O.A. and Abiodun, A.O., 2017. Financing constraints of small and Medium Enterprises in South-Western Nigeria. *International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(6), pp.26-39.

UKEssays. November 2018. Wa Municipal Profile. [online]. Available from: <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/tourism/community-profile-of-the-wa-municipality.php?vref=1> [Accessed 25 August 2020]

UNIDO (1983), *The Potential for Resource-based Industrial Development in the Least Developed Countries*, No.5 - Malawi.

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, “Probabilistic population projections based on the World Population Prospects: The 2017 Revision” (New York: United Nations, 2017). Retrieved from <http://esa.un.org/unpd/wpp/>

West; D and Wood, G. (1972). *Financial Management*. The U.S.A. Hayton Muffin Company.

Wang, Y. (2016). What are the biggest obstacles to growth of SMEs in developing countries? – An empirical evidence. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 16: 3, 167-176. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214845016300539>

Wellalage, N. and Locke, S., 2017. Access to credit by SMEs in South Asia: do women entrepreneurs face discrimination? *Research in International Business and Finance*, 41, pp.336-346.

West; D and Wood, G. (1972). *Financial Management*. U.S.A. Hayton Muffin Company

Weston, J. F. and Copeland, T. E. (1998), “*Managerial Finance*”, CBS College Publishing, New York.

World Economic Forum, World Bank, African Development Bank, and OECD. 2015. “The African Competitiveness Report.” Geneva. http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_ACR_2015/Africa_Competitiveness_Report_2015.pdf.

World Population Review. Most Corrupt Countries 2022. Retrieved Apr 3, 2022, from <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/most-corrupt-countries>

Wu, T., 2010. Strategic Choice: Johnson and Scholes Suitability, Feasibility, and Acceptability Model.

www.appirio.com

XINHUA. Ghana’s Unemployment Rate Rises to 13.4 Percent. 2021. Available online: <https://africa.cgtn.com/2021/12/17/ghanas-unemployment-rate-rises-to-13-4-percent/> (accessed on April 2022).

Yin, R.K. (2003), *Case study research – design and methods*, 3rd Edn, *Applied Social Research Methods Series*, vol.5, Sage Publication, Newbury Park, California

Zeller (1994) Factors Influencing Participation and Credit Constraints of a Financial Self-Help Group in a Remote Rural Area: The Case of ROSCA and ASCRA in Kemang Village West Java: <http://scialert.net/fulltext/?doi=jas.2009.2067>.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: QUESTIONNAIRES FOR SMEs

Abdul-Mumin Bapube Abubakar is a Doctorate of Business Administration candidate at the University of West Scotland, London Campus. The researcher will assist a representative of the sampled SME in completing this questionnaire. The study is on the following topic "The Management and Credit Accessibility Challenges Facing SMEs in Ghana: Proposing an Alternative Solution". The privacy and confidentiality of all respondents and their responses will strictly be respected. All data collected from this survey is purposely for the completion of the above-stated research topic.

Thank you.

Signature:

Section A: Respondent's Information/

1. Gender of the respondent (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i). Male ii) Female

2. Age of respondent (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i. 18-30	<input type="checkbox"/>
ii. 31-40	<input type="checkbox"/>
iii. 41-50	<input type="checkbox"/>
iv. 51-60	<input type="checkbox"/>
v. 61-70	<input type="checkbox"/>
vi. Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Indicate the highest level of education obtained (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i. No formal education	<input type="checkbox"/>
ii. Primary education	<input type="checkbox"/>
iii. Junior High school	<input type="checkbox"/>
iv. Secondary/Technical/Vocational	<input type="checkbox"/>
v. Tertiary	<input type="checkbox"/>
vi. Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section B: Questions on Firm Management

4. Type of enterprise/firm (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i) Sole Proprietor	
ii) Partnership	
iii) Family-Owned Business	
iv) Private Limited Company	
v) Public Limited Company	

5. For how long has the firm been in business? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Less than one year	
ii) Between two and five years	
iii) Between six and ten years	
iv) Between eleven and fifteen years	
v) Over fifteen years	

6. How will one classify the organization? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Micro (Between 1 and 5 employees)	
ii) Small (Between 6 and 30 employees)	
iii) Medium (Between 31 and 100 employees)	
iv) Large (Over 100)	

7. Are there the required number of qualified staff for the organization? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes, there are qualified staff for all the roles	
ii) Yes there are staff for all the roles, but they are not qualified	
iii) No, one person performs multiple roles because there is not enough staff.	

8. What is the highest qualification of the management team? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Senior High School Certificates	
ii) Diploma	
iii) Degree	
iv) Masters	
v) Other (specify).....	

9. Has any member of the management team ever been trained in basic business management practices (bookkeeping, stock management, customer service and financial management,)? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

10. If yes to question 9, which institution offered the training? If no skip to question eleven (11) *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) A university/college	
ii) An NGO	
iii) Government (NBSSI)	
iv) Others.....	

11. Does the organization have an existing business plan? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

12. Does the organization practice standard bookkeeping? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes, all business transactions are recorded and balanced accordingly.	
ii) Yes but sometimes personal finances get mixed up with business capital.	
iii) No, the organization does not keep accounting records at all.	

13. What percentage of profit does the organization make quarterly on its investment capital? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Less than 10%	
ii) Between 10% and 20%	
iii) Between (20% and 30%)	
iv) Between 30% and 50	
v) Between 50% and 100%	
vi) Over 100%	
vii) Please state any percentage loss if applicable.....	

14. Will the organization welcome a well-structured business management training centre in the region that is accessible by all, for practical business training/mentoring purposes with the capacity to train in the local dialect? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

15. If yes, will the organization be willing to pay a token for its services? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

Section C:

The following questions relate to the financing issues of the sampled SMEs: the difficulty in accessing credit, the options available to them as well as some prospects.

16. Has the organization ever applied for a loan facility? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

17. If no, why not? If yes, skip to question eighteen (18) *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) It would not be considered for a loan facility	
ii) Fear of defaulting in repayment due to high interest	
iii) It does not have what it takes to get a loan (collateral)	
iv) Others (specify).....	

18. If yes to question sixteen (16) above, where? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Bank	
ii) Microfinance Institution	
iii) Government (MASLOC)	
iv) Venture Capital Funds	
v) Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	
vi) Others (specify).....	

19. What were the pre-conditions the organization fulfilled before being granted the loan? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Collateral,	
ii) Equity	
iii) Total assets,	
iv) an Audited financial statement (account),	
v) Business plan.	
vi) Other (specify).....	

20. Has the organization ever been refused or denied credit from a credit institute? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

21. If yes to question 20 above, why was the organization refused the loan by the credit institute?

(Please tick the appropriate box)

i) Bad credit history	
ii) No collateral security to pledge	
iii) Not enough deposit or equity base	
iv) Lack of proper management practices	
v) Other (please specify).....	

22. What was the highest amount the organization ever borrowed from a credit institute?

(Please tick the appropriate box).

i) Less than GHC 10,000	
ii) Between GHC 10,000 and GHC 20,000	
iii) Between GHC 20,000 and GHC 30,000	
iv) Between GHC 30,000 and GHC 50,000	
v) Above GHC 50,000	
vi) Not applicable	

23. What was the purpose of the loan acquired? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Startup Capital	
ii) Working Capital	
iii) Expansion of Business	
iv) Other (specify).....	

24. Has the organization ever had a problem repaying a loan? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

25. If the response to question 24 above is yes, what created the problem? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Short payment duration	
ii) A high amount of monthly repayment	
iii) High-Interest rate	
iv) Low turnover	
v) Other (specify).....	

26. What was the loan repayment period? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Up to 1 year	
ii) Up to 2 years	
iii) Up to 3 years	
iv) Other (specify).....	

27. How the organization does generally find lending rates amidst interest charges? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Low (1% to 5%)	
ii) Acceptable (6% to 10%)	
iii) Average (11% to 15%)	
iv) High (16% to 20%)	
v) Extremely High (21% and above)	

28. What are the consequences of defaulting on loan payments?

i) Arrest	
ii) Seizure of valuables	
iii) Naming and shaming in the print media	
iv) Blacklist	
v) Other (specify)...	

29. How was the initial capital raised for the organization? *(Please tick the appropriate boxes)*

i) Personal Savings	
ii) Bank credit	
iii) Friends and relatives	
iv) Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	
v) Other (specify).....	

30. What are the sources of continuous funding for the business? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Bank Loan	
ii) Personal Savings	

iii) Retained Profits	
iv) Private Institutions	
v) Trade Credit	
vi) Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	
vii) Donor	
viii) Family/Friends	
ix) Other (specify).....	

31. What are the significant constraints to the growth of the business? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Lack of Finance	
ii) Competition	
iii) High interest on bank loans	
iv) High government taxes	
v) Inadequate managerial skills	
vii) Lack of the required technology	
vi) Other (specify).....	

32. How has Covid-19 impacted your business?

i) Negatively	
ii) Positively	
iii) No impact	

33. How do you see your business after Covid-19?

i) Fully operating	
ii) Partly operating	
iii) Closed down	
iv) Unable to predict	

Section D: This set of questions is on SME policy recommendation.

34. Is there any policy framework governing SMEs accessing credit in Ghana? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	
iii) I do not know	

35. If No, is there a need for a comprehensive SME policy in the country? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

36. As a management member, what policy recommendations will the organization want to see in place that will ensure a better environment for SME growth in Ghana?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

APPENDIX B: QUESTIONNAIRES FOR SME FINANCING INSTITUTIONS

Abdul-Mumin Bapube Abubakar is a Doctorate of Business Administration candidate at the University of West Scotland, London Campus. The researcher will assist a representative of the sampled SME in completing this questionnaire. The study is on the following topic "The Management and Credit Accessibility Challenge Facing SMEs in Ghana: Proposing an Alternative Solution". The privacy and confidentiality of all respondents and their responses will strictly be respected. All data collected from this survey is purposely for the completion of the above-stated research topic.

Thank you.

Signature:

Section A: Respondent's Information

1. Gender of the respondent (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i). Male ii) Female

2. Age of respondent (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i. 18-30	
ii. 31-40	
iii. 41-50	
iv. 51-60	
v. 61-70	
vi. Other (specify)	

3. Indicate the highest level of education obtained (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i. No formal education	
ii. Primary education	
iii. Junior High school	
iv. Secondary/Technical/Vocational	
v. Tertiary	
vi. Other (specify)	

SECTION B

6. Does the organization have a special facility for SMEs? (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i) Yes	
ii) No	

7. If yes to question 6, state the name of the facility.

.....

8. What percentage of the organization's credit facility has been accessed by SMEs? (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i) Less than 50%	
ii) Between 51% and 60%	
iii) Between 61% and 70%	
iv) Between 71% and 80%	
v) Between 81% and 90%	
vi) Between 91% and 100%	

9. Do you grant credit to start-ups/fresh business ideas? (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i) Yes	
ii) No	

10. If no in question 9 above, how many years would an SME has to be in business in order to qualify for a facility? (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i) Between 1yrs and 5yrs	
ii) Between 6yrs and 10yrs	

iii) Between 11yrs and 15yrs	
------------------------------	--

11. What are the requirements with which SMEs can obtain credit from your institution? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

.....

12. Does this financial institution make a background check to ensure managers of SMEs have basic financial management skills before granting them credit? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

13. Does this financial institution occasionally provide any form of basic financial management training to your clients (SMEs) to increase their chances of surviving their businesses to be able to pay back their loans? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

14. If yes to question 13, what are some of the specific contents you take them through during the training?

.....

15. If no, will the organization welcome a well-structured SME management training centre in the region that is accessible by all, for practical business management training/mentoring purposes with the capacity to train in the local dialect? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

16. What are the organization's annual loan recovery rates for SMEs? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Less than 50%	
ii) Between 51% and 60%	
iii) Between 61% and 70%	
iv) Between 71% and 80%	
v) Between 81% and 90%	

vi) Between 91% and 100%	
--------------------------	--

17. What are the common reasons for loan defaults among SMEs?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

18. As a financial institution, what can be done to bridge the gap between financial institutions and most of the SMEs who for some reason do not want to access your credit facilities?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

19. How has Covid-19 impacted your business?

i) Negatively	
ii) Positively	
iii) No impact	

20. How do you see your business after Covid-19?

i) Fully operating	
ii) Partly operating	
iii) Closed down	
iv) Unable to predict	

21. As a financial institution, what policy recommendations will you want to see in place that will ensure a better environment for SME growth in Ghana?

.....

.....

.....

APPENDIX C: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SME SKILL DEVELOPMENT AND ADVISORY ORGANIZATIONS

Abdul-Mumin Bapube Abubakar is a Doctorate of Business Administration student at the University of West Scotland, London Campus. The researcher will assist a representative of the sampled SME in completing this questionnaire. The study is on the following topic "The Management and Credit Accessibility Challenge Facing SMEs in Ghana: Proposing an Alternative Solution". The privacy and confidentiality of all respondents and their responses will strictly be respected. All data collected from this survey is purposely for the completion of the above-stated research topic.

Thank you.

Signature

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for more information.

Section A: Respondent's Information

1. Gender of the respondent (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i). Male ii) Female

2. Age of respondent (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i. 18-30	<input type="checkbox"/>
ii. 31-40	<input type="checkbox"/>
iii. 41-50	<input type="checkbox"/>
iv. 51-60	<input type="checkbox"/>
v. 61-70	<input type="checkbox"/>
vi. Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Indicate the highest level of education obtained (*Please tick the appropriate box*)

i. No formal education	<input type="checkbox"/>
ii. Primary education	<input type="checkbox"/>
iii. Junior High school	<input type="checkbox"/>
iv. Secondary/Technical/Vocational	<input type="checkbox"/>
v. Tertiary	<input type="checkbox"/>
vi. Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>

SECTION B:

5. What kind of products do the organization offer SMEs? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i). Financial Management Training	
ii). Skills development Training	
iii). Business Advisory Services	
iv). Referral Services	
v). Others Specify.....	

6. Please explain your selected product in question 5 above.

.....

.....

.....

.....

7. How many clients on average access the services of the organization in a year? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Below 20	
ii) Between 21 and 50	
iii) Between 51 and 75	
iv) Between 75 and 100	
v) Above 100	

8. Does the organization follow up on its clients to monitor their progress after providing your services? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

9. How does the organization measure the progress of its clients? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Annual turnover	
ii) Size of employees	
iii) Size of production	
iv) Number of branches	
v) Other (Specify).....	

10. What average percentage of clients will the organization consider to have improved yearly? *(Interviewer to assist with calculations) Please tick the appropriate box*

i) Less than 10%	
ii) Between 10% and 20%	
iii) Between (20% and 30%)	
iv) Between 30% and 50	
v) Between 50% and 100%	
vi) Over 100%	

9. As an advisory institution, please list five common challenges faced by your clients (SMEs). Kindly specify in order of ranking.

- i.....
- ii.....
- iii.....
- iv.....
- v.....

10. As an advisory institution, how can the challenges listed in question 9 above be solved?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

11. Will this advisory institution recommend basic financial management training as a mandatory basic requirement for accessing credit by SMEs in the country? *(Please tick the appropriate box)*

i) Yes	
ii) No	

12. If yes in question 11 above, what are some of the specific contents you will recommend for the training?

.....

.....

.....

13. Does this advisory institution also provide credit/Grants to SMEs?

i) Yes	
ii) No	

14. If yes to question 13 above, in what way?

.....
.....
.....

15. How has Covid-19 impacted your business?

i) Negatively	
ii) Positively	
iii) No impact	

16. How do you see your business after Covid-19?

i) Fully operating	
ii) Partly operating	
iii) Closed down	
iv) Unable to predict	

17. Does Ghana has a national SME policy?

i). Yes	
ii). No	
iii) I don't know	

18. As an advisory institution, what policy recommendations will you want to see in place that will ensure a better environment for SME growth in Ghana?

.....
.....
.....

APPENDIX D: CHINA ON THE VERGE OF BECOMING THE WORLD'S LARGEST ECONOMY BY 2030

APPENDIX E: INTEREST RATES OF AFRICAN COUNTRIES

Country	Last Interest rates	Previous	Reference	Unit
Cape Verde	0.25	0.25	Oct/21	%
Comoros	0.94	0.94	Mar/21	%
Morocco	1.5	1.5	Oct/21	%
Mauritius	1.85	1.85	Oct/21	%
Seychelles	2	2	Sep/21	%
Algeria	3	3	Jul/21	%
Libya	3	3	Oct/21	%
Cameroon	3.25	3.25	Oct/21	%
The Central African Republic	3.25	3.25	Oct/21	%
Chad	3.25	3.25	Oct/21	%
Equatorial Guinea	3.25	3.25	Oct/21	%
Gabon	3.25	3.25	Oct/21	%
Republic of the Congo	3.25	3.25	Oct/21	%
Lesotho	3.5	3.5	Oct/21	%
Botswana	3.75	3.75	Dec/21	%
Namibia	3.75	3.75	Oct/21	%

South Africa	3.75e	3.5	Nov/21	%
Swaziland	3.75	3.75	Nov/21	%
Benin	4	4	Oct/21	%
Burkina Faso	4	4	Oct/21	%
Guinea Bissau	4	4	Oct/21	%
Ivory Coast	4	4	Oct/21	%
Mali	4	4	Sep/21	%
Niger	4	4	Oct/21	%
Senegal	4	4	Oct/21	%
Togo	4	4	Oct/21	%
Rwanda	4.5	4.5	Nov/21	%
Mauritania	5	5	Oct/21	%
Tanzania	5	5	Nov/21	%
Tunisia	6.25	6.25	Oct/21	%
Uganda	6.5	6.5	Oct/21	%
Ethiopia	7	7	Jun/21	%
Kenya	7	7	Nov/21	%
Burundi	7.06	7.04	Jun/21	%
Egypt	8.25	8.25	Oct/21	%
Congo	8.5	8.5	Oct/21	%
Sao Tome and Principe	9	9	Oct/21	%
Zambia	9	8.5	Nov/21	%
Madagascar	9.5	9.5	Oct/21	%
The Gambia	10	10	Oct/21	%
Guinea	11.5	11.5	Oct/21	%
Nigeria	11.5	11.5	Nov/21	%
Malawi	12	12	Oct/21	%
Mozambique	13.25	13.25	Nov/21	%
Sierra Leone	14	14	Oct/21	%
Ghana	14.5	14.5	Nov/21	%
South Sudan	15	15	May/21	%
Sudan	17.1	19.3	Aug/21	%
Angola	20	20	Nov/21	%
Liberia	20	20	Oct/21	%
Zimbabwe	60	40	Oct/21	%